

LITERATURE REVIEW OF REGIONAL OR INTERNATIONAL WATER DIPLOMACY SUCCESS STORIES AND LESSONS LEARNED ON IMPLEMENTED METHODOLOGY

Jordan River

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This report summarizes the key findings of the desk study “**Literature Review of Regional or International Water Diplomacy Success Stories and Lessons Learned on Implemented Methodology**”, developed by the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Yarmouk University with support from Water Diplomacy Center (WDC), Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan. The findings are based on an extensive literature review, consultation with an expert of regional and international panel. In total, 259 publications were studied and 16 experts from international institutions, NGOs, government entities, the private sector and academia were involved in the development of the Water Diplomacy Index (WDI). The project team is grateful for the support of experts who have volunteered their time to inform the content of the index. We are also indebted to the valuable comments of the WDC reviewers.

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1. Background

Water is essential for human development. It is essential for society's livelihood support system, and its management is crucial for economic prosperity and poverty alleviation. Water is also a critical factor for regional cooperation and development (Wolf, 2010; UNEP-DHI and UNEP, 2016). Transboundary waters are the aquifers and lake and river basins shared by two or more countries. It is estimated that 313 rivers and lakes, and 468 aquifers, are shared by two or more countries, and a total of 153 UN Member States rely on waters that either flow from or flow to another country (Figure 1). Transboundary rivers alone account for 60% of the world's freshwater flows, and river and lake basins are home to more than three billion people (UNECE and UNESCO, 2024). While transboundary water cooperation is essential for advancing sustainable development, only 43 out of 153 UN Member States sharing transboundary waters have 90% or more of these waters covered by cooperative arrangements that are operational, and over 20 countries lack any such arrangements. Europe, North America and sub-Saharan Africa show the highest levels of cooperation; whereas across Asia, Latin America and North Africa only 4 out of 69 countries have 90% or more of their basin area covered (UNECE and UNESCO, 2024). By 2030, water demand is projected to exceed sustainable supply by 40%, increasing the potential for conflict over these resources (UNEP, 2015). Conflicts over shared water resources are evident among many countries, e.g., the Nile River. Such a situation reinforces the importance of dialogue, research and capacity building to better understand how to best manage water for regional development.

Water diplomacy refers to managing and resolving transboundary water disputes and fostering cooperation through dialogue, mediation, negotiation, and agreements. Examples like the Euphrates-Tigris Initiative for Cooperation (ETIC) highlight the success of water diplomacy in uniting communities and fostering peaceful cooperation (Kibaroglu, 2020). ETIC is an academic initiative founded in 2005 by scholars from Iraq, Syria, Türkiye and the USA. Its principal aim is to provide opportunities to enhance dialogue and mutual understanding among riparian states of the Euphrates-Tigris System. It is dedicated to improving the living conditions of the people in both rural and urban areas in the Euphrates Tigris region, strengthening cooperation and sustainable development in harmony with nature using scientific means, advocacy, research and education (ICBA, 2024).

There are two tracks of water diplomacy:

A) Formal Diplomacy

Official/Formal communication between state actors with the authority and mandate to speak and make decisions on behalf of their governments or institutions.

B) Informal Diplomacy

Dialogue between non-officials to build relations, resolve conflict, manage a crisis or build trust, based on agreed mandate, roles and responsibilities. Such parties include academics, NGOs, People, etc.

Figure 1: Global Transboundary River Basins (UNESCO-IGRAC, 2015).

The Blue Peace Index is a research tool that measures how well countries manage transboundary water resources. The index scores each basin, and the countries that fall within them, according to five categories (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020):

- 1) Policy and legal frameworks: Are national and international policies in place to protect resources?
- 2) Institutions and Participation: Do the necessary mechanisms for collaboration exist and are all stakeholders engaged?
- 3) Water Management Instruments: Are water availability and pollution measured, and disaster risks monitored?
- 4) Infrastructure and Financing: Is funding to develop water resources available from national, international and private sources?
- 5) Co-operation context: Are water resources under pressure, and does the political and socio-economic context support cooperation?

By 2020, the index was determined in seven selected river basins. Table 1 and figure 2 shows the investigated river basins: Amazon, Amu Darya, Mekong, Sava, Senegal, Syr Darya, and Euphrates and Tigris. Table 2 highlights (**bold**) the basins with index value below the average value for each category, e.g., The Mekong River score for Policy and legal frameworks is below the category average although its overall score is 55

(The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). River basins with an index value below the overall average value include Amu Darya, Syr Darya, Euphrates-Tigris.

Figure 2: Selected River basins assessed for the Blue Peace Index.

Table 1: The riparian states of the river basins indexed by Blue Peace.

River Basin	Riparian States
Amazon	Brazil, Peru, Colombia, Venezuela, Ecuador, Bolivia, Guyana
Amu Darya	Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan
Mekong	China, Myanmar, Laos, Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam
Sava	Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia
Senegal	Guinea, Mali, Senegal, Mauritania
Syr Darya	Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan
Euphrates and Tigris	Turkey, Syria, Iraq, Iran

Table 2: Blue Peace Index of selected river basins (Blue Peace, 2024).

River Basin	Overall score (49.1)	Category score (average value)				
		Policy and legal frameworks (53.9)	Institutions and participation (55.9)	Water management instruments (45.6)	Infrastructure and financing (39.1)	Co-operation context (51)
Amazon	54.2	55.3	61.8	47.9	43.5	62.7
Amu Darya	37.3	42.4	46.6	32.3	30.8	34.5
Mekong	55	49.1	63.4	63.2	43..4	55.9
Sava	67.9	88.6	68.1	65.6	48.2	69
Senegal	56.2	57	69.8	49	51.5	53.7
Syr Darya	48.1	52.7	58	41.7	38.4	49.8
Euphrates and Tigris	25	32	23.3	19.8	18.2	31.4

2. Project Objectives

The goal of this project is to conduct a comprehensive literature review of regional and international water diplomacy success stories. The specific objectives are:

- a) To identify the methodologies implemented, assess their effectiveness, and extract valuable lessons and best practices.
- b) To guide future water diplomacy efforts, promote cooperation, and ensure sustainable management of shared water resources based on the lessons learned from success stories.
- c) To build capabilities of the Water Diplomacy Center (WDC) by enhancing current knowledge, fostering partnerships, and mediation to ensure equitable and peaceful solutions for countries sharing water resources. This aligns with the WDC's mission to advance water diplomacy by serving as a hub for knowledge, partnerships, and mediation.

3. Research Questions

- a) What are the characteristics of successful regional or international water diplomacy initiatives?
- b) What methodologies and frameworks have been used in these successful cases?
- c) What key factors contribute to the positive outcomes of water diplomacy efforts?
- d) What are the common challenges faced in water diplomacy, and how have successful initiatives addressed them?

4. Methodology

4.1 Data collection

To address this objective, a systematic bibliometric analysis was conducted across Web of Science, SCOPUS, Research Gate, and Google Scholar, and government & international organization websites such as UN Water, World Bank, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), etc. utilizing search terms related to Water Diplomacy. The keywords for the search for success stories included water diplomacy, water cooperation, water conflicts, water sharing agreements, water governance, water resources management, transboundary water institutions. The identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion criteria considered in the identification and selection of the specific literature included in this study are as follows:

- a) Only publications that are relevant to water diplomacy (a focus on water diplomacy initiatives)
- b) Only publications that are related to shared water resources
- c) Publications that have a clear demonstration positive and negative outcomes
- d) Only publications that elaborated on the methodology description (a detailed explanation of methodologies used in the initiative.
- e) Only publications from high quality reputable indexed journals, reports and official websites.
- f) Only publications used the English Language.

4.2 Analysis framework

Analysis framework encompassed qualitative content analysis approach to identify themes, recurring strategies, and factors contributing to success, analyzing the methodologies and extracting lessons learned, focusing on key aspects such as negotiation processes, stakeholder involvement, legal and institutional frameworks, and technological innovations. Criteria for evaluating the success of the methodologies were established, including the resolution of conflicts, sustainability of water management practices, and stakeholder satisfaction.

4.3 Water Diplomacy Index (WDI)

The WDI is developed to evaluate the success of water diplomacy in the management of transboundary water resources. The WDI is based on selected criteria of the success stories, where each story (river basin) assigned a score of a maximum 100 designating its level of efficiency based on the evaluation criteria. The criteria were derived from lessons learned from successful management of worldwide transboundary water resources and the opinions of international and regional expert. The final list of criteria was ranked by the same experts according to their importance to the management of shared water resources. Each criterion was ranked on a scale of 1 to 10, where 1 represents the least important and 10 represents the most crucial factor in successful water diplomacy. The preliminary proposed criteria were modified continuously to incorporate the experts'

knowledge on the subject. The mean rank value for each criterion was used to calculate the WDI. Additionally, the experts assigned a key aspect of water diplomacy that fits most appropriately for each criterion based on Keskinen et al. (2021). Keskinen et al. (2021) identified five water diplomacy aspects that include, *Technical, Cooperative, Integrative, Preventive, and Political* (Table 3). For this study, each water diplomacy aspect was assigned a weight value in reference to how many water diplomacy criteria it included. This is explained by the fact that an aspect with a higher number of criteria can be more important than an aspect with lower number of water diplomacy criteria. For example, there three criteria in the Integrative and Preventive aspects, i.e., assigned a weight value 3, while the Cooperative aspect assigned a weight value 6 because it contains 6 criteria. The **WDI** is calculated according to the following formula:

$$WDI_{RB} = 100 * [(WDA_w * \Sigma C_{WRB}) / (WDA_w * \Sigma C_w)] \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

where WDI_{RB} is the water diplomacy index of a river basin, C_{WRB} is the sum of weights for a river basin, WDA_w is water diplomacy aspect weight, C_w is criteria weight.

In this study, five shared river basins were assessed for their WDI: the Rhine River Basin (RRB), the Columbia River Basin (CRB), the Senegal River Basin (SRB), Yarmouk River Basin (YRB), and the Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB). These river basins were chosen because they showed represent various geographic regions and showed various levels of transboundary water management and cooperation.

Table 3: Key aspects of water diplomacy, together with examples of related key approaches and mechanisms (Keskinen et al. 2021).

Water diplomacy aspect	Examples of related key approaches, frameworks and mechanisms
TECHNICAL: providing an information basis for the diplomacy about water, related resources and the environment.	Information on hydrology, water quantity, quality and timing; knowledge production and products such as hydrological models and impact assessments
COOPERATIVE: Cooperation and good governance to promote reasonable and equitable water use.	Cooperative arrangements; benefit sharing approaches; international agreements on shared waters; sustainability
INTEGRATIVE: Connecting multiple forms and levels of institutions and stakeholders and the different types of knowledge.	Multi-track Diplomacy; Integrative Diplomacy; Integrated Water Resources Management; knowledge co-production
PREVENTIVE: Peace mediation and conflict prevention.	Preventive diplomacy; peace mediation and peace building; conflict resolution
POLITICAL: Inherently political process that goes far beyond water per se; part of wider diplomatic setting and geopolitics.	The most strongly political track: critical hydropolitics; geopolitics; foreign policy; regional cooperation

4.4 Dissemination Plan

The dissemination plan for the results of this project will include the following 3 methods:

- a) **Report Distribution:** the final report will be widely disseminated to relevant stakeholders, including:
 - 1) Government agencies that deal with water resources management and foreign affairs.
 - 2) International organizations focused on water diplomacy and sustainable development.
 - 3) Academic institutions and research centers specializing in water resources and international relations.
 - 4) Water management NGOs and advocacy groups.
- b) **Publication:** a summary of the key findings will be submitted for publication in relevant academic journals or water diplomacy newsletters (open-access options will be prioritized to maximize accessibility).
- c) **Presentations:** presentations could be delivered at conferences and workshops on water resource management and international relations in coordination with the Water Diplomacy Center.

5. Results

5.1 Background

The study aimed at examining the extent of success in managing shared water resources worldwide including river basins, aquifers and lakes. More than 259 publications (Table 4) using the above-mentioned keywords underwent thorough analysis. The literature investigation included 51 publications dealing with water diplomacy and water cooperation related to transboundary water resources, laying the foundation for reviewing case studies. The collected literatures were categorized by geographical region: Africa, Asia, Europe, Middle East, North America, and South America.

Table 4: Number and type of literature investigated for this study.

No.	Topic/Geographic area	No. of resources
1	Middle East Shared Water Resources	67
2	Africa Shared Water Resources	36
3	Europe Shared Water Resources	38
4	Asian Shared Water Resources	53
5	North America Shared Water Resources	14

Thirty shared water resources were investigated (Table 5), including twenty-three river basins, five lakes, and two aquifers. These shared water resources are distributed geographically as shown in table 4: 4 river basins

from Africa, 10 from Asia, 3 from Europe, 4 from the Middle East, and 2 from North America, 3 lakes from Africa, one lake from Europe and another from North America. Additionally, two main African transboundary aquifers were studied; the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System and the Northwestern Sahara Aquifer System. The investigated cases are arranged alphabetically. Each study consists of four key sections:

- a. **Background:** it addresses the geography and characteristics of the water resource.
- b. **Problems and Motivations:** it lays the background for the problems encountered in sharing water resources and the reasons that developed cooperation between the riparian countries.
- c. **Cooperation methods:** this section addresses all aspects of cooperation chronologically.
- d. **Lessons learned:** the lessons learned from each case of disputes and cooperation are addressed for the purpose of knowledge dissemination.

Table 5: Transboundary water resources investigated in this study.

Region	River Basin	Lakes	Aquifer
Middle East	Euphrates-Tigris Basin, Jordan River Basin, Orontes River Basin, & Yarmouk River Basin.		Disi Aquifer
Africa	Niger River Basin, Orange River Basin, Senegal River Basin, & Zembezi River Basin.	Chad Lake, Tanganyika Lake, & Victoria Lake.	African Transboundary Aquifers (TBA)
Europe	Danube River Basin, Iberian Rivers, & Rhine River Basin.	Baltic Sea	
Central Asia	Amu Darya River Basin, Irtysh River Basin, & Syr Darya River Basin		
South Asia	Aras River Basin, Barhamaputra River Basin, Ganges River Basin, Harirud River Basin, Koshi River Basin, Mekong River Basin, & Saralbhanga River Basin		
North America	Columbia River Basin Delaware River Basin	Great Lakes	

5.2 Case Studies

5.2.1 Africa

Examples from Africa are represented by five river basins, three lakes and transboundary aquifers.

River Basin	Lakes	Aquifer
Niger River Basin, Orange River Basin, Senegal River Basin, & Zembezi River Basin	Chad Lake, Tanganyika Lake, & Victoria Lake	African TBAs (The Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System and The Northwestern Sahara Aquifer System)

The Niger River Basin (NRB)

Background

Niger River is the 3rd longest river in Africa and the 9th longest river in the world with an approximate length of 4200 km and its tributaries include river Benue (1200 km), (Oguntunde & Abiodun 2013). The Niger River Basin (NRB) is the largest transboundary basin in West Africa and occupies an area of about 2.2 million km², including part of Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Guinea, Côte d'Ivoire, Mali, Niger, and Nigeria (Figure 3) (Andersson et al., 2017; World Bank Group, 2021) The Niger originates near the Fouta Djallon

Mountains in the South of Guinea at an elevation of roughly 800 m, whereas the basin's population density is high; the total basin population is around 100 million (Andersson et al., 2017; World Bank Group, 2021). The Niger river is vital for the socioeconomic development of the region contributing between 20% and 50% of the Gross Domestic Product for the African countries within its basin, as well as being mainly responsible for agriculture, food security and employment (World Bank Group, 2021). The river is an important natural resource that is often key for livelihoods, particularly in Mali and Niger (Andersson et al., 2017). It is vital for cities like Bamako, Niamey and Abuja, for both domestic drinking water provision and irrigation. The Niger River also forms a backbone of energy security in this region where the installed hydropower capacity equals to 2,000 megawatts, although much of this potential remains underdeveloped (World Bank Group, 2021).

Figure 3: The Niger River Basin, and locations of major reservoir dams in the basin: (1) Selingue, (2) Markala, (3) Goronyo, (4) Bakolori, (5) Kainji, (6) Jebba, (7) Dadin Kowa, and (8) Lagdo (Yue et al., 2022).

Problems and Motivations

The large-scale decrease in rainfall across the Sahel resulted in large-scale disasters including the **droughts and famines of the 1970s and 1980s** (Andersson et al., 2017; Mahe et al., 2013). The basin experiences extreme climatic events, including **periodic droughts and intense floods**, with significant consequences for local livelihoods, agriculture and human security (International Alert, 2011). Floods are an increasing threat killing people and damaging infrastructure, causing family tragedies, incurring expensive repair bills and disrupting transport. Some of the continued flooding (e.g., 2008 and 2016) have been attributed to climatic variability but also to changes in land use (Aich et al., 2015). This region has been defined as an area where future **changes in climate** could be particularly impactful (Diallo et al., 2016; Andersson et al., 2017). This combination of factors, in addition to **large dams** and small-scale abstractions, makes it difficult to manage water resources in the region and poses challenges to sustainable development (International Alert, 2011).

In recent years, the **competition for water resources** due to growing demand, increased environmental degradation, and climate variability have made the Niger River Basin a long-standing hotspot for conflicts among its riparian states. The first major dispute arose after the creation of the **Niger Basin Authority (NBA)**

in 1964 — an institution intended to promote cooperation among the basin nations, such as Mali, Niger and Nigeria. Powers were only mandated with the NBA to manage disputes, but the NBA **struggled to manage the situation effectively**, with limited funding and political instability limiting power enforcement of cooperative water management strategies (Grossmann, 2006). One of the early controversies was **the construction of the Kainji Dam in Nigeria**, which finished in **1968**. This dam radically changed the natural flow of the Niger River, with negative consequences for agriculture and fisheries especially in neighboring countries such as Niger and Benin. This led to reduced water availability for downstream countries who would see their local economies crippled, augmented tensions with Nigeria because of their water management practices (International Alert, 2011).

By the **1970s and 1980s**, the basin faced **extended periods of drought** that intensified competition over water. At those times the countries in the basin were in a more acute state of competition for access to water for its agricultural and pastoral uses, with tensions especially high between Mali, Niger and Nigeria. The disputes in the basin have been further escalated by the commissioning of **the Sélingué Dam in Mali in 1982**. Construction of the dam fundamentally shifted the river's hydrology, hindering water flow downstream to communities in Niger and Nigeria, limiting their crop yields and the availability of surface water. It also exacerbated tensions between **farmers and pastoralists** in these countries dependent on this river for irrigation and livestock during crucial farming periods (Thébaud and Batterbury, 2001; Goulden & Few, 2011). Severe flooding events are no stranger to Nigeria, as was evidenced **in 2001 as millions of people were displaced by flooding** events that caused thousands of dollars' worth of damage to crops and infrastructure. The floods, which had the effect of entrenching pre-existing tensions, led to complaints from impacted communities across Nigeria claiming that upstream planning decisions exacerbated the impact of the floods (International Alert, 2011). The struggle to control the consequences of both floods and droughts further sharpened the competition for deteriorating water resources during this time. In the early 2000s, identified herd pathways were introduced in Mali to reduce conflicts between the pastoralists and farmers. Yet these efforts did not eliminate the underlying tensions as new land investments and climate variability continued to put pressure on traditional resource management mechanisms in the region (Benjaminsen et al., 2010; International Alert, 2011). **In 2008, Nigeria and Niger went to war over water** during a drought, something that reflected the persistent problems brought by managing the flow of the Niger River. **The negotiations in 2008 ended without an agreement on water allocation**; they were inhibited by **longstanding distrust between the riparian countries**, particularly between Mali and Niger on the one hand and Nigeria on the other hand, which feared Nigeria's unilateral decisions on water management (Scheumann & Neubert, 2006). **The Niger Basin Water Charter, ratified in 2010**, aims to consolidate the evolution of cooperation over time in order to resolve these challenges. Yet its implementation has been slow, while conflicts over dam constructions (like that of the Kandadji Dam in Niger) have continued and have put downstream countries in

fear of scarce water for farming and fishing, which makes it even more challenging to reach sustainable management of the basin's resources. In addition, **political instability**, especially in **Mali and Burkina Faso since 2015**, has been an added complication in regional cooperation to manage the Niger River Basin. Due to the internal conflicts in some of these countries their involvement in cooperative water management programs has been limited leading to a cycle of conflict and scarce resources continuing in the region (World Bank Group, 2021).

Cooperation methods

Several treaties, conventions and initiatives have been signed for transboundary cooperation on the NRB, promoting sustainable water management and conflict resolution in the riparian countries. The cooperation began with the founding of the **Niger Basin Commission in 1964**, an organization which was subsequently transformed in **1980** into the **Niger Basin Authority (NBA)**. The NBA was assigned to improve cooperation between the basin's member states, as well as the basin's integrated management and development of water resources. This was succeeded by the **Niger Basin Water Charter signed in 1992**. The charter was a critical legal framework to guide equitable allocation and sustainable management practices by the nine riparian states (Scheumann & Neubert, 2006). **The 2004 Paris Declaration** was a pivotal moment that sought to enhance regional cooperation, where the riparian nations agreed to jointly develop and sustainably manage shared water resources. Based on this, the **Shared Vision Process (SVP)** was set in motion reconfirming the role of the NBA as a coordinating entity and culminating in the adoption of a **Sustainable Development Action Plan (SDAP)** to the basin in **2007**. This was **followed in April 2008 by an 8 billion US\$ 20-year investment program**, supported by the World Bank and other international donors. The program consisted of the **building of three major dams** in the upper basin, the Fomi Dam in Guinea, the Taoussa Dam in Mali, and the Kandadji Dam in Niger which would all operate in cascade to optimize water management. This has been made possible by the implementation of the **Lending Program in the Niger River Basin**, which is a crucial part of this effort and has helped to develop and implement the necessary tools for the water resources shared management and development of the basin. The outcomes of this program have paved the way for SVP adoption among Niger Basin member states, which prioritized its investments and advance regional cooperation (World Bank Group, 2021). **The Niger Basin Water Charter ratification in 2010** represented another victory in regional cooperation. This charter sought to create a full legal framework to govern transboundary waters, with provisions for the coordinated management of dams and the equitable sharing of benefits. **The Kandadji Program, which started in 2013**, has the same objectives as it seeks to maximize the optimization of water storage with impact on regional, national and local scales. This program focuses on improving water security, agricultural development, and safeguarding biodiversity while prioritizing the reduction of social and environmental impacts. A major project linked to this program, the Kandadji Dam project, **is anticipated to**

support around 33,000 project-affected individuals through innovative resettlement approaches (World Bank Group, 2021). The need for collaborative approaches is further underlined by the signature of the **Agreement on the Management of Water Resources in the Niger River Basin in 2013** on the effective management of water utilizing its resources (International Alert, 2011). **In 2015**, the **Niger Basin Climate Resilience Investment Plan** was endorsed in response to the increasing challenges of climate change. This framework reinforces the regional determination to strengthen resilience with actionable investments, showcasing the continuous collaboration to foster sustainable growth and prevent regional strife within the Niger River Basin through a collaborative approach among the river countries. **In 2019**, the NBA further solidified its institutional framework with the formal adoption of an **annex to the Water Charter that focused on the cooperative management of dams**. This annex established a political framework for the integrated management of water resources, which is one of the most relevant aspects of potential conflict that could be raised in the basin (World Bank Group, 2021).

Lessons learned

- 1) **The need for collaborative frameworks and legal agreements** on transboundary water resources for optimal allocation to maintain sustainability and peaceful use among riparian states. For example, the **Niger Basin Authority (NBA)** was established, allowing for cooperation among the nine riparian countries in 1980, leading to the adoption of the **1992 Niger Basin Water Charter** which emphasized principles of equitable water sharing and sustainable management.
- 2) The necessity of **integrating local communities into decision-making processes** has been emphasized, as their involvement can enhance the legitimacy and effectiveness of water management strategies.
- 3) The Niger River Basin emphasize **the importance of adaptive management** in the face of climate variability and changing socio-economic conditions, which involves ongoing monitoring and flexibility in governance strategies.

Orange-Senqu River Basin (OSRB)

Background

The Orange-Senqu River, which runs for 2300 km, starts in Lesotho and is locally named the Senqu (Figure 4). This river system covers nearly the whole plateau of South Africa, with its basin extending over around one million km² across four nations: Lesotho, South Africa, Namibia, and Botswana. South Africa holds most of the basin at 64.2%, while Namibia accounts for 24.5%, Botswana 7.9%, and Lesotho 3.4% (Wolf, 1995; Conley & van Niekerk, 2000; Sadoff & Grey, 2002). The Orange-Senqu River Basin (**OSRB**) includes all of Lesotho and reaches into major South African urban centers such as Johannesburg, South Africa's most

populous city, and Soweto, located in Gauteng Province, the country's wealthiest region (Sebastian, 2008). Approximately 14.5 million people reside within the basin, underscoring its role as a critical water source and economic lifeline for the region.

Figure 4: The Orange-Senqu River Basin (Lange et al.,2007).

The average yearly natural runoff from the entire basin is estimated to be around 11,900 million cubic meters annually. Because of numerous developments and an increasing number of water users, less than half of this flow makes it to the river's mouth (ORASECOM, 2008). The river navigates through diverse climatic zones and ecological systems, which greatly influences its hydrology and management strategies. The river originates in Lesotho's eastern highlands, benefiting from relatively favorable climate conditions, but as it moves westward, it encounters increasingly arid landscapes that pose challenges for water resource management (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000).

Problems and Motivations

Disputes among the riparian countries of the Orange River basin—particularly South Africa, Namibia, and Lesotho—have primarily revolved around water allocation, management, and ecological preservation. The **Lesotho Highlands Water Project (LHWP), initiated in the late 1980s**, has been a significant source of tension. The construction of dams and reservoirs in Lesotho, as part of this project, altered natural flow patterns, which **impacted water availability for downstream users** in South Africa and raised concerns among local communities in Lesotho about the equitable distribution of benefits (Hirji & Duda, 1995).

In **1989, tensions escalated over the construction of the Katse Dam in the Lesotho Maluti Mountains**. The dam, completed in 1997, **provides 72 megawatts of electricity for Lesotho and supplies South Africa with water**. The dam **raised concerns in Namibia** about potential reductions in water availability (Wolf, 1998). These concerns were compounded by historical conflicts over grazing rights and water access, highlighted by **violent clashes in 1991** between communities along the river. These clashes underscored the deep-seated ethnic and resource-based tensions that underlie many of the disputes in the region (Wolf, 1998). Ever since Namibia achieved independence in 1990, the country had become increasingly worried about its entitlement to the river water, and this was especially true with the growing **expansion of the LHWP** by South Africa. This would drastically **reduce Namibia's water supply**, potentially endangering its development and ecological integrity (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000). Namibia has therefore sought to assert its rights to water released from South African storage facilities and demanded clarification of its border with South Africa along the Orange River. The fear is that low water allocations may be damaging to Namibian agricultural and domestic water demands, as well as its ecological balance (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000). Moreover, the **establishment of irrigation schemes** on the Orange River has created additional problems over water rights. Such projects can change both the flow and the quality of water that flows downstream into other countries, fueling tensions over how the river's resources ought to be shared. The ecological value of the **Orange River estuary**, which is recognized as a **Ramsar wetland**, adds an additional dimension to these conflicts. As such, this estuary needs to be managed collaboratively such that the biodiversity conservation goals are in balance with the economic requirements of the local communities (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000).

Cooperation Methods

The governments of the four **riparian states** recognize the severe scarcity of water resources in the Southern African region. They have **committed to working together to manage and develop the river system sustainably as a shared water resource**. This collaboration aims to significantly benefit all parties by promoting mutual prosperity, peace, security, and the well-being of their populations (ORASECOM, 2008). As a critical transboundary resource linking multiple drainage basins in South Africa, the river exemplifies

the necessity of integrated river basin management to optimize sustainable utilization and ensure equitable access among all stakeholders (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000).

Cooperation around the Orange-Senqu River regarding transboundary conflicts has evolved significantly over the years. **The Lesotho Highlands Water Project (LHWP)** (Figure 5) was designed to divert water from the Lesotho Highlands to South Africa, primarily to meet the growing water demands of urban areas like Johannesburg and to generate hydroelectric power for Lesotho. The Lesotho Highlands Water Project (LHWP) is a multi-phased project to provide water to the Gauteng region of South Africa and to generate hydroelectricity for Lesotho. It was established by the 1986 Treaty signed by the governments of the Kingdom of Lesotho and the Republic of South Africa. The project entails harnessing the waters of the Senqu/Orange River in the Lesotho highlands through the construction of a series of dams for the mutual benefit of the two countries. Phase I of the project was completed in 2003, and Phase II is currently underway. The Treaty governing the LHWP and the Phase II Agreement commits both Parties to take “all reasonable measures to ensure that the implementation, operation and maintenance of the project are compatible with the protection and the existing quality of the environment and, in particular, shall pay due regard to the maintenance of the welfare of the persons and communities immediately affected by the Project”. The **Lesotho Highlands Development Authority (LHDA)** is therefore mandated to ensure that the risks associated with resettlement are addressed and that the livelihoods of affected people are restored (Wallis, 1996; Conley & van Niekerk, 2000; LHDA, 2024). Together, they crafted an agreement that improved the water resource development in Lesotho while also **restricting environmental degradation** and maximizing the benefits for both nations (Hirji, 1998). This agreement is also a good example of cooperation in international water laws. Consequently, **public participation** and detailed hydrologic studies were part of the **1994 Orange River Replanning Study (ORRS)**. This study focused on the river’s minimum flow requirements and other control measures necessary for ecological protection (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000).

In 1995, the Treaty on the **Development and Utilization of the Water Resources of the Orange River Basin** was signed, which provided an equally reasonable and fair use of shared waters along with proper environmental care (Conley & van Niekerk, 2000). **The Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Shared Watercourse Systems, signed in 1995**, also underscored the region's commitment to cooperation. The protocol sought to foster regional cooperation in the management of water resources and confirmed the need for equitable use and sustainable management of shared water resources between member states, including South Africa and Namibia (Wolf, 1998).

In 2000, all riparian countries established the **Orange-Senqu River Commission (ORASECOM)**, which is tasked with the joint management of the river basin and ensuring equitable allocation of water by the member countries. ORASECOM has carried out transboundary water projects, exchanged data, and designed measures to address challenges such as water scarcity and environmental sustainability. It has a circular role in allowing

countries to discuss and agree on water projects such as dams and irrigation systems that can be beneficial to all countries involved.

Figure 5: The Lesotho Highlands Water Project (Delves et al, 2021).

This commission was responsible for the management of the 1995 SADC Protocol on Shared Watercourse Systems and aims to promote the sustainable management and development of the river's water (Hirji, 1998; Wolf, 1998). Finally, the **Integrated Water Resource Plan (ORBMP) for the Orange River Basin** for the year **2002** defined principles of integrated water resource management, elaborating on issues such as pollution management, ecosystem protection and equity between users. This plan also illustrated how cooperation is often critical to the effective management of transboundary water resources, integrating development requirements with the environmental sustainability of the Orange River Basin (Hirji, 1998).

The Orange River, flowing through Lesotho, South Africa, Namibia, and Botswana, **serves as a prime example of successful international cooperation in water management** due to its significant geopolitical and hydrological characteristics (Sadoff & Grey, 2002).

Lessons learned

- 1) **Cooperative Framework:** The countries sharing the river need a cooperative framework. **ORASECOM** encourages the integrated nature of water resource management for South Africa, Lesotho, Namibia, and Botswana through a commission promoting cooperation on projects, such as the Lesotho Highlands Water Project which serves upstream and downstream needs.
- 2) **Effective Communication:** Trust between stakeholders is critical. Face-to-face meetings and joint planning sessions among member states and their ORASECOM committees have also facilitated dialogue and data sharing, thereby addressing concerns about both water quality and quantity, and defusing the potential for conflict.
- 3) **Comprehensive Legal Framework:** A clear legal framework is a prerequisite for water allocation and usage. The **2000 ORASECOM Agreement** establishes an equitable utilization framework which sets a set of structured provisions that would facilitate to pre-empt conflicts on sharing a common limited resource.
- 4) **Environmental Considerations:** Incorporating environmental considerations are crucial for the river's well-being. **The ORBMP** regulates water quality and protects ecosystems to ensure sustainability for human use and ecological integrity.
- 5) **Integrated Development Projects:** ORASECOM advocates for projects that are beneficial to multiple countries. Shared irrigation systems and water structures are among them. These projects bring countries closer together and promote greater collaboration.

Senegal River Basin (SRB)

Background

The Senegal River, which flows for 1,800 km through West Africa, has a vast drainage basin spanning 280,000 km². This basin is shared by four nations (Figure 6): Guinea, accounting for 7% of the basin's area, Mali with 35%, Mauritania 50%, and Senegal 8% (Gaye, 2013; World Bank Group, 2021). The Senegal River basin (SRB) is home for around 12 million people. The river itself is fed by three primary tributaries: the Falémé and Bafing, both of which start in the sandstone highlands of Guinea, and the Bakoye, which originates in western Mali. These three rivers meet in Mali, forming the Senegal River, which eventually empties into the Atlantic Ocean (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Figure 6: The Senegal River Basin (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

The basin is largely defined by a sub-Saharan desert climate (Djman, 2017) and is divided into three main topographic zones: mountainous regions, valleys, and the delta area (Gebremichael et al., 2022). The river has an average annual discharge of 25 billion cubic meters. The SRB is essential for water, food, and energy security in the region. It supplies 100% of Nouakchott's (the capital city of Mauritania), water and 60% of

Dakar's, (the capital city of Senegal), making it a key resource for the urban populations and contributing significantly to the Gross Domestic.

In addition to water supply, the basin is crucial for energy production. The Malian dams Manantali and Felou provide approximately 90% of Mali's electricity and contributing significantly to the energy needs of Mauritania and Senegal (World Bank Group, 2021). The Senegal River sustains productive agricultural land, particularly in the alluvial valley stretching between Bakel and Dagana in Senegal. Following the annual flood retreats, crops such as millet, rice, and vegetables are planted. Additionally, the river serves as a valuable source of fish. However, overfishing has posed a significant threat to this vital resource (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Problems and Motivations

According to The Economist Intelligence Unit (2020), the basin **encounters substantial environmental and developmental difficulties**, and the nations involved continue to face challenges in addressing some of the fundamental needs of their populations such as drinking water. These issues highlight the necessity for better water management to ensure equitable access to water for all segments of society. Additionally, the individual countries face **difficulties in managing domestic water availability, controlling pollution, and implementing effective environmental policies**. Given the region's high vulnerability to the impacts of climate change, the lack of robust national safeguards is a significant and troubling gap (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Riparian countries in the SRB are faced with a plethora of challenges and disputes resulting mainly from competing demands for water resources and the cumulative impacts from upstream developments. The system is being **strained as water demand for irrigation** continues to rise, with 90% of Mauritania and 80% of Senegal's irrigated land relying on the river. Such high interdependencies introduce **tensions**, particularly in dry years when water demand is especially high, resulting in negotiations among states that are commonly in conflict (World Bank Group 2021). In addition, the basin is prone to **environmental degradation**, as upstream developments threaten the seasonal floods necessary to recharge local aquifers and sustain the livelihoods of many fishermen, pastoralists and farmers in the valleys below. These problems are compounded **by climate change**, which is anticipated to increase variability in water availability, fueling competition between the riparian breakers. Poverty, conflict, and displaced populations are larger regional challenges that shape the fragile socio-hydrological system of the SRB and can complicate cooperative management among states (World Bank Group, 2021).

Tension arose over the construction of the **Manantali dam** (completed 1988), as the riparian states were forced to negotiate how to distribute water and benefits from operating the dam. This proposed multinational project involves damming the Senegal River in Mali to facilitate hydropower and regulatory use of the river flows;

but countries downstream, such as Mauritania and Senegal, express concern about less water available to them for irrigation during dry seasons (Sadoff & Grey, 2002). The dam decreased seasonal flooding downstream, negatively impacting the agricultural practices of farmers and causing adverse effects on their livelihoods in Mauritania and Senegal (World Bank Group, 2021). Similarly, as there is a greater demand for water in Mali for irrigation, as opposed to hydropower generation in Senegal, these competing needs for water also creates conflicts (Sadoff & Grey, 2002).

Increased upstream extraction for irrigation has also raised concerns about both water quality and water quantity, with the rise in agricultural runoff contaminating water, with downstream countries being particularly affected. Moreover, **fluctuations in seasonal river** flow driven by climatic conditions further strain relations, especially in **years of drought**, when competition for scarce water resources becomes heightened, jeopardizing irrigation needs in Mali and hydropower use in Senegal. Such tensions deteriorate with the historical aspect of regional conflicts and the differences in countries' economic needs, which put the perception of inequity in the maintenance and distribution of the cooperative projects' benefits (Sadoff & Grey, 2002). In 1991, Mauritania and Senegal initiated talks aimed at addressing these issues, but **disputes over the use of water resources and the management of the river's hydropower capacity remained contentious**. In the late 1990s, the situation became even more strained **when Senegal accused Mali of unilaterally diverting water for use in irrigation**, creating further frictions in the bilateral relationship. Environmental degradation worries, where upstream developments were viewed as endangering seasonal floods vital for the recharge of regional aquifers and the livelihoods of fishermen, pastoralists, and farmers located in the lower valleys, compounded these conflicts (World Bank Group, 2021). **In the 2000s conflicts regarding the environmental impacts** of these projects, as local communities expressed concerns about the effects on their livelihoods and ecosystems (Sadoff & Grey, 2002).

Despite that the riparian states signed the **OMVS** (the Senegal River Basin Development Organization) **charter** in 2002, disagreements persisted over the operational management of the Manantali Dam and the Diama Dam (at the border between Senegal and Mauritania), as well as the fair distribution of water resources among Guinea, Mali, Mauritania, and Senegal. This illustrates the complexities surrounding transboundary water governance endeavors in the region. In addition, **Guinea only formally joined the OMVS in 2006**, due to political instabilities and sovereignty fears and encumbered these attempts further and demonstrated challenges in its effective and co-operative management of Senegal River Basin (World Bank Group, 2021).

Cooperation methods

The basin features significant rainfall in the upstream regions, while downstream areas experience considerably less precipitation. This hydrological disparity necessitates effective cooperation among the countries to manage water allocation and ensure sustainable development, particularly considering the challenges posed by climate variability and competing water demands (Mettrop et al., 2019).

The river has a long history of water cooperation among the basin states dating back to colonial times. Prior to independence, Mauritania and Senegal participated in water cooperation through **the Organisation Autonome de la Vallée (OAV) and the Mission d'Aménagement du Bassin du Fleuve Sénégal (MAS)**. In 1963, the four riparian states formed their own community with the conclusion of the **Bamako Convention for the Development of the Senegal River**, the first postcolonial West African treaty covering water resource management (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

A milestone in the history of cooperation was the creation of one of the first river boundary organizations in the region in 1972, the **Organisation pour la Mise en Valeur du Fleuve Sénégal (OMVS) or the Senegal River Basin Development Organization**. It was established when the basin countries were experiencing the worst drought in the late 1960s (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020; United Nation, 2024). OMVS serves as the main institution promoting cooperation among the riparian states. It focuses on integrated water resource management and the development of shared infrastructure (World Bank Group, 2021). Despite occasional setbacks, often caused by “micro-nationalisms” and the tendency of some parties to act unilaterally, collaboration and negotiations among the four countries have persisted over time, even during periods of disagreement. The UN’s Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2024) has commended the OMVS for its success in ensuring the **“equitable sharing of water resources, through development and management, between co-basin states of a transboundary river.”**

A distinctive feature of this cooperation is the **joint ownership of the dams built along the river** by three countries: Mauritania, Mali, and Senegal. This shared ownership is particularly uncommon for infrastructure on a transboundary river (United Nations, 2024). **The 1992 OMVS Convention** laid the legal groundwork for collaboration, emphasizing principles of equitable water sharing and joint management of the basin's resources, including hydropower and irrigation projects (World Bank Group, 2021). **The 1994 "Protocol on the Management of the Senegal River"** aimed to enhance cooperation in water resource management and address environmental concerns arising from development projects, ensuring that the interests of all riparian states are considered (Sadoff & Grey, 2002). In **2002, the Senegal River Basin Water Charter** was adopted, which further strengthened cooperative efforts by promoting sustainable water management practices and ensuring the involvement of local communities in decision-making processes. Although Guinea initially participated as an observer in the early years of the OMVS and raised no objections to downstream projects, its official inclusion as an upstream riparian state in 2006 was a significant milestone for the organization (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). The OMVS has implemented the **Senegal River Master Plan**, developed through a participatory approach to guide the development of large hydraulic infrastructure projects, such as the Koukoutamba Dam in Guinea, which aims to enhance water storage and energy production while considering the needs of all basin countries. **The successful implementation of major infrastructure projects**, such as the Manantali Dam (in Mali) and the planned dams of Koukoutamba (the Bafing River in

Guinea) and Gourbassi (Falémé River on the Senegal-Malian border), exemplifies the collaborative efforts to enhance hydropower generation and irrigation capacity while addressing environmental concerns (World Bank Group, 2021). Additionally, the establishment of the **Permanent Water Commission (PWC)** within OMVS facilitates ongoing negotiations and coordination regarding water allocation and management, particularly during periods of drought or low water flow.

Lessons learned

1. **Engaging in proactive dialogue and fostering mutual trust** will go a long way in laying a robust foundation for the joint management of the river. Such an approach not only ensures the sustainability of water resources, but also contributes to regional stability and peace, as shared water resources lead to interdependencies that force cooperation while conflicts over water sources lead to tensions.
2. Prioritizing **inclusive governance and stakeholder engagement** allows the countries to more effectively manage the challenges of transboundary water management and guarantee fair access for all the communities that rely on the river's resources.
3. **Development of a comprehensive management framework:** The establishment of the **Basin Master Plan** emphasizes a systematic approach to water resources management.
4. **Enhanced Information Sharing:** Strengthened information sharing at the basin level has been an essential requirement for effective governance. A case in point is the establishment of a regional data management system that enables the riparian countries to exchange hydrological data to monitor water levels and usage, both significantly important for informed decision-making during periods of drought.
5. **Addressing Implementation Challenges:** Indeed, certain OMVS projects faced difficulties in bringing together the relevant national agencies in the early stages. In response to these challenges, the OMVS has undertaken efforts to improve processes and encourage collaboration, focusing on increasing project efficiency.
6. **Cross-Sectoral Approaches:** The need for a stronger cross-sectoral approach is evident, especially in high-priority areas such as gender and fragility. In Senegal and Mauritania for instance, training sessions on the development of good irrigation practices have targeted women farmers to build gender equality while increasing agricultural productivity.
7. **OMVS remains the only RBO to have attracted significant non-donor investment for its infrastructure projects,** including with the recent awarding of the Koukoutamba hydroelectric project in Guinea to Sinohydro.
8. **Focus on Non-Structural Measures:** The difficulties encountered in establishing non-structural measures, such as education and capacity building, highlights the need for a focus on human resources

and institutional capacity investment. OMVS has also held capacity-building workshops for local stakeholders to better understand sustainable water management practices and engage the community

9. One reason for the OMVS's success is the **deep shared history and culture of the peoples** of Guinea, Mali, Mauritania and Senegal, compared with some parts of Sub-Saharan Africa, where ethnic fractionalization makes collaboration difficult within as well as between countries.

Zambezi River Basin (ZRB)

Background

The Zambezi River, the biggest and most interconnected river basin in southern Africa, originates in the Kalene Hills in Zambia's Northwestern Province. It travels southward before turning east, passing through seven countries—Angola, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Malawi, and Mozambique—over approximately 2,650 km. It eventually empties into the Indian Ocean, with mean annual discharge at the mouth to be around 4,200 m³/s (130 km³/year) (MacDonald, 2007). The Zambezi River Basin (ZRB) is home to around 47 million people (ZAMCOM, 2019) and spans an area of 1.39 million km², making it the fourth-largest river basin in Africa (Figure 7). It accounts for about 4.5% of the continent's total land area (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, 2016). Geographically, Zambia dominates the Zambezi Basin covering 41.7% of the total area, followed by Angola (18.4%), Zimbabwe (15%), Mozambique (12.8%), Malawi (8%), Tanzania (2%), and Botswana and Namibia at one percent each (ZAMCOM, SADC, SARDC, 2015).

Zambezi river has a highly seasonal flow due to the influence of changing rainfall across the Zambezi basin, resulting in a highly variable water supply. The basin supports a variety of ecosystems and biodiversity and is critical to the lives of millions that rely on it for crops, fish, and hydropower. The river has important geographical features along its course, such as the Victoria Falls, one of the largest and most famous waterfalls in the world, which attracts tourism and contributes to the local economy (Hirji, 1998). Lakes Kariba and Cahora Bassa were created down the principal Zambezi River for hydropower generation. Lake Malawi is a natural freshwater lake offering numerous economic opportunities, notably commercial fishing. The Zambezi River also hosts one of the seven wonders of the world (Victoria Falls) and essential wetlands such as the Barotse wetlands in western Zambia, which are critical habitats for numerous ecosystems (Tumbare, 2004).

Figure 7: The Zambezi River Basin (Salmoral et al., 2019).

Problems and Motivations

The Zambezi Basin faces significant *risks of overexploitation* and a focus on short-term gains rather than long-term sustainable development. The combined effects of climate change and increasing human demand on resources have led to unavoidable **environmental changes** within the basin (ZAMCOM, SADC, SARDC, 2015). The Zambezi River has been a persistent source of disputes among its riparian countries, primarily due to conflicting water demands and the challenges of joint management. **Historical tensions** were inflamed by the construction of the **Kariba Dam in the 1950s**, which sparked disputes between Zambia and Zimbabwe over water allocation and environmental impacts, particularly on downstream Mozambique. **In the late 1990s, discussions** among Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, and South Africa highlighted these **conflicts** as each pursued large-scale water abstraction projects to meet their development goals, often at the expense of others. **Zimbabwe's** ambitions for irrigation and hydropower expansion clashed with **Botswana's** need for water

supply, given that approximately 94% of Botswana's river flows originate outside its borders (Hirji, 1995). Additionally, **the potential for unilateral actions by upstream countries**, such as Zambia and Angola, posed significant risks to downstream nations like Mozambique, which stands to be disproportionately affected by upstream developments. The complexity of these **disputes** is exacerbated by **capacity imbalances among the countries**; for instance, Zambia, as the largest contributor to the Zambezi Basin, contrasts with Malawi's total reliance on the basin's surface water resources, highlighting a disparity in stakes and interests (Hirji, 1998). **The absence of comprehensive treaties or effective river basin organizations** has resulted in informal cooperation, leaving many issues unresolved and increasing the potential for conflict (Grey & Sadoff, 1996). The establishment of **the Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM)** in 2004 aimed to address these issues through enhanced cooperation, yet the lack of comprehensive agreements has continued to impede effective resource management (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, 2004). Projections indicate that the basin's population increase, leading to increase in food demand and rise in energy consumption will further intensify competition for water resources (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, 2016).

Cooperation Methods

Cooperation around the Zambezi River regarding transboundary conflicts has been facilitated through several key initiatives and agreements aimed at promoting sustainable management of shared water resources. One of the earliest of these initiatives was **ZACPLAN (Zambezi Action Plan) launched in 1987** with the aim to foster the sustainable and cooperative management and development of the Zambezi River Basin (Hirji 1998). **In 1995 SADC (The Southern African Development Community) adopted a Protocol on Shared Watercourse Systems** that emphasized the principles of equitable utilization and information exchange, as well as conservation of shared watercourses in the member states concerned (Hirji 1998, Grey and Sadoff 1996, Southern African Development Community 2000). The protocol provides a basis for dispute resolution and management on a cooperative basis with arbitration authority provided by the SADC panel (Hirji, 1998). Further efforts include the establishment of **Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM) in 2004**, which aims at integrated water resources development and better cooperation among the eight basin countries (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, 2004). **The 2008 Integrated Water Resources Management Strategy and Implementation Plan for the Zambezi River Basin** has acted as a guiding framework for change and established platform for collaboration among riparian states. It emphasizes inclusive basin management, involving diverse stakeholders, including women's groups, youth organizations, small-scale farmers, business associations, and decision-makers from local authorities, national and regional levels (World Bank Group, 2021). Ongoing initiatives, **such as the 4th Regional Strategic Action Plan for Integrated Water Resources Development formulated in 2016**, strongly advocate for cooperative measures to tackle water, energy, and food safety issues in the basin (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, 2016).

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Regional Cooperation:** Cooperation between the riparian countries is ideally needed for effective transboundary water resources management. The formation of the Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM) under the ZACPLAN initiative illustrates the need for collaborative frameworks to resolve common water challenges.
2. **Legal Frameworks for Resource Sharing:** The SADC Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses establishes a legal foundation for fair resource sharing and dispute resolution, emphasizing the importance of formal agreements in the effective governance of shared water resources.
3. **Continuous Assessment and Adaptation:** Ongoing evaluation and adaptation of management practices is important to address emerging challenges, ensuring sustainable resource use and resilience in the face of changing conditions.
4. **Long-term Commitment:** Water management diplomacy necessitates a long-term effort from all parties engaged. Indeed, projects to integrate water resources like ZACPRO 6 are continuing processes as transboundary water management involves complex facets that require an ongoing approach

African Transboundary aquifers (TBAs)

Background

Transboundary aquifers (TBAs) are crucial as they represent shared water resources that cross national borders. A total of 72 TBAs (Figure 8) have been recognized in the African mainland and the extent of the TBAs is more than 40% of the continental Africa (IGRAC & UNESCO-IHP, 2015a). These aquifers are crucial since groundwater is the only reliable drinking water source in many parts of Africa. Among the forty-seven countries on the mainland of Africa, the only two with no TBAs known to be available in their borders are Sierra Leone and Equatorial Guinea (Nijsten et al., 2018). About 400 million people live in regions underlain by these aquifers (UNESCO-IHP & UNEP, 2016), therefore TBAs play an important role in water resource provision for a large proportion of the population, especially in regions where water scarcity may be an issue.

The Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System (NSAS–AF63) is one of the largest aquifers worldwide that covers about 2.5 million km² northeast Africa, known for its significance in drinking water and irrigation supply in an arid environment, specifically, Egypt, Libya, Chad, and Sudan (CEDARE, 2001; Nijsten et al., 2018). The NSAS estimated groundwater storage is about 500,000 million cubic meters and expected recoverable volume is about 3% (IAEA et al., 2013). **The Northwestern Sahara Aquifer System (NWSAS –AF69)**, which spans Algeria, Libya, and Tunisia, is another important transboundary aquifer supplying water in a region of extreme aridity. The exploitation of NWSAS waters by drilling increased from 0.6 à 2.5 billion m³ /an, since the late seventies (Sahara and Sahel Observatory, 2008). Below is a summary of the aquifer main

characteristics. The theoretical reserve of the aquifer is around 1 million km², while the theoretical recharge is 1 billion m³ (AbuZeid et al., 2025).

Figure 8: The transboundary aquifers of Africa with codes (IGRAC and UNESCO-IHP, 2015a).

Problems and Motivations

The management of transboundary aquifers (TBAs) in Africa faces several critical challenges due to the unequal distribution of resources and varying management capacities within the social, economic, and environmental contexts of the countries that share them. Despite offering substantial resources for Africa’s development, **only 11 of the 72 known TBAs** have been extensively studied. The main problems affecting competent management are (Nijsten et al., 2018):

- 1.The reluctance of countries to share hydrogeological data**, which hampers accurate resource assessment and leads to misunderstandings over water allocation.

2. **Lack of comprehensive legal and institutional frameworks for governing shared aquifers in many countries**, resulting in unregulated exploitation and conflicts, that is exemplified by the **Iullemeden Aquifer**, where differing national interests complicate cooperation.
3. **The absence of awareness regarding the importance of TBAs suppresses collaborative efforts**, while fragmented management approaches lead to individual countries implementing their own strategies without considering the transboundary nature of the resources.
4. **Socio-economic disparities among countries** as rich nations are able to invest more resources into ground water management that leaves poorer neighbors at a disadvantage and creates tensions over resource use.

The Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System (NSAS) and the Northwestern Sahara Aquifer System (NWSAS) posed several challenges that needed to be addressed in terms of their sustainability and appropriate management. **Groundwater overexploitation** is one of the main threats for both aquifers driven by growing irrigation and public supply demands, which cause severe drops in water levels. Important declines in water levels have been reported in the NWSAS, and more importantly in areas that are highly dependent on the aquifer for agricultural and domestic purposes (IAEA et al., 2013). With growing populations and decreasing water availability from other sources, the NSAS is under mounting pressure, which threatens water quality, and has the potential to harm biodiversity and accelerate land degradation. Both aquifers also face serious **water quality problems** — on top of over-extraction. The **saline water intrusion** effects of the NSAS, which could be found in the northern sectors of the NSAS, make it difficult to use the groundwater for drinking and agriculture. Extensive exploitation of the aquifer over the last forty years enabled Egypt and Libya to withdraw significant amounts from the resources for irrigation and public water supply (Quadri, 2017). On the other hand, **poor agricultural practices and inadequate waste management** can endanger NWSAS and its groundwater, which harms its quality, and puts the local public's health at risk (Tujchneider & van der Gun, 2012). Moreover, both aquifers suffer from **lack of governance and mismanagement**. Due to the **inactions of the NSAS Agreements**, the terms set forth for sustainable use and protection of the resources are not effective. In addition, **lack of integrated systems and moderators in the NWSAS** makes it impossible to properly resource and manage information and make necessary decisions to build proper resource management systems (Contin, 2017). **Political disputes and the socio-economic differences** between the nations that share these aquifers make the situation much worse. All factors combined pose a serious threat in terms of **political and social instability** that shall impact relations, and the enforcement of the governance needed to effectively manage the NSAS and NWSAS acquirers (AbuZeid et al., 2015).

Cooperation & Methods

The effort to explore and manage the actual cross border aquifer resources was started in **North Africa during the 1970s** due to the need to develop and manage the sedimentary groundwater resource in arid areas (Quadri, 2017; Nijsten et al., 2018). Since the early 1970s, Egypt, Libya and Sudan began coordinating and exploring opportunities for development that led to the establishment of the **Joint Authority for the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer (JANSA)**. After a long stillness, the countries involved obtained funding to start a research program that is consisted of: (1) training of staff from the four national institutions responsible for the NSAS; (2) database development; and (3) development of a groundwater model. This research program and other projects were funded by United Nations Development Programme and the Global Environment Fund (UNDP-GEF), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).

Despite the vast amounts of data available, little has been done to consolidate aquifer information to develop systematic data archives and regional monitoring strategies, a challenge that led to the creation of the **Nubian Aquifer Regional Information System (NARIS)** to pool and share information on aquifer properties, including water quantities, extraction rates, geological layers and flow patterns. A portion of the database is dedicated to the archive of past research and academic publications (Scheumann & Neubert, 2006). A major result of the program was **the revival of JANSA**. As such, at the core of calls for ongoing regional collaboration in aquifer governance was the necessity for data to be consistently shared. To achieve this, two agreements were signed. **The first** addressed the transfer of information gathered and integrated into NARIS during the project. Under **the second agreement**, the parties committed to updating the system regularly through continuous observation, upkeep, and database management. These records are stored on a server operated by the **Centre for Environment and Development for the Arab Region and Europe (CEDARE)** in Egypt. Access to NARIS is exclusive to the water agencies of the participating countries. Concerning permissions, any modifications made to the data by one agency can be reviewed and adjusted by the others (Grossmann, 2006).

The conference hosted by Tripoli in 1999 "**Regional Aquifer Systems in Arid Zones**", introduced the definition of regional aquifers as a key concept for developing the **International Initiative on Shared Aquifers**, later globalized under the **ISARM program (Internationally Shared Aquifer Resource Management)** led by UNESCO (UNESCO, IAH, & FAO, 2000; UNESCO-IHP, 2009). **ISARM program** commenced in the **early 2000s**, has methodically identified and mapped TBAs across Africa while **fostering extensive cross-border dialogues** to outline challenges and devise optimal management strategies for these aquifers. **Only seven aquifers have specific agreements in place for joint research, monitoring, or governance** (Nijsten et al., 2018).

The African Ministers' Council on Water (AMCOW), established in 2002, has been instrumental in promoting the management of TBAs across the continent. In the same year, a workshop organized by the ISARM initiative resulted in the creation of **an inventory** that identified 38 African TBAs, **along with a map** indicating their approximate locations (Appelgren, 2004).

For the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System (NSAS), the establishment of **the Joint Authority for the Study and Development in 1992** was a pivotal development, facilitating collaboration among Egypt, Libya, Chad, and Sudan. This authority has played a crucial role in **fostering dialogue and coordinating research efforts**, though it has encountered challenges in implementing comprehensive management strategies (Quadri, 2017; IAEA et al., 2013). Key initiatives for the NSAS include the **"Programme for the Development of a Regional Strategy for the Utilization of the NSAS"** and the **"Regional Action Programme for Integrated NSAS Management,"** both **funded by GEF** (Global Environment Facility) and implemented by UNDP, IAEA, and UNESCO-IHP, focusing on data sharing, joint monitoring, and equitable resource exploitation (IAEA et al., 2013). Similarly, for the NWSAS, a **cooperative framework** established in **1997** by Algeria, Libya, and Tunisia emphasizes data sharing, joint monitoring, and the formation of a **Coordinating Unit and Steering Committee** to oversee management efforts (AbuZeid et al., 2015). These frameworks facilitate joint decision-making and consultative management approaches, with a commitment to joint risk mitigation and addressing issues such as over-extraction and pollution (Tujchneider & van der Gun, 2012).

Stretching across Botswana, South Africa, and Zimbabwe (Figure 9), **the Tuli Karoo Transboundary Aquifer** represents a vital shared groundwater resource. Recognizing the interconnected nature of groundwater systems, the three nations collaboratively prioritized harmonized data collection to track water levels, flow dynamics, and surface water interactions. To address this need, a cross-border initiative was launched. Strategically placed monitoring boreholes in the aquifer now house automated data loggers, capturing hourly readings of groundwater depth, electrical conductivity, and pH levels. Information streams from these devices to a centralized digital platform, accessible to all participating countries, fostering transparency and joint analysis of aquifer health (IWMI, 2021).

Figure 9: The Tuli Karoo transboundary aquifer (IWMI, 2021).

Lessons Learned

- 1) **Importance of Regional Cooperation:** African countries have learned through experience that the cooperation of all countries sharing a water resource is essential. NSAS and NWSAS agreements show how collaboration can improve sustainable water management.
- 2) **Management of Shared Resources:** Utilization of shared water resources must be managed to meet the demands of the concerned countries. Such strategies must involve an exchange of data and information as well as the formulation of joint policies to tackle challenges like climate change and population growth.
- 3) **Legal and Institutional Framework:** The experience suggests that strong legal and institution framework is necessary to ensure agreement compliance. Cooperation was sometimes undermined by national institutions in the countries concerned not being fully up and running.
- 4) **Importance of Data and Information:** The experience points to the importance of collecting and analyzing data to understand the condition of water resources. For example, the four countries that are part of NSAS agreed to share data to facilitate sustainable use of the water.
- 5) **The Nubian Aquifer Regional Information System** is a strong example of shared information that is not publicly available, accessible only to the parties bound by the agreement. The renewal of a joint commission to guide the creation of the database is expected to be highly significant, as it is intended to support political-level management decisions and cross-border consultations.

The Chad Lake

Background

Lake Chad (Figure 10) is an important resource for the food security of around 15 million residents of Cameroon, Chad, Niger and Nigeria, and part of the Central African Republic (World Bank Group, 2021). The lake is an important source of income for the coastal populations where fishing, agriculture, and livestock farming are highly developed and significant to the Sahelo-Saharan region, well known for its recurrent food insecurity (World Bank Group, 2021). Lake Chad is also Africa's fourth-largest lake as well as the largest one in Western and Central Africa, according to a 2003 joint report by the World Bank and the Global Environment Facility (2003). The Lake Basin is composed primarily of two subbasins, the Chari-Logone and the Kamadugu-Yobe. The Chari River flows north from the highlands of the Central African Republic into southern Chad, delivering roughly 95% of the lake's surface water that enters each year. The lake itself has a shallow profile of about 1.5 meters deep, giving it a very low water volume. According to Asah (2015), extensive wetlands and seasonal floodplains stretch away from the lake's central body, creating the second-largest assemblage of wetland ecosystems on the continent. Figure 10 shows the continuous shrinkage of the lake between 1963 and 2007 (<https://www.grida.no/resources/5651>).

Figure 10: Lake Chad shrinkage over time (UNEP, 2018).

Problems and Motivations

The lake area represents a very **fragile socio-hydrological system** affected by several transboundary risks, yet mainly **demographic pressure** and **long-lasting conflicts (political instability)** that worsen the vulnerability of impoverished populations (Asah, 2015; World Bank Group, 2021). Lake Chad significant challenges such as **severe shrinkage**, pollution, and overfishing have led to disputes among the riparian countries of Chad, Niger, Nigeria, and Cameroon. **The decrease of size in the lake** is caused by consuming water and **lack of cooperation between the countries** which share the waters of the lake (UNDP, 2006). The lake's surface area has decreased dramatically (Figure 1) from about 22 902 km² in 1963 to 304 km² in 2001 (Osman-Elasha, 2009) to less than 1,500 km² by 2015, primarily due to climate change and unsustainable water management practices (Scheumann & Neubert, 2006). This drastic reduction has intensified competition for water resources, leading to **conflicts over water allocation and usage rights**. Moreover, the vulnerability of the lake is aggravated by **historical droughts** during the **1970s and 1980s** (World Bank Group, 2021). Besides drought, **irrigation expansion** is one of the main causes of deepening water scarcity and social-ecological degradation in the Lake Chad Basin. Integrated biosphere models show that anthropogenic water use, primarily through irrigation, accounts for half of the observed area change since the 1960s (Coe & Foley, 2001).

The hydrology of Lake Chad Basin is heavily influenced by widespread water **diversion projects** and the construction of **large dams**, mainly for hydroelectricity and monoculture irrigation agriculture. One case in point is **the Maga Dam**, which is 1400m long on the Logone-Chari River. The Cameroon dam was initially commenced by French colonists long before Cameroon gained its independence, but it was concluded by the Cameroonian government in 1979 with a capacity of 4 billion cubic meters (Berardo & Gerlak, 2012).

The lake is also at risk from potential changes to its hydrological conditions, driven by **climate change**, and **the unchecked expansion of irrigation** in the Chari-Logone basin, which supplies nearly 90% of the lake's water. Additionally, **pollution from surrounding countries** threatens the health of local populations, the lake's rich biodiversity, and agricultural productivity. The **growing exploitation of hydrocarbons in the region and the excessive use of pesticides in farming** are already impacting animal health, particularly ruminants and fish. **Untreated sewage and industrial waste** further compound these risks. With one of the highest population growth rates globally, the Lake Chad Basin faces escalating threats of natural **resource overuse and sociopolitical instability**, especially if job creation fails to keep pace with the growing number of young adults entering the workforce (World Bank Group, 2021). While the **Lake Chad Basin Commission (LCBC)** was created in 1964 to foster cooperation between these states, tensions have continued, particularly around the equitable access and distribution of water to sustain irrigation and fishing (Scheumann & Neubert, 2006).

Cooperation Methods

According to World Bank and GEF (2003), Cameroon, Chad, Niger, and Nigeria formed the **Lake Chad Basin Commission (LCBC) in 1964** by signing an agreement called the **Fort-Lamy Convention**. The treaty, now recognized under the name of Chad's current capital N'Djamena (Asah, 2015). In 1994, Central African Republic became a fifth member, and the 'basin' was extended to cover the upstream portion of the Logone-Chari and Komadugu-Yobe subbasins. Sudan, with aquifers beneath its western border shared with Chad, was included as a sixth member in 2000, and Libya joined in 2007. All water resources supplying the lake, its related floodplains, wetlands and aquifers are included in the present conventional basin characterized by an area of 967,000 km². Five member countries contribute to the LCBC's budget, which is divided as follows: Cameroon 26%, Central African Republic 4%, Chad 11%, Niger 7%, and Nigeria 52% (Asah, 2015).

These efforts have also been promoted by the **World Bank's engagement** in the Lake Chad Basin. Between 2003 and 2004, the Senegal, Niger, and Lake Chad basins have been funded through grants from the **Global Environment Facility (GEF)**. The grants, which ranged from 3 to 6 million, were mainly focused on three aspects: (1) building the institutional capacity of river basin organizations (RBOs), (2) performing transboundary diagnostic assessments and developing strategic action plans accordingly, and (3) executing pilot projects across borders in support of the action plans. Additionally, in 2015, it supported the preparation of the **Lake Chad Development and Climate Resilient Action Plan through CIWA** (Cooperation in International Waters in Africa) grant, which helped to mobilize support from development partners, and which was presented at COP21 in Paris (World Bank Group, 2021). An instance of this is where the World Bank supported a regional **International Development Association (IDA) initiative** to address forced displacement-related issues (though not specifically focusing on water-related dimensions in this case). Such challenges were Great Roadblocks for World Bank's financial activeness in the Lake Chad Basin region, which have hindered countries sharing Lake Chad to cooperate with each other effectively. Central to this challenge has been the structural limitations of the **Lake Chad Basin Commission (LCBC)**, which has suffered from a lack of member state support and weaknesses in project implementation and resource mobilization (World Bank Group, 2021).

Lessons learned

- 1) **The importance of strong institutional frameworks** is underscored as the **Lake Chad Basin Commission (LCBC)** struggled to meet its needs because it received lack of support from its member states to enable effective project implementation.

- 2) **Fostering political stability and enhancing communication among the riparian countries**, since political turbulence and spatial remoteness have made communication and reaching an agreement difficult in case of Chad lake.
- 3) **Regular dialogue and engagement** is needed for successful transboundary water management pointing towards limited strategic decision-making.
- 4) **Third party engagement** is instrumental in cooperation and joint management of water resources.

Lake Tanganyika

Background

Lake Tanganyika (Figure 11) is one of the largest freshwater lakes by volume and is the second deepest lake in the world and is shared by four riparian countries: Burundi (8%), the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC (45%)), Tanzania (41%) and Zambia (6%) (Bootsma & Hecky, 2003). Approximately, the lake covers an area of 32,900 km² and has a mean depth of 570 meters, with a maximum depth reaching 1,470 meters in the southern basin (Bergonzini et al., 2015).

Figure 11: The Lake Tanganyika Basin (Small Boats Nation, 2024).

The Lukuga River acts as the lake's primary outlet, channeling water into the vast Congo River network (Dettman et al., 2005). To the north, the Ruzizi River—originating from Lake Kivu—feeds into Tanganyika as its major inflow. These are supplemented by smaller tributaries like the Kalambo River and Tanzania's second-largest waterway, the Malagarasi River, which also contribute to the basin's hydrology (Scheffél & Wernet, 1980; Coulter, 1991; Kullander & Roberts, 2011).

More than 12 million people reside in its basin, relying on the lake for food, work, and economic stability. Population growth in the region remains high, with annual rates hovering between 2.9% and 3.1% across bordering nations (Odada et al., 2004). The lake features a rich array of aquatic environments, ranging from thick vegetation like emergent and submerged plants to shallow, nutrient-rich plateaus filled with sediment near river deltas. These diverse environments foster an extraordinary array of species, interconnected through intricate relationships. Current estimates indicate more than 2,000 plant and animal species inhabit the lake, with approximately 600 found nowhere else on Earth (Coulter, 1991; Snoeks, 2000).

Problems and Motivations

Lake Tanganyika has encountered numerous challenges and disputes among its bordering countries largely due to **insufficient enforcement of fisheries regulations and a lack of cooperative management of shared resources**. Throughout the 1990s, the region experienced significant **ethnic conflicts**, particularly in the Democratic Republic of Congo, which disrupted local fishing communities and hindered effective resource management (Cacaud, 1999). The civil war in Burundi further exacerbated these issues by 1994, leading to a breakdown in communication and collaboration among the countries (Cacaud, 1998). The **removal of forests** across the basin has drastically intensified **soil erosion**, stripping away fertile topsoil and triggering sediment buildup. As eroded materials flow into the lake's shallower zones, they smother habitats and disrupt fundamental ecological processes, weakening the diversity, population numbers, and overall balance of aquatic life. Studies reveal that between 40% and 60% of forested land in the lake's central basin has been stripped bare, with nearly all forests in the northern basin eradicated. This widespread clearing stems largely from activities such as **harvesting firewood, producing charcoal, temporary farming methods** like slash-and-burn, and converting land to pasture. Such practices have worsened **soil degradation**, channeling massive amounts of sediment into Lake Tanganyika's waters (Azanga et al., 2016). In 2000, the **World Commission on Dams, (2000)** highlighted the neglect of environmental and social considerations in agreements, which contributed to ongoing conflicts over resource management.

By the turn of the 21st Century, **pollution** from cities such as Bujumbura in Burundi and Kigoma in Tanzania had reached staggering levels. Degraded river basins released excessive sediment which further exacerbated the problem and there were calls for urgent intervention (Uitto & Duda, 2002). The rise of agriculture has

consumed a greater dependency on **chemical inputs** such as synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides. At the same time, the **urban household and industrial wastes** are contaminating groundwater and surface water more. This type of pollution adversely affects aquatic biodiversity, habitat destruction, decreased fish stocks and public health crisis in the lake (Phiri et al., 2023). These challenges are compounded by **plastic waste** that generated by inefficient recycling or waste management systems in towns from the four countries swamp the lake with bottles, bags and other non-biodegradable material, and they make their way into the local water. With an inability to cost-effectively recycle or dispose of, the lake is a cesspool (Azevedo-Santos et al., 2021). **Climate change** added an additional layer of complexity. However, over the last century the ecosystem of Lake Tanganyika has experienced a continuous warming related to shifts in climatic conditions (Kraemer et al., 2015; Plisnier et al., 2018).

Methods of Cooperation

Transboundary conflicts around Lake Tanganyika have required dynamic approaches to management informed by the lake's complex political and ecological context. Early efforts, **in the 1990s, collaborative scientific research** was helped to create a common understanding of the lake's vulnerable ecosystem. This foundation became critical for supporting cooperative governance (Uitto & Duda, 2002). Furthermore, in the early 1990s as one of the first **Global Environment Facility (GEF)** projects, the Lake Tanganyika initiative sought to develop a cooperative structure for the management of the transboundary lake that is shared among four riparian countries (Uitto & Duda, 2002). A project coordinating unit was established to undertake national and joint activities, supervised by a **Steering Committee** consisting of high-level representatives of each country. The project emphasized **integrating conservation with sustainable development working closely with local communities** to combine conservation with livelihood needs. Programs focused on a variety of challenges, including biodiversity loss, fisheries management, sedimentation, pollution, and socio-economic issues. This narrative showcases the essence of a unique approach, illustrated further by a mid-term evaluation conducted by UNDP to align strategic plans with global goals as outlined by GEF's Operational Strategy's International Waters objectives. The collaborative process of joint fact-finding and GIS technology allowed for joint data collection, producing a **Transboundary Diagnostic Analysis (TDA)**, which identified key priorities: hotspots of urban pollution such as Bujumbura and Kigoma, excessive sediment runoff from particular river basins (especially in Burundi and DRC) and overfishing resulting from commercial demand and trade across boundaries (Uitto & Duda, 2002).

A Strategic Action Programme (SAP) outlined activities for individual and collective implementation, fostering capacity-building among national officials in environmental monitoring (Uitto & Duda, 2002). Concurrently, discussions began on a draft international treaty in 1999—**the Convention on the Sustainable Management of Lake Tanganyika** to institutionalize cooperation through a joint **Management Committee**

and Secretariat (Cacaud, 1998; Uitto & Duda, 2002). The project led to significant progress in technical knowledge about transboundary issues, helped identify areas of key intervention and strengthened collaboration at local level between governments, scientific institutions and communities despite ongoing political tensions. The **project materials were shared through a dedicated website** where stakeholders from various countries, UNDP, GEF and international advisors could share and access central materials. For participants without reliable internet access, the updates and resources were sent once a quarter on CD-ROMs. Putting large parts of the website in public furthers this and allows NGOs, government, and funders to track progress in real time and can engage with what is being generated in terms of the project's outputs. This method provided for internal coordination while ensuring external accountability (Uitto & Duda, 2002).

In the early 2000s, the **Lake Tanganyika Biodiversity Project (LTBP)** continued to scale up joint research, addressing overfishing and pollution through collaboration between governments and scientists (Phiri et al., 2023). To address this and the fragmented management approaches of the four riparian nations on the shores of Lake Tanganyika, the riparian states collaboratively developed the **Lake Tanganyika Authority (LTA)**, as established **within the framework of the Convention on the Sustainable Management of Lake Tanganyika**. This approach aims to achieve coordinated and transboundary governance across the lake and its basin that addresses both conservation and sustainable use of resources (LTA Secretariat, 2011). In 2010, the LTA launched **the Strategic Action Programme (SAP)**, a framework to guide long-term ecological management, which was further updated in 2011. The SAP also noted increasing human activities—such as agriculture, urbanization, and resource extraction—as key drivers of biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation in the basin. However, progress faced challenges (LTA Secretariat, 2011). From the 16th of December 2021, the set-up a Regional Charter on Sustainable Management of Fisheries was endorsed by the Conference of Ministers of the Lake Tanganyika Authority, creating a common instrument for the regulation of the three main commercial pelagic fish species in Lake Tanganyika. This Charter was adopted by convention of the riparian states and sets out harmonized measures for managing and to enforcing them. However, the successful execution of these guidelines heavily depends on a firm monitoring system (LTA Secretariat, 2021).

Lessons Learned

1. **Sustained Collaboration Among Riparian States:** The sustainable management of shared ecosystems relies on permanent cooperation between all bordering countries. Although the Lake Tanganyika Authority (LTA) did manage to create a platform for dialogue, political instability revealed deficiencies in continuing cooperation during crisis. Over the long term, necessary governance frameworks must be flexible including rotating leadership roles or crisis response protocols that facilitate collaboration amidst competing national objectives.

2. **Transparency and Adaptive Communication:** Transparency in collaboration encourages trust among governments, NGOs, and local stakeholders. The Lake Tanganyika project shows how tailored communication strategies bridge gaps in connectivity and literacy and uses public websites, CD-ROMs for offline communities and firewalled platforms in cases where security for data exchange is paramount.
3. **Empowering Local Communities as Stewards:** Given vast traditional knowledge and direct reliance on the lake's ecosystems, local communities must be included in conservation strategies. The **Lake Tanganyika Biodiversity Project (LTBP)**, for example, focused on partnerships between governments, scientists, and local stakeholders to solve overfishing and pollution issues, implicitly assuming community participation in monitoring and enforcement.
4. **Harmonized Data Systems with Regional Equity:** Collecting data in a coordinated manner is essential for successful management across borders, but differences between national resources undermine its implementation. Joint GIS mapping showed what could be done with shared technology, but challenges like the variable funding or technical ability needed to create joint maps need solutions like **regional training centers or pooled funding for equipment**. Success is contingent on making sure that nations can equitably contribute to, and benefit from, unified monitoring frameworks.
5. **Balancing International Support with Local Leadership:** Partnerships worldwide, like those with the Global Environment Facility (GEF), lend support and mobilize good practices to jumpstart initiatives. Yet excessive dependence on external forces threatens to erode local ownership. The LTA has moved from UNDP-guided projects to regionally managed programmes. This equilibrium guarantees that projects stay culturally pertinent and economically viable once outside assistance concludes.

Lake Victoria

Background

Lake Victoria, the largest lake in Africa and the second-largest freshwater lake in the world, spans an area of 69,000 km² (Figure 12). It is situated on the borders of Uganda, Kenya, and Tanzania, with Uganda and Tanzania holding the majority shares (45% and 49%, respectively) while Kenya holds 6% (Ayoma, 2023). Rwanda and Burundi are a part of the upper watershed that drains into Lake Victoria through the Kagera River with catchment area of 194,000 km² (Ministry of Water, 2024).

Approximately 40 million people live in the basin, where it supports approximately 4 million livelihoods and employs around 200,000 people, making it a crucial resource for the local communities (Aloo & Othoro, 2019; Ministry of Water, 2024). Lake Victoria is characterized by several significant properties that contribute to its ecological and socio-economic importance. The lake is the source of the Nile River, impacting multiple countries that rely on its waters for various uses (Kerubo, 2005).

Figure 12: The Lake Victoria Basin (Olaka, 2019).

Problems and Motivations

Historically, Lake Victoria has been at the center of disputes among the riparian countries—Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania—due to conflicting interests in the use and management of water resources. On July 4, 1962, Tanzania issued identical notes to Britain, Egypt, and Sudan, rejecting colonial-era Nile treaties and proposing renegotiation. By November 21, 1963, Egypt responded, asserting the continued validity of the 1929 Nile Waters Agreement, which it argued remained binding between Britain and its former East African territories. Egypt expressed openness to informal technical discussions with the three East African nations. Sudan, however, offered no response to either Tanzania’s initial note or Egypt’s reply. Tanzania acknowledged Egypt’s position in a December 21, 1963, communication. Following its union with Zanzibar, Tanzania dismissed the treaty’s legitimacy, arguing it was neither real nor dispositive meaning it did not permanently settle territorial or resource rights. The government maintained that the agreement applied only to British-administered territories and ceased to hold after independence (Seaton & Maliti, 1973; Kerubo, 2005). In Kenya, public pressure has urged leaders and the government to utilize water resources from rivers feeding into Lake Victoria for domestic use. Prioritizing irrigation has been emphasized to ensure food security,

particularly during periods of drought or water shortages. (Kerubo, 2005). In more recent history, Lake Victoria has witnessed **numerous conflicts and challenges among the bordering countries** due to competition for its resources. **In 2008**, tensions flared between **Uganda and Kenya** over Migingo Island after Ugandan officials claimed sovereignty, while Kenya insisted the island fell within its exclusive economic zone. This territorial disagreement led to heightened diplomatic friction, culminating in the deployment of naval assets by both nations.

Years later, in 2019, Uganda's **abrupt prohibition on fishing activities** in Lake Victoria—justified by unsustainable practices and dwindling fish populations—ignited unrest among Kenyan and Tanzanian fishing communities, who faced severe economic disruption. **Violent clashes and protests erupted** before regional diplomacy facilitated a resolution: Uganda revoked the ban and pledged joint efforts with Kenya and Tanzania to implement sustainable fisheries management strategies (Ayoma, 2023). **Lake Victoria's ecological health faces mounting strain from persistent threats**, including dwindling fish populations due to overexploitation, contamination from industrial discharges, and the unchecked spread of invasive vegetation such as water hyacinth. These compounding pressures have heightened tensions, with Kenyan fishers frequently reporting aggressive enforcement by Ugandan patrols in disputed waters. Such **confrontations** have not only deepened mistrust between the two nations but also exposed the fragility of unilateral governance approaches. Addressing these intertwined ecological and political challenges demands urgent, regionally coordinated measures to protect the lake's biodiversity while supporting the millions reliant on its resources (Nyamweya, 2023).

Methods of Cooperation

Cooperation methods around Lake Victoria regarding transboundary conflicts have evolved significantly over time through various treaties and agreements. The groundwork for such cooperation began when Sudan, following its independence in 1956, demanded a review of the **1929 Anglo-Egyptian Treaty**. This marked a **significant shift towards collaborative management** of shared water resources, highlighting the need for more inclusive and equitable frameworks that considered the interests of all riparian states (Godana, 1985). In 1977, the **Kagera Basin Organization Agreement** was signed by Burundi, Rwanda, and Tanzania, with Uganda joining later. This agreement focused on the **integrated development of the Kagera River Basin**, which feeds into Lake Victoria, and underscored the importance of regional cooperation in managing water resources. This initiative was one of the earliest examples of a coordinated approach to water management in the Lake Victoria Basin, setting a precedent for future collaborations (Kerubo, 2005).

A landmark moment came in **1994** with the founding of the **Lake Victoria Fisheries Organization (LVFO)**, reflecting Kenya and Uganda shared commitment to governance. Cooperation hasn't always been smooth, but

joint efforts like the LVFO highlight a persistent drive to balance ecological health with livelihoods (Ayoma, 2023).

The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (WB) led **Lake Victoria Environmental Management Project**. The project is a regional effort that was conceived and **initiated to address the observed environmental challenges** through bringing the attention of the partner states and stakeholders to the problems threatening sustainable development and utilization of the lake basin resources and strengthening of governing institutions (Ministry of Water, 2024).

The Nile Basin Initiative (NBI) lunched in 1999 aimed to promote joint management and development of the Nile Basin, including Lake Victoria, and to facilitate dialogue and cooperation between the riparian states. This initiative served as critical to the promotion of a shared vision for the sustainable use of water resources, addressing conflicts, and to ensure that the benefits of basin resources are shared equitably among all the countries involved (Okidi, 2003). The **East African Community (EAC) Treaty in 2000** puts the region at the forefront of regional integration and cooperation among the member states. EAC **inspired cooperation in the management of the resources of Lake Victoria** and demonstrated the opportunity to collaborate between countries on transboundary water management. This treaty led to the establishment of an expansive regime for lake resource sustainable development, which further encouraged regional stability and prosperity (East African Community Secretariat, 2003).

Lessons Learned

1. **Renegotiating colonial legacy agreements:** Outdated agreements, such as the 1929 Nile Waters Agreement, can exacerbate disputes, as seen in Tanzania's rejection of the treaty and demands for renegotiation post-independence. Modern frameworks need to consider current realities and sovereignty concerns.
2. **Risks of unilateral actions:** Unilateral decisions, like Uganda's 2019 fishing ban, can trigger regional tensions and conflict among riparian countries. Effective conflict resolution channels, such as organizations like the LVFO, are critical to managing disputes collaboratively.
3. **Need for regional cooperation:** Collaborative institutions and treaties, including the East African Community Treaty and the Lake Victoria Fisheries Organization, facilitate joint management and sustainable use of resources, emphasizing the value of multilateral engagement.
4. **Science-driven projects bridge ecological and socio-economic divides:** **The Lake Victoria Environmental Management Project (LVEMP)** ensured that scientific research was complemented by the necessary building of institutional capacity. LVEMP emphasized that the cross-border nature of environmental challenges requires an integrated approach, as demonstrated through sound scientific solutions to pollution costs, fishing and invasive species using data.

5.2.2 Asia

Examples from Asia are represented by three transboundary river basins from Central Asia and seven transboundary river basins from South Asia.

Region	River Basin
Central Asia	Amu Darya River Basin, Irtys River Basin, & Syr Darya River Basin
South Asia	Aras River Basin, Barhamaputra River Basin, Ganges River Basin, Harirud River Basin, Koshi River Basin, Mekong River Basin, & Saralbhanga River Basin

Amu Darya River Basin (ADRB)

Background

The Amu Darya River, flowing for 2550 km from the Pamir Mountains in Tajikistan, is among the most significant water resources in Central Asia that is created by the merging of the Panj and Vakhsh rivers (Salminen, 2019; The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). The river runs in a west-northwest direction, eventually reaching the Aral Sea, and serves as a boundary line between Afghanistan and the neighboring countries of Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan., highlighting its significance in regional geopolitics as shown in Figure 13 (Rycroft & Wegerich, 2009). The modern history of Amu Darya associates with getting over of the bitter legacy and securing of welfare and wellbeing for five riparian nations including Kyrgyz Republic. The Amu Darya River has the largest annual runoff in Central Asia ($564:00 \times 108 \text{ m}^3$) (Varis, 2014), which it serves as one of the limited water sources for the arid steppe and desert regions located downstream in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan (Britanica, 1998a; Bernauer & Siegfried, 2012). It has historically supported extensive agricultural activities, particularly cotton production, which has contributed to environmental degradation, including the drying of the Aral Sea (Salminen, 2019; The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). In Tajikistan, the Vakhsh River, located upstream, is heavily utilized for generating hydroelectric power. (Rakhmatullaev, 2010). The Amu Darya relies almost entirely on precipitation from mountainous regions and the melting of glaciers during the summer. In spring, water flow increases due to snowmelt in the middle sections of the river. During winter, the lower sections of the river often freeze for extended periods, while in the upper sections, melting and shifting ice can form natural dams, leading to sudden flash floods (Britanica, 1998a).

Figure 13: Map of Amu Darya River (USAID, 2024).

Problems and Motivations

Due to minimal summer precipitation in the central and downstream sections, the **extensive use of river water** for irrigation has **caused some tributaries**, such as the Zerafshan, **to dry up** before reaching their confluence (Britannica, 1998b). Moreover, the Amu Darya is **affected by climate change**, with the melting of glaciers leading to altered water availability, which poses challenges to food security and regional stability (Salminen, 2019).

The Amu Darya River basin (**ADRB**) has been the focus of intense disputes among Central Asian countries, especially since the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, when newly independent countries began to face the challenge of sharing water sources. According to the World Bank (2021), **since 1951, there have been 24 significant conflicts** related to water in the basin developed, with the most frequent water disputes occurring between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, **highlighting the serious competition for shared water** (Wang et al., 2021).

Afghanistan is already under a high amount of water stress and this situation will only worsen because of the effects of climate change and a growing population and a predicted doubling of water withdrawals by Afghanistan (International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea - ICWC, 2018). In addition, the heavily inefficient and **wasteful nature of irrigation practices in Turkmenistan** leads to significant water loss, contributing to

water stress in the region (UNECE, 2012). Beginning in the mid-20th century, the river underwent **extensive exploitation**, mainly for irrigation, resulting in it drying up before reaching the Aral Sea (Britannica, 2024c). **Water tensions in the region emerge from conflicting national preferences**, including upstream countries (e.g., Tajikistan) focused on the development of hydropower and the expansion of irrigation, and downstream countries (e.g., Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan) that prioritize agricultural production (especially cotton) and, thus, maintaining access to water (King & Sturtewagen, 2010; Kai et al., 2015). Regional cooperation frameworks have been agreed since the Soviet collapse, with **Afghanistan often excluded from discussions** over water-sharing agreements that have an outsized impact on this war-torn nation, which has the most to lose and gain with respect to the Amu Darya's resources.

The disputes are complicated further by historical deals that do not adequately take into account the realities of water distribution today. **During the negotiations in 1977**, Afghanistan proposed a water-sharing agreement with the Soviet Union but was offered only 6,000 m³ of water per year, which was below Afghanistan's demands, and consensus was never reached (King & Sturtewagen, 2010). Likewise, Soviet-era **irrigation policies** that diverted immense amounts of water for agricultural purposes **furthered the devastating drying of the Aral Sea**, creating yet more regional environmental and economic issues (Salminen, 2019). Decades of **inefficient water use** coupled with the effects of **climate change** have substantially decreased the Amu Darya's flow, heightening dependency on groundwater and complicating trans-boundary relations (King & Sturtewagen, 2010).

Among the most controversial issues have been **large infrastructure works** like dams and reservoirs. The most significant is the **Rogun Dam** in Tajikistan, which started construction in the early **2010s** and has been a major source of contention with Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan is particularly opposed, noting the dam will leave less water for the fields below, cutting agricultural yields, especially of cotton. The project raised **tensions and accusations** that Tajikistan was worsening the situation (Salminen, 2019). The impact of large reservoirs and dams has been a recurring source of conflict, as these infrastructures affect the water flow needed for irrigation in downstream countries (Wang et al., 2021). **In 2016**, Kyrgyzstan announced that it was "freezing" its membership of The International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (**IFAS**) due to the poor consideration of its interests. Since then, it has boycotted water allocation meetings chaired by the International Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC) (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

It can be concluded that **collaboration** and integration across the four riparian nations **remain highly restricted, worsening coordination challenges**. The mandate of the International Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC) and the Amu **Darya Basin Water Organization (BWO)** under it, which includes only three of the bordering countries hold full membership. is **restricted mainly to water allocation, setting water policy, and some capacity-building initiatives**. These bodies lack the authority and resources for comprehensive transboundary water management (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Poor coordination on pollution control, disaster management, and investments in the region's infrastructure has created serious vulnerabilities to climate change in the basin and exacerbated existing debt and social and environmental problems. A large part of this lack of cooperation on infrastructure and investments derives from the legacy of the basin's oversized transboundary water infrastructure — big dams and reservoirs that were built under a centralized management system during the Soviet era. These **structures also now require high-maintenance and extensive renewal** (adelphi and CAREC, 2017). Such a situation proceeds because, in 1991, the states decentralized and nationalized their water management systems, while also distrusting the actions of the other riparian states. Furthermore, the **differing interests** of the basin nations and the inability of existing agreements to comprehensively address all concerns have further **hindered effective cooperation** (adelphi and CAREC, 2017). Although Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan have established agreements that define the current annual water-use rules among them, these **agreements do not include provisions for potential future changes**, which could create significant challenges down the line. Additionally, despite Afghanistan's strong interest in participating, its cooperation efforts are hindered by the fact that it shares a substantial portion of its Amu Darya basin border with Turkmenistan, a country known for its limited approach. **Afghanistan's exclusion from regional discussions** and the failure to account for its water needs in a realistic manner remain critical weaknesses in the existing framework (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Cooperation Methods

Historical treaties, such as the **1873 Frontier Agreement between Afghanistan and Russia** and later **agreements** with the Soviet Union in **1946 and 1958**, primarily focused on establishing territorial boundaries without addressing water sharing (King & Sturtewagen, 2010). In 1977, Afghanistan dispatched a delegation to Tashkent, Uzbekistan, to negotiate a water-sharing agreement. However, the Soviet Union proposed an annual allocation of only 6 km³, falling 3 km³ short of Afghanistan's requested amount. As a result, no agreement was reached (Rycroft & Wegerich, 2009).

In the 1980s, Soviet water authorities created **Basin Water Organizations (BWOs)** to manage the Amu Darya River (ICWC, 2024a). The **1992 Almaty Agreement** (Agreement on Cooperation in the Field of Joint Management of the Use and Conservation of Water Resources in Interstate Sources,) established the foundation for regional cooperation in water management, emphasizing sustainable use of transboundary water resources and promoting dialogue among riparian states (Wang et al., 2021; ICWC, 2024b). In the same year, the **Interstate Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC)** was established to administer water allocations as well as releases in the Amu Darya and Syr Darya river basins, establishing a framework for water management among the countries (Wang et al., 2021). Its role involved promoting operational collaboration for managing shared water resources, such as approving and enforcing water distribution among

the basin nations and setting the primary goals of regional water policy. It also oversaw the existing Amu Darya Basin Water Organization (**BWO**) (ICWC, 2024c). **The International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS) was established in 1993** to tackle the environmental crisis in the Aral Sea basin by fostering collaboration and minimizing ecological degradation (Wang et al., 2021). **The inter-State commission on sustainable development (ICSDD)**, which has operated since approving an agreement in 1993 on joint actions to overcome the Aral Sea crisis, to achieve a sustained improvement of the environment and the socio-economic development of the region of the Aral Sea, is also part of it. The ICSDD indeed governed socioeconomic processes and environmental conditions of the Aral Sea basin. **In 1997, both centers, ICWC, and ICSDD, were captured under the IFAS** during reorganizing institutions (Wang et al., 2021). The function of regional integration as a promoter of cooperation also looked to be a response to the awareness of the member states about the relevance of Aral Sea ecological disaster and the necessity of better coordination of their reaction concerning it (Horsman, 2008).

Management of the basin water resources is defined in the **1999 Ashgabat Declaration**, which covers the **Interstate Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC)** and its executive bodies within the **International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS)**. Combining and consolidating institutions under one umbrella was intended to streamline administrative functions, avoid duplication of services, and improve coordination among stakeholders. Established structures, regular meetings, a secretariat, and the ICWC **Scientific Information Center (SIC)**, regional branches are part and parcel of the mentioned framework. Nevertheless, the effective governance formulation has been challenged and attempts to amend elements of the IFAS architecture during 2008–2012 were unsuccessful (UNECE, 2017). **The 2000 Agreement on the Use of Water Resources of the Amu Darya River** attempted to give specific rules for dividing water according to both upstream and downstream state's needs., while **the 2007 Agreement on Cooperation in the Field of Water Resources Management** was aimed to improving joint water management and the efficiency of resource utilization (Wang et al., 2021).

A noteworthy example of **bilateral success** is Uzbekistan's decision to abandon its long-held opposition to construction of the **Rogun Dam in Tajikistan**. Although Uzbekistan, as a downstream country, is worried that filling the dam will drastically decrease water flows and harm its water security, Uzbekistan ultimately agreed to the project (Putz, 2017; Bekchanov et al., 2015). Likewise, while **Afghanistan** does not engage in regional discussions and its full participation in the ICWC is improbable, it has formed a **bilateral partnership** with **Tajikistan** to oversee the management of the Panj River (UNECE, 2020).

The countries manage water resources daily via the **Amu Darya Basin Water Organization (BWO)**. Additionally, the water authorities of these **countries have collaborated with each other and with international institutions on joint programs and projects** under the **ICWC Scientific Information Center (ICWC)**, (ICWC, 2017a). Yet, in reality, collaboration is primarily restricted to water allocation and some capacity-

building activities. Recent **attempts to reform the IFAS and the ICWC framework have largely failed** due to a lack of trust among the member states (ICWC, 2017b). A key factor contributing to this lack of trust and cooperation is the perception among member states that the Amu Darya Basin Water Organization (BWO) and the ICWC Scientific Information Center (SIC) are primarily Uzbek institutions, as both are headquartered in Uzbekistan (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Nevertheless, **Afghanistan's political instability prevents it from participating in cooperative arrangements** (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020), resulting in its exclusion from regional water management initiatives. Afghanistan was largely excluded from frameworks such as IFAS, and the 1998 Agreement on the Use of Water Resources of the Amu Darya River Basin (which was signed by Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan) even after the dissolution of the Soviet Union (King & Sturtewagen, 2010).

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Regional Cooperation:** Effective water management requires strong regional cooperation among riparian states. The establishment of frameworks like the **ICWC** demonstrates that collaborative governance can facilitate better water resource management.
2. **Need for Comprehensive Agreements:** Comprehensive treaties that address both environmental and socio-economic aspects are crucial. The **Framework Agreement on the Use of Water Resources of the Amu Darya River Basin** exemplifies how integrated approaches can promote equitable water distribution and sustainable management.
3. **Balancing Upstream and Downstream Interests:** Any meaningful diplomacy must take the interests of both upstream and downstream countries into account. **The 2000 Agreement on the Use of Water Resources of the Amu Darya River** emphasizes the importance of setting common standards for all related stakeholders.
4. **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Water management agreements should be flexible and adaptable to changing environmental conditions and socio-political contexts. The evolving nature of water diplomacy in Central Asia illustrates the need for mechanisms that can respond to new challenges, such as climate change and population growth.
5. **Role of International Support:** Cooperation with international organizations and stakeholders can magnify the impact of regional water management endeavours. Entities such as **the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS)** have played a decisive role in mitigating ecological problems while also fostering cooperation.
6. **Building Trust and Communication:** Developing trusts and open lines of communication between countries is crucial for conflict resolution and cross-border cooperation. The history of conflicts

around this resource in Central Asia illustrates how vital it is to have conversation in a positive atmosphere of trust and a mutual understanding.

Irtys River Basin (IRB)

Background

The Irtys River (Figure 14) runs for 4248 km, starting on the western slopes of the Mongolian Altai (China). It flows through Kazakhstan, then joins the Ob River at Khanty-Mansiysk (Russia), and finally meets the Arctic Ocean (Krupa et al., 2024). From Khanty-Mansiysk and northwards the Irtys River Basin (IRB) covers a drainage area of approximately $165 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$ with drainage area percentages of Mongolia (< 1%); China (2.9%), Kazakhstan (53.1%) and Russia (44%) (Xia et al., 2015). The Irtys River is a river of great ecological and hydrological importance as a resource for approximately 15 million people (Radelyuk et al., 2022). Flow varies throughout the year, with the highest flow rates generally seen in the spring (snowmelt) or the summer months (rainfall), both of which are important to maintaining the river's ecological health (Zhang et al., 2017a). The watercourses of the river also have small and big reservoirs that support several hydroelectric power plants. Used for many economic activities including industrial, social, and agricultural purposes, the river is the region's most valuable water source (Krasnoyarova et al., 2019). The wetlands within its water basin are home to a high number of wildlife and support a multitude of fish species.

Figure 14: The Irtys River Basin (Radelyuk et al., 2022).

Problems and Motivations

Anthropogenic activities such as urban sewage and industrial discharges have grown significantly, increasing **pollution** in and around urban areas like Omsk (Gulchenko & Bazhenova, 2016). Moreover, **climate change** has impacted water and snow cover dynamics, further deteriorating the river's ecological status (Zhang et al., 2017). The river has facilitated conflicts between riparian countries and led to significant environmental damage. With the **construction of cascade reservoirs in 1959**, the river's hydrology changed incomparably, leading to very high waterflows which resulted in further downriver **ecological devastation**. For example, at the end of the 1990s the flow in the Russian area of the Irtysh dropped three times in relation to the 1990s; such drop has alarmed over "the quantity and quality" of the water. Furthermore, in 2004 the Chinese government announced plans to use up to 40% of the Irtysh for the Karamay oil fields, causing concerns in Kazakhstan and Russia about potential **over-extraction and depletion** of water downstream. Moreover, the river's **water quality declines** because of industrial emissions and domestic sewage. Notably, the Omsk region experiences the problems of worsening water quality sector (Gulchenko & Bazhenova, 2016). **Discharges from open pits and mines** have also impacted the tributaries of the Irtysh, making the water quality problem even more complex (Radelyuk et al., 2021). These challenges, exacerbated by climate change, include a shift towards earlier snow cover melting and reduced snow depth in late spring, threatening the availability of water in the basin (Zhang et al., 2017a; Gao et al., 2021). **Regional agreements** involving all riparian countries **have not yet been concluded**, so management of the water sources remains ineffective, **disputes over the allocation and management of waters continue** (Krasnoyarova et al., 2019). Even with the adoption of the **1997 UNECE Water Convention**, which serves as a guideline for managing transboundary rivers, **China is not a ratifier, further complicating cooperation** (Biba, 2013).

On the other side, China has increased on a **large scale the extraction of water resources from Kara-Irtysh** that caused disturbances in the state of the aquatic ecosystem of the Lake Zaisan and, accordingly, affected the operation of the Upper Irtysh reservoirs and hydroelectric power plants (Krasnoyarova et al., 2019).

Cooperation Methods

During the Soviet Union, the Irtysh River was managed within a centralized system, with limited need for international agreements. But, with the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, newly independent Kazakhstan inherited a significant portion of the Irtysh basin, necessitating agreements with Russia and China.

In 1992, Russia and Kazakhstan signed an agreement on the joint use and protection of transboundary water bodies, establishing a framework for cooperation. **The Agreement on Cooperation in the Use and Protection of Transboundary Rivers (2001)** mark a crucial step that provided China-Kazakhstan basis for joint management of transboundary water resources (Zonn et al., 2018). **By 2006 Kazakhstan and China** agreed to exchange hydrological and hydrochemical information, facilitating better monitoring and

management of the river. Then in **2008 China and Russia signed an agreement** on the rational use and protection of transboundary waters, further strengthening the legal framework.

The **2011 Sino-Kazakh Agreement (Agreement on the Protection of the Water Quality of Transboundary Rivers)** states the need for mutual activities in the areas of water quality and quantity monitoring, and for providing information about water supply and consumption (Zhiltsov et al., 2018; Zonn et al., 2018; Krasnoyarova et al., 2019). The treaties have led to the establishment of joint commissions aimed at facilitating cooperation in the management of these rivers. The **China-Kazakhstan Joint Commission** has held multiple annual meetings to address issues related to the utilization and protection of transboundary waters, including the Irtysh River (Chen et al., 2013).

Kazakhstan and Russia apply a Basin Management System, which governs the usage and sustenance of the river, including limits on water use, as well as an oversight system over water protection zones (Ministry of Ecology, Geology and Natural Resources, 2019). While **Russia and Kazakhstan** have **established bilateral mechanisms** for water resource management, comprehensive trilateral cooperation with China remains limited. China's upstream water usage continues to be a point of concern for downstream nations, highlighting the need for enhanced multilateral dialogue and sustainable water management practices (Muratshina, 2012). The **1997 UNECE Water Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes** is viewed as a guiding framework for transboundary river management (Biba, 2013), but it is yet to be ratified by China.

Lessons learned

- 1. Importance of Multilateral Agreements:** Multilateral agreements demonstrate the need for collaborative frameworks to effectively manage water resources. They are designed to allow countries to collaborate on issues of shared water resources, exchange information, and plan for long-term sustainable joint management. The Irtysh case demonstrates the shortcomings of bilateral agreements on complex issues such as water allocation and pollution control. **China's non-ratification of the 1997 UNECE Water Convention** hinders comprehensive cooperation and hinders the development of a shared understanding of water rights and responsibilities.
- 2. Need for Joint Monitoring and Data Sharing:** To build trust and facilitate informed decision-making among riparian states, open and transparent data on water quantity, quality, and usage pattern must be made available. China has long been alarmed by Kazakhstan's and Russia's anger about over-extraction that leads to less water in the downstream, because there has not been comprehensive and shared data on water use in China.

3. **Institutional Frameworks and Capacity Building:** The development of institutional frameworks is vital to create institutional partnerships for capacity building and governance. These aspects are catered through institutional frameworks which coordinate action and promote collaboration among stakeholders.
4. **Addressing Political Will and Commitment:** The success of water management diplomacy is often contingent on the **political will** of the involved parties. The lack of political commitment can hinder the implementation of agreements and the establishment of effective management practices.
5. **Early Engagement and Conflict Prevention:** The early engagement among riparian states and proactive dialogue is essential in preventing and resolving conflicts over water resources. They can also contribute to standoffs and undermine development of solutions for sustainable water management.
6. **Adaptation to Changing Conditions:** The complex interplay between water resources, ecosystems, and human activities calls for integrated management approaches that consider social, economic, and environmental factors. Management strategies will have to be assessed continually and adjusted to meet challenges as they occur.
7. **Enhanced Trust and Communication:** Building trust and open communication among the three countries is essential for effective cooperation.

Syr Darya River Basin (SDRB)

Background

The Syr Darya River, the longest river in Central Asia, stretches approximately 3019 km and initiates in the Tian Shan Mountains, traversing Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Kazakhstan before flowing into the Aral Sea (Varis, 2014; Wang et al., 2021). Through its course (Figure 15) several rivers such as Naryn, Karadarya, and Chirchik rivers feed into the Syr Darya (Bernauer & Siegfried, 2012; Britanica, 2024a). The river continues its course, through the northern Turan Plain until it reaches the Aral Sea. The Syr River basin (SDB) is home to five major reservoirs: Toktogul, Andijan, Charvak, Karakum, and Shardarya. Among these, the Toktogul, Andijan, and Charvak reservoirs are found in the upstream areas, while the remaining two are located further downstream (Wang et al., 2021).

The Syr Darya plays a crucial role in supporting crop cultivation in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Kazakhstan. Additionally, electricity-generating facilities are operational in all four countries along the river, with significant facilities located upstream on the Naryn River in Kyrgyzstan (IHA, 2024). The river's flow is predominantly sustained by snowfall in the mountains, supplemented by a portion of glacier meltwater that contributes during the summer season, which keeps water levels high until autumn. In winter, the lower sections of the river freeze, but water flow surges in spring due to snowmelt and higher rainfall, often leading to flood risks (Wang et al., 2021; Simonov, 2024). The river supports several large reservoirs, including

Toktogul, Andijan, and Charvak, which are essential for hydroelectric power generation and agricultural irrigation, particularly in the upstream regions (Wang et al., 2021).

Figure 15: The Syr Darya River Basin (USAID, 2024).

Problems and Motivations

The Syr Darya River once served as a vital water source for the Aral Sea, but since the middle of the 20th century, **extensive irrigation has caused the Aral Sea to nearly vanish** and water flow to be severely reduced (Britanica, 2024). However, **initiatives backed by the World Bank**, such as the building of a dam in 2005 to isolate the Northern Aral Sea, have helped stabilize water levels in the Northern Aral Sea (World Bank Group, 2014). The river's health is further threatened by **climate change**, which endangers the glaciers that feed it, potentially impacting water availability and food security across the region (Salminen, 2023).

Cooperation among these countries **has generally been limited**. The Fergana Valley, shared by Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan, has been a **hotspot for water-related disputes**, driven by **ethnic tensions and competition for fertile land**. For example, **in 1990, clashes broke out** in the Kyrgyz city of Osh over water access, leading to 300 deaths (Megoran, 2004; Wang et al., 2004).

The Syr Darya River has been a matter of numerous disputes among Central Asian countries, particularly following the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, which led to a reconfiguration of water management and allocation practices. One of the primary issues is the **competition for water resources between upstream Kyrgyzstan and downstream Uzbekistan**, with nine recorded conflictive events primarily due to their shared interests in the river. **The construction of the Toktogul Reservoir in Kyrgyzstan** has been particularly

hostile, as it regulates water flow that is crucial for Uzbekistan's agricultural needs, especially during the growing season. In **June 2001, Kyrgyzstan passed a law classifying water as a commodity**, which mandated that downstream countries, including Uzbekistan, would have to pay for water usage, escalating tensions further. This law led to **Uzbekistan cutting off all natural gas deliveries to Kyrgyzstan**, demonstrating the interconnection of water and energy supplies in the area. Moreover, **in 2012, Uzbekistan also cut off natural gas supplies to Tajikistan** in response to Tajikistan's plans to construct the Rogun Dam, which Uzbekistan argued would interrupt its water availability from both the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers (Wang et al., 2021).

Cooperation Methods

The Soviet Water Ministry created the **Syr Darya Basin Water Organisation (BWO) in 1987** for the management of the Syr Darya (ICWC, 2024d). The earliest and arguably the most significant agreement was the **1991 Almaty Agreement** (Agreement on Cooperation in the Field of Joint Management of the Use and Conservation of Water Resources in Interstate Sources), which articulated principles of cooperation between newly independent states of Central Asia and emphasized the need for co-management of transboundary waters (King & Sturtewagen, 2010). One of the main initiatives in this area was the formation of the **Interstate Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC) in 1992** of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan within the framework of the "**Agreement on Cooperation in Joint Management, Use and Protection of Water Resources of Interstate Sources**". It was crucial in establishing the operational framework for water release and resource distribution across the Syr Darya and Amu River basins (Wang et al., 2021). The ICWC, **assumed responsibility for the existing Syr Darya BWO** and was responsible for the collaboration among neighboring countries on the shared management of water resources that cross borders through functional actions, including the approval and implementation of resource sharing between the nations within the basin, and the establishment of the primary focuses of the regional water strategy (ICWC, 2024d).

The five countries founded during **1993 the International Fund to Save the Aral Sea (IFAS)** and the **Interstate Council for the Aral Sea Basin (ICAS)**, which includes the ICWC. It was intended to address environmental and ecological crises faced in the region of the Aral Sea basin aiming to facilitate sustainable development and cooperation between the states. The following year, the **Inter-State Commission on Sustainable Development (ICSD)** was created, which helped manage human and environmental interactions in the Aral Sea area (Wang et al., 2021). **The ICWC, and thus the Syr Darya BWO operating under it**, are tasked with limited, mainly water allocation, quotas and capacity-building activities and only three of the neighboring countries are full members. It lacks the authority and capability to handle wider cross-border water management responsibilities, and as a result needs individual member states to come over these

challenges. Moreover, regional coordination on pollution control, disaster management, and developing infrastructures is also insufficient, making the basin especially vulnerable to the effects of climate change. **The IFAS has no sources of finance of its own, so it has limited potential to invest in the water sector** (OECD, 2020). While water sector financing has grown in recent years, it is still significantly lower than is needed for sustainable management of the required infrastructure (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). **In 1998**, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan reached an agreement (**Agreement on the Joint Use of Water Resources of the Syr Darya River Basin**) to jointly manage the river, with **Tajikistan joining the agreement in 1999**. The goal of the agreement was to ensure mutual advantages by enabling Kyrgyzstan to generate power during the winter while allowing downstream countries to access water for irrigation in the summer (Wang et al., 2021). However, **the agreement could not reflect the multiple needs for the interest of upstream countries in high water years and the interests of downstream countries in low water years**. The newly liberated states evolved at variegated pace and their divergent interests resulted in competing and trust between each other (Saidmamarov et al., 2020) was yet another obnoxious factor. The function of the ICWC and its operational units functioning under the IFAS was outlined in 1999 in connection with the so-called **Ashgabat Declaration**, through which regular meetings, a secretariat, the **ICWC Scientific Information Centre (SIC)** and regional bodies have all been established. Efforts to reform different segments of the IFAS architecture from 2008–2012 were unsuccessful (UNECE, 2017). **In 2000, the Framework Agreement on Water Resources Management in the Countries of the Central Asia** was adopted, which aimed to develop a unified approach of water resources management in the region (Wang et al., 2021). **A positive example of collaboration** in the region, outside the Syr Darya Basin, is the **Chu-Talas Transboundary Water Commission**, formed by Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. Since its establishment **in 2002**, the commission has been actively functioning and regularly benefits from assistance provided by international partners (UNECE, 2024). **In 2016** Kyrgyzstan threatened to “freeze” its participation in the IFAS, in protest of the failure to accommodate its interests, and has not participated in any ICWC resources sharing meetings. Since there is no existing mechanism to officially address such disputes within IFAS, this has resulted in unresolved tensions and challenges (MENAFN, 2024). Since 2016, **better relations between Uzbekistan and its neighboring countries** have enabled more effective collaboration on certain water-related challenges. A significant milestone was the establishment of a bilateral **Joint Working Group on Environmental Protection and Water Quality** in the Syr Darya Basin by Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan **in 2018** (CAREC, 2024). Expanding these bilateral initiatives could serve as a crucial first step toward enhancing regional water management efforts.

Countries sharing the river have shown varying levels of commitment to multilateral agreements. For example, **Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan** have signed the **1991 Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment** in

Transboundary Contexts. Meanwhile, **Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan** have both ratified the **1992 UNECE Water Convention, with Uzbekistan also joining the 1997 UN Watercourses Convention**. Yet Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, positioned upstream, have hesitated to adopt the key UN water agreements, reflecting their cautious stance as upper-basin states (Janusz-Pawletta & Gubaidullina, 2015).

Despite efforts, activities in the basin are marked by **fragmented discussions, limited cooperation, and weak functioning of existing institutional frameworks** (UNECE, 2017). **At the regional level, coordination is primarily focused on operational matters like water allocation and sharing**. The ICWC Scientific Information Centre (SIC) has put forward several proposals to enhance the operational efficiency of the BWO, but these have seen little backing from member states, highlighting a **lack of trust and commitment to multilateral efforts** (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). This issue is further complicated by the perception among riparian states that the Syr Darya BWO and the ICWC SIC are dominated by Uzbekistan, as both institutions are based in the country.

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Regional Cooperation:** Efficient governance of shared water resources across borders depends on strong collaboration between riparian states. Successful examples of this type of cooperation include the formation of institutions like the **ICWC and IFAS**, demonstrating the importance of working together towards common goals when it comes to river basin management.
2. **Need for Comprehensive Agreements:** Agreements such as the "Agreement on the Joint Use of Water Resources of the Syr Darya River Basin" and the "Framework Agreement on Water Resources Management in the Countries of Central Asia" show **that states must draft treaties covering such important aspects** as water distribution and consumption.
3. **Balancing National Interests:** Competing demands over water resources highlight the ability to balance national interests with regional necessities. Each country has its own unique set of priorities, and successful diplomacy incorporates those differences into sustainable deals.
4. **High-Level Political Will:** Water management diplomacy that succeeds needs the political will and commitment of national leaders. It needs high-level engagement to shortcut bureaucratic hurdles and to ensure agreements are implemented.

Aras River Basin (ARB)

Background

The Aras River is a vital transboundary watercourse shared by Türkiye, Armenia, Iran, and Azerbaijan (Figure 16). Stretching approximately 1070 km, the river originates in the southern Lesser Caucasus Mountains and drains a basin area of about 97000 km², with renewable water resources estimated at 7.8 billion m³ (BCM) (Williams et al., 2006; Hajihoseini et al., 2023). Its course delineates the borders between Armenia and Türkiye, as well as between Iran and Armenia, and partially marks the boundary between Azerbaijan and Iran. As the primary southern tributary of the Aras-Kura River system, the river forms part of an international network of waterways that ultimately flows into the Caspian Sea. The Aras River Basin (ARB) is distributed among Türkiye (24.5%), Armenia (23.2%), Iran (39.3%), and Azerbaijan (12.9%). The river is vital in fulfilling the water needs of the surrounding nations for municipal, agricultural, and industrial purposes (Hajihoseini et al., 2023).

Figure 16: The Aras River Basin (Hajihoseini et al., 2023).

Problems and Motivations

The Aras River has been **at the center of disputes among the riparian states** due to the geopolitics and environmental issues. **The fall of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) in 1991 initiated a prolonged conflict**, especially with the subsequent aggravation of **the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict** which

rapidly escalated in **1992 with military actions endangering hydraulic structures**, including the Khoda-Afarin Dam where **rockets exploded in 1994**. From **1995 to 2017, water quality concerns escalated**, such as issues caused by pollution from Armenia's industrial sector, leading to serious contamination of the Aras River and further alarms raised by Iran and Azerbaijan over declining water quality (Bozkurt, 2025). **During the 2018–2021 period**, the situation was aggravated when **Türkiye started filling the Karakurt Dam** and Iran protested over reduced water discharges, accusing Türkiye of **not fulfilling the 1955 water protocol** to supply minimum flow from the Sarisu River (Hajihoseini, 2023). **Iran has also objected to the construction of a border wall by Türkiye** along the Iran-Türkiye border initiated in 2017, arguing it disturbs natural flows of water and environmental conditions (Hajihoseini et al., 2023).

Cooperation Methods

The first phase of cooperation took place during the **Soviet Union era (1926–1990)**, which focused on infrastructure construction, water quantity management, and joint governance. During this time, the riparian states worked together to build key projects, **such as the Aras Dam** (between the USSR and Iran) with a capacity of 1350 million m³ (MCM) **and the Akhurian (Arpachay) Dam** (between the USSR and Türkiye) with a capacity of 525 MCM (Soghoian, 2009). In 1921, **the Soviet Union and Iran entered a friendship treaty** that included provisions addressing water-related matters, specifically **the use of rivers and border waters along the Caspian Sea**, such as the Etrak and Aras rivers.

The Treaty of Moscow in 1921 defined the thalweg of the Aras and Akhurian Rivers as the geographic border between Türkiye and the USSR, which was crucial for establishing the framework for future cooperation (Kibaroglu et al. 2011). Following this, **in 1927, the Protocol on the Beneficial Uses of Boundary Waters** was established, granting both nations the right to develop water-related infrastructure on tributaries within their territories of the Aras River, provided these projects did not negatively impact the neighboring country (Soghoian, 2009). Later, in **1957, Iran and the USSR reached an agreement** to develop initial plans for the shared use of the Aras River's water for irrigation and power generation, stressing that even if one side used its portion of resources more slowly, it would not restrict the other side from utilizing its fair share (Hajihoseini et al., 2023).

In 1963, Türkiye and the Soviet Union (which included Armenia at the time) **signed an agreement** centered on constructing a dam along the Akhurian River. The dam was built between 1975 and 1980 and became operational in 1980 (Kibaroglu et al., 2011). **In 1973, a Permanent Joint Commission was established** for the operation of the Aras Dam between the **USSR and Iran**, further solidifying cooperative management of the river (Hajihoseini et al., 2023). A **similar commission was established between the USSR and Türkiye** to manage and develop the Arpaçay/Akhuryan Dam. Additionally, a joint **memorandum of understanding** was **signed in 1988** between **Iran and the USSR** for the construction and operation of the Khodaafarin and

Qiz-Qalasi regulatory dams downstream of the Aras Dam, although construction was delayed due to geopolitical tensions (Hajihoseini et al., 2023).

The Council of Ministers of the **USSR and the Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic in 1962** reached an agreement to divert the Arpa River into Lake Sevan. Later, **in 1974, the Armenian Soviet Socialist Republic and Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic signed a further agreement** to channel water from the Vorotan River into the lake (Yu et al. 2015). Vorotan and Arpa rivers flow into the Aras River as its tributaries. **In 2006, Armenia and Azerbaijan joined the European Union (EU) Neighborhood Policy action**, committing to enhance regional cooperation, particularly in addressing water-related challenges. This agreement obligates both nations to create integrated river basin management plans. Additionally, they must adopt legislation and policies that comply with the **EU Water Framework Directive (WFD)** (Hannan et al., 2013). **In 2006, Iran and Armenia** took a notable step toward tackling environmental issues by creating a **Joint Working Group** to monitor the water quality of the Aras River (Aubrey, 2014). By **2015**, they further agreed to develop a **shared online system for real-time monitoring of the river's water quality**. Earlier, in **2007, Iran and Armenia signed a cooperation agreement to develop a joint hydropower project** at Meghri and Qharachilar. In 2014, **Iran and Azerbaijan** reached an **agreement to collaborate on constructing the Ordobad and Marazad** hydropower plants along the Aras River. Furthermore, **in 2016, Iran and Azerbaijan reached an agreement** that established a **Joint Technical Committee** to address technical and financial matters related to the river (Hajihoseini et al., 2022). The mentioned **agreements and discussions** have led to multiple collaborative water projects, **making the Aras basin unique in this region**.

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Cooperative Frameworks:** Cooperative frameworks among riparian states are necessary for effective management of shared water resources. Current agreements like Treaty of Moscow (1921) and other agreements emphasize the need for formalization of collaboration.
2. **Joint Infrastructure Development:** Collaborative infrastructure projects like dams and irrigation systems would improve water management and reduce tensions. Also, joint projects can lead to mutual benefits and improved relations.
3. **Monitoring and Data Sharing:** Establishing mechanisms for monitoring and data-sharing on water quality and quantity among countries is essential to enable informed decision-making. An example of this approach is the jointly formed working group between Iran and Armenia that monitors the water quality of the Aras River.

Brahmaputra River Basin (BRB)

Background

The Brahmaputra River, known as the Yarlung Tsangpo in the Tibet and the Jamuna in Bangladesh, originates in Tibet Autonomous Region (TAR) of China, and empties into the Bay of Bengal (Vij et al., 2024). The river is the fourth largest in the world in terms of annual discharge. The Brahmaputra River Basin (BRB) (Figure 17) is shared between four countries: China (50.5% of the total basin area), India (33.6%), Bangladesh (8.1%), and Bhutan (7.8%). It has an area of 580000 km² home to over 100 million people, predominantly farmers (Barua, 2018). The river creates livelihood, inland water navigation and hydropower development opportunities. Most people rely on agriculture, livestock, forestry, fisheries and enterprises on the riverbank (Barua et al., 2017).

Figure 17: The Brahmaputra River Basin (Vij, 2020).

The Brahmaputra River itself transverses three physiographic provinces, the Tibetan Plateau in China, the Himalayan region shared by China and India, and the alluvial floodplains of both India and Bangladesh. In these regions, the hydrological effects of climate change are expected to be major, resulting from the interactions of glacial melt, monsoon variation and rising sea levels (Vij et al., 2019).

Problems and Motivations

Communities in the Brahmaputra's flood-prone downstream floodplain have been increasingly experiencing **severe flooding** induced by rising river levels and **prolonged drought** associated with changing monsoon patterns (Vij et al., 2019). Increased socio-economic demands across Bangladesh and India such as **population growth and energy consumption are leading to greater pressure on the river** (Rasul, 2014). Continued **tensions between India and Bangladesh** exist regarding flood management strategies and resource development on the Brahmaputra River (Bassett & Fogelman, 2013). Bangladesh has experienced **asymmetry of power in bilateral negotiations** with India on the Ganges and Teesta Rivers (Ho, 2016). Currently, there is **no comprehensive international treaty** that governs the management of the Brahmaputra basin that includes all four riparian nations (Barua, 2018). Although **some bilateral agreements and Memoranda of Understanding have been signed** to address specific issues such as flood warning and information sharing, **attempts to establish a basin-wide management framework have been difficult to take place**. Moreover, **changing regional politics** affect cooperation possibilities (Barua, 2018). The political sensitivity of the Brahmaputra has also led to the 'securitisation' of water, and indeed, even basic data on streamflow, sediment transport, water withdrawals and use has been constrained (Surie & Prasai 2015). This **lack of transparency** has created an atmosphere of mistrust, hostility, and suspicion in basin countries that hinders cooperation on joint water management (Barua, 2018). **India's completion of the Farakka Barrage in 1975**, which has been alleged to divert water from the Ganges and affect the flow of the Brahmaputra has also contributed to making Bangladesh water-scarce in the dry season (Banerjee, 1999). Moreover, Bangladesh's concerns about **India's proposed construction of multiple hydropower projects** in Arunachal Pradesh such as the Lower Subansiri Hydroelectric Project have arisen as they would change the flow and sediment transportation in the river, leading to **greater flooding and degradation downstream** (Ahmed, 2007). Furthermore, **the lack of a comprehensive water-sharing agreement has led to tensions**, as Bangladesh has repeatedly sought negotiations with India through the **Joint Rivers Commission (JRC)** to address these issues, but satisfactory resolutions have yet to be achieved (Chowdhury, 2010). **The 1996 Ganges Water Treaty** between India and Bangladesh, while addressing some water-sharing issues, leaves **ambiguities** (Lebel et al., 2010). The water-sharing agreements between India and Bangladesh (Tanzeema & Faisal, 2001) may need to be revised to address the impacts of climate change, as snowmelt patterns often fail to coincide with periods of highest water demand downstream, highlighting the region's sensitivity to climate variability (Subedi, 1999). **The 1996 Ganges River Treaty** includes provisions for water releases to Bangladesh, which remains highly vulnerable to upstream diversions. However, with future water availability likely insufficient to meet the needs of both countries, the potential for more **serious conflicts could increase** (Lebel et al., 2010). **China's Zangmu Hydroelectric Power Station**, launched in 2015, is the first large-scale hydropower facility on the Brahmaputra River (India Today, 2014). Additionally, **China's 12th Five-Year**

Plan of Energy Development, effective from 1 January 2013, intended to construct three more dams on the same river. China is also advancing a major **South-North water diversion project** involving the Brahmaputra (Barua, 2018). These developments have raised alarms in India, which worries that reduced downstream flows could harm its economy and environment. India perceives China's actions as unilateral, especially in hydropower development, and criticizes its lack of transparency and information sharing (Ho, 2013).

The lack of a formal water-sharing agreement between India and China has left India vulnerable to unilateral actions by China, creating a precarious situation for water governance (Bhatt, 2022). The lack of a trustworthy, comprehensive, and authoritative scientific data network for the basin (Biswas, 2011) adds complexity to decision-making, especially concerning water infrastructure projects in the region. This gap has resulted in uncertain outcomes and fostered distrust and suspicion among communities sharing the river (Barua, 2018).

Methods of Cooperation

Although, transboundary-level water cooperation between Bangladesh and India is limited (Barua et al., 2018; Hill, 2013), one significant initiative is **the Indo-Bangladesh Joint Rivers Commission (JRC)**, established in **1972**. **JRC** serves as a platform for both countries to address issues related to transboundary rivers and work towards equitable water sharing (Ahmed, 2007). **The Ganges Water Treaty (GWT), signed in 1996**, marked a milestone in water-sharing agreements between Bangladesh and India. Although it primarily focused on the Ganges, it set a precedent for future negotiations regarding the Brahmaputra. Additionally, the proposed establishment of a **River Basin Organization (RBO)** has been advocated as an apex body to facilitate integrated water resources management among co-riparian countries, promoting cooperation and conflict resolution (Ahmed, 2007).

The 1996 Mahakali Treaty between India and Nepal addresses water resource management and hydropower development, facilitating cooperation on shared river systems, including tributaries of the Brahmaputra (Rahaman, 2009). **The 1996 India-Nepal Power Trade Agreement**, for instance, moved discussions about hydroelectric power sales from national governments to private entities (Crow & Singh, 2009). **The 2005 Memorandum of Understanding between India and China** aimed to facilitate the sharing of hydrological data, yet the effectiveness of this agreement has been limited, as both countries have struggled to establish substantial cooperation mechanisms for water management (Xie & Jia, 2017). Moreover, **informal cooperation has been observed through expert dialogues**, such as the **Dhaka Declaration on Water Security** issued in **January 2010**, which called for improved data sharing and transparency regarding water flows, particularly during low flow seasons (BIPSS & SFG, 2010). **The Brahmaputra Dialogue** project was **launched in 2013**, to address these pressing issues through **multi-track diplomacy**, yet the effectiveness of such initiatives remains limited (Barua, 2018). Also, **the 2015 Ganges River Agreement**, though not

pertaining to Brahmaputra directly, laid the groundwork for future negotiations by laying the basis for data sharing and collaborative use of common water. **The first bilateral meeting between India and Bangladesh on the Brahmaputra River** took place in **2018**, indicating a shared realization about the importance of a collaborative approach to transactional issues like water sharing and management. In addition, **sharing real-time data on river flows during the monsoon season in 2019** was a significant step towards better flood management and disaster preparedness in the region (Vij et al. 2019).

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Trust and Transparency:** The collaboration between China and India emphasizes the need for developing trust through open and clear communication and information exchange. Particularly in a context where water resources are potential causes of conflict, trust is critical for effective collaboration.
2. **Addressing Broader Regional Concerns:** Cooperative water management can assist with more widespread regional concerns, like the effects of climate change as well as water scarcity. That is why coordination is vital to devise strategies benefiting populations and promoting regional stability.
3. **Challenges in Implementation:** Despite the frameworks and agreements, challenges remain in the implementation of cooperative measures. Political will, domestic pressures, and differing national priorities can hinder progress. Also, continuous dialogue and commitment are necessary to overcome these challenges.

Ganges River Basin (GRB)

Background

The transboundary Ganges River (Figure 18) forms in India at the confluence of several tributaries originating from the Himalayan Mountains of Tibet (China) and India. After receiving additional tributaries from Nepal, the Ganges continues its journey in India until it enters Bangladesh, where it joins the Brahmaputra River to form the Barak–Meghna River, which empties into the Bay of Bengal (Lebel et al., 2010; Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2012). The Ganges, or Ganga as it is known there, is the largest river basin in India and considered a holy river for Hindus (Alley, 2012).

The Ganges River spans approximately 2525 km, with a basin area close to 1.1 million km² (Mirza, 2004). About 80% of the Ganges River Basin (GRB) is in India, about 18% in Bangladesh and about 2% is in Nepal and China. The GRB is one of the most densely populated regions globally with a total population of more than 300 million (Salman, 1998). The river is characterized by its extensive floodplain, which supports diverse

ecosystems and provides fertile land for agriculture (Gopal, 2004). Bangladesh owes the fertility of its soil in its southwestern territory to the Ganges.

Figure 18: The Ganges River Basin (Mirza, 2004).

Problems and Motivations

The river's hydrological dynamics are influenced by seasonal monsoons, which can lead to both **flooding and drought**, impacting water availability for millions of people who depend on it for drinking, sanitation, and irrigation (Nishat & Faisal, 2000). The Ganges represents a complex interplay of reverence, ecological significance, and pressing environmental challenges that necessitate comprehensive management strategies (Swain, 2004). However, the Ganges River has long been **a source of conflict between India and Bangladesh**, primarily stemming from issues surrounding **water allocation and pollution**. This is because of **India's hydro hegemony** that has tended to apply the absolute sovereignty principle to water resources management. A pivotal moment in these disputes occurred in **1975** when India constructed **the Farakka Barrage**, designed to divert water for improving navigation in the Hooghly River and reducing siltation in Calcutta. While the barrage served India's purposes, it drastically **reduced water flow** downstream to Bangladesh, especially during the dry season. This diversion resulted in **severe water shortages in Bangladesh**, particularly in the agricultural and drinking water sectors (Salman, 1998). Once **a short-lived agreement** in 1975 expired and bilateral relations deteriorated, **India proceeded with the unilateral development** of the river (Swain, 2004). The construction of the Farakka Barrage **triggered the first major water-sharing conflict** between the two countries, leading to the **1977 agreement** covering lean seasons from 1978 to 1982. This agreement, while important, was seen as a temporary measure and **failed to provide a lasting solution**.

Subsequent attempts to address the issue included a **Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) in 1982**, renewed in 1985, but these agreements also **fell short of resolving the core tensions**. Following the expiration of the 1985 MOU, Bangladesh suffered from acute water shortages, **leading to escalating tensions between the nations** (Salman, 1998; Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2012). By the early 1990s, the situation had worsened, with **water scarcity** becoming a pressing issue, affecting agriculture, drinking water, and the livelihoods of people in Bangladesh. Both nations returned to the negotiating table in hopes of finding a more sustainable resolution, but frustrations mounted as a lack of formal cooperation persisted (Salman, 1998). Apart from water allocation, **the pollution of the Ganges** further exacerbates tensions. **India is responsible for significant pollution in the river**, with 87% of untreated sewage from Indian cities discharged directly into the water, leading to high levels of contamination. This pollution affects both countries but is particularly detrimental to Bangladesh, where the downstream effects compromise public health and the agricultural sector (Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2012). Moreover, **India's National River Linking Project**, proposed in 1982 and revived in 2002, seeks to divert water from the Ganges to other basins, raising alarms in Bangladesh about potential reductions in water availability and heightened salinity intrusions in the delta (Lebel et al., 2010).

Cooperation methods

Cooperation methods regarding the Ganges water in the context of transboundary conflicts between India and Bangladesh have been formalized through several treaties and agreements aimed at managing shared water resources. The first significant agreement was **the 1977 Treaty**, which established a framework for sharing the Ganges waters (60:40) during the dry season for 5 years (Abbas, 1982; Mirza, 1998). The **Side Letter to the 1977 Agreement**, included a reference to **Nepal** as well (Salman, 1998). This was followed by the **1982 and the 1985 Memorandum of Understandings**, which were effective until May 31, 1988 (Salman, 1998). **After a prolonged period of negotiation** and a vacuum of cooperation lasting over eight years, **the two countries signed the 1996 Treaty**, which marked a significant advancement in their bilateral relations by providing a comprehensive framework for sharing the Ganges waters during the dry season (Dixit and Mirza, 1997). In the Treaty, the overall ratio of water-sharing is 52:48 for Bangladesh and India. This treaty also fostered **an environment encouraging to ongoing dialogue and cooperation** on water-related issues, including the potential for future agreements on enhancing the river's flow (Salman, 1998; Mirza, 2004). The Treaty has resolved a long-standing problem between Bangladesh and India. However, the withdrawal of water upstream of Farakka has put the Treaty to a difficult test. The implication is that the treaty discharge values are less likely to occur than they are expected (Mirza, 2004).

The **bilateral Committee on Flood Forecasting** was established in **2008** between **India and Nepal** to enhance data sharing and improve flood management strategies, thereby promoting regional cooperation (Lebel et al., 2010). **Nepal and India have signed treaties** over dam construction to generate hydropower,

expansion of irrigation, and building embankments for flood management (Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2012). Furthermore, pressure from **domestic environmental non-governmental organizations (DNGOs)** has played a crucial role in advocating for cleaner water and compliance with existing legislation, demonstrating the influence of civil society in shaping water governance (Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2010). Additionally, the establishment of the **Joint River Commission between India and Bangladesh in 2011** has facilitated dialogue, cooperation, and addressing emerging challenges, highlighting the importance of collaborative approaches in managing transboundary water resources (Salman, 1998; Bhatt, 2022).

The Ganges River Basin Management Plan, initiated in 2013 in collaboration with various stakeholders, aims to promote sustainable water management practices and enhance cooperation among riparian states. Furthermore, initiatives such as **the South Asia Water Governance Programme**, launched in 2015, have been developed to foster regional collaboration and improve water governance frameworks, emphasizing the importance of data sharing and joint research activities among countries in the region (Bhatt, 2022). Above all, **no treaty on the Ganges among the four riparian states** was ever concluded, **nor** has any **joint river basin management forum** for all riparian states been set.

Lessons learned

1. **Importance of Formal Agreements:** Establishing formal treaties, such as the **1977 Treaty** and the **1996 Treaty**, is crucial for regulating water sharing and fostering cooperation between countries.
2. **Role of Institutions:** The establishment of institutions like the **Indo-Bangladesh Joint Rivers Commission** is essential for facilitating scientific studies and discussions on water management.
3. **Addressing Root Causes:** Recognizing that **addressing the root causes of water scarcity**, such as the need for flow augmentation, is vital for sustainable management, as treaties have often focused on sharing arrangements without adequately tackling water availability.
4. **Limited Scope of Cooperation:** The primary focus of cooperation (e.g., the **1996 treaty**) has been on water quantity, neglecting other crucial issues like flood management, drought mitigation, drainage congestion, and water quality. This narrow focus hinders comprehensive and sustainable solutions for the entire basin.
5. **Dominance of Bilateral Negotiations:** India's insistence on bilateral negotiations has prevented the formation of a more equitable and inclusive framework for decision-making. This approach benefits India by maintaining its dominant position and limiting the influence of other riparians, particularly Bangladesh and Nepal.
6. **Perceived Hegemonic Behavior:** India's actions and negotiating stances are perceived by upstream and downstream neighbors as prioritizing its own interests at the expense of others. This perception of

hegemonic behavior erodes trust and hinders cooperation. **The role of non-governmental organizations** demonstrates the influence of civil society in shaping water governance.

Harirud River Basin (HRB)

Background

The Harirud River with a length of 1124 km and a basin area of 112000 km², originates 250 km west of Kabul Province in Afghanistan (Figure 19). Its biggest tributary, Kabgan River, joins Harirud River approximately 70 km east of Herat Province (Shroder and Ahmadzai, 2016). The river, then, flows northward to form a 160 km Afghan–Iran political border (Kamran et al., 2017), and continues further north to form a 170 km Turkmen–Iran political border before it reaches the Karakum desert in Turkmenistan (Thomas and Warner, 2015). The total annual available water flow of the Harirud River is 1.6 billion cubic meters (BCM), of which 1.07 BCM reaches Iran and Turkmenistan’s Doosti Dam located at their political border (Nagheeby and Warner, 2018). The basin is characterized by its asymmetric socio-economic factors, where upstream Afghanistan's water management strategies directly impact the downstream countries of Iran and Turkmenistan (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018). The river's flow is crucial for agricultural and economic activities in these regions, making it a vital resource for all riparian states.

Figure 19: The Harirud River Basin (Loodin & Warner, 2022).

Problems and Motivations

The Harirud River Basin (HRB) has been a **focal point of conflict among** Afghanistan, Iran, and Turkmenistan, primarily due to unilateral actions taken by all riparian states regarding water resource development. The legal agreements established between **Iran and the Soviet Union in 1921 and in 1926 excluded Afghanistan** from any negotiations regarding the construction of dams or the allocation of water resources (Sinaee, 2012), which has led to persistent concerns and actions for Afghanistan. For instance, while **Iran and the Soviet Union** were negotiating the construction of a common downstream dam in 1974, **Afghanistan sought assistance from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)** to analyze its own dam project, indicating a desire for **international support in the face of growing tensions** (Wadsam News, 2013). Afghanistan had planned for this project **with support from India and Britain**. However, significant delays due to internal conflicts and civil wars, prevented its construction until after the U.S. intervention in 2001 (Pant, 2010; Wadsam News, 2013).

The Afghans were concerned particularly regarding the **Doosti Dam** that was officially **opened in 2004** on the Iran-Turkmenistan border. The early opening of the dam is interpreted as a strategic move by Iran and Turkmenistan to solidify their claims over water resources before Afghanistan could assert its rights (Sinaee, 2012). **A significant escalation occurred in 2013** when Afghanistan began construction on **the Kamal Khan Dam**, which raised immediate concerns in both Iran and Turkmenistan about potential reductions in water flow that could adversely affect their agricultural and domestic water supplies (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018). In the same year, **Afghan officials indicated a preference to postpone negotiations** until after the completion of their water control initiatives, **further entrenching the cycle of mistrust**.

The **lack of effective communication and negotiation mechanisms** has led to a defensive posture from Iran and Turkmenistan, who seek to protect their water rights while Afghanistan continues its unilateral development. In 2015, Iran and Turkmenistan expressed their concerns regarding Afghanistan's water management policies, fearing that the dam's construction would exacerbate their vulnerability to water shortages. Moreover, the opening of the **Salma Dam** (Afghan-India Friendship Dam) **in 2016**, with the help of the **US, raised concerns in Iran and Turkmenistan** about reduced downstream water flow and ecological impacts (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018). For instance, studies predict that the dam **could reduce water discharge by as much as 73%**. In addition to the Salma Dam, **Afghanistan has been developing several new irrigation schemes** along the Harirud River with the backing of the Asian Development Bank (ADB) (ADB, 2005; CFC, 2013).

The geopolitical dynamics further complicated these conflicts, as both Iran and Turkmenistan viewed the presence of external powers, particularly the United States and India, in Afghanistan as a direct threat to their national security. They were concerned that these powers might support Afghan projects that could alter the hydrological balance in the basin, intensifying their fears of water scarcity (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018).

Diplomatic tensions escalated in 2016 when Iranian officials criticized Afghanistan for its unilateral water projects. Iran's concerns were rooted in the belief that Afghanistan's actions could destabilize the region's water balance, prompting Iran to seek assurances regarding its water rights. **By 2018, Afghanistan continued to pursue its water development projects**, including the construction of additional dams, **without formal agreements** with Iran and Turkmenistan. This ongoing development further strained relations, as both downstream countries felt increasingly marginalized and threatened by Afghanistan's actions.

Cooperation methods

There is **no formal signed agreement between all the riparian states** on the utilization and allocation of water resources of the HRB. However, there was formal agreements between **Iran and the Soviet Union**, which have **excluded Afghanistan**. The first significant legal framework concerning water allocation was established between **Iran and the Soviet Union in 1921**, known as the **Agreement on the Regimes of Border Rivers**, which was followed by a further **agreement in 1926** on equal utilization (50/50) of the Harirud River (Sinaee, 2012) that further addressed water allocation (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018). These treaties established a framework for managing the river's resources. The lack of Afghan involvement in these early agreements has contributed to ongoing tensions and conflicts over water rights.

Apart from an **unbinding 1973 water accord** between Iran and Afghanistan that defined an acceptable rate of discharge from the Helmand, there are no formal water-sharing agreements. Trust was further undermined when the accord was **violated by Afghanistan during a drought between 1998 and 2002**. On the other hand, in 2004, the downstream co-riparian states of Harirud River Basin **built the Doosti Dam** at the downstream of the Harirud River **without negotiating with the Afghan government** (Shroder & hmadzai, 2016), of which its storage capacity has been 1.25 BCM (Nagheeby et al., 2019). The dam provides irrigation and drinking water for the downstream nations.

Both Iran and Turkmenistan, in letters sent to the Afghan government in **2006 and 2010**, requested the trilateral cooperation in the management of water resources of the Harirud River, for which the request had no response (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018). The past negotiations regarding water arrangements, like those established between Iran and Russia in the earlier years of the 20th century, have set the foundation upon which contemporary legal principles regarding water allocation in the basin are built, making it necessary to strive for a cooperative approach, which can help combat water scarcity while balancing conflicts emerging from neighboring states (Nagheeby & Warner, 2018).

Lessons learned

1. **Lack of Agreement:** Since there was **no transboundary water agreement** between Afghanistan and its neighbors, downstream riparian, Iran and Turkmenistan, were able to pursue a resource-capturing strategy such as building the Doosti dam at times when Afghanistan was in a state of turmoil.
2. **External Influence:** Foreign construction of dams in Afghanistan was driven by geopolitical interests of outside actors like the US and India, emphasizing **the role of external/intervening actors in reshaping basin dynamics**.
3. **Political Instability:** The Taliban regime was unstable and unrecognized which was causing the political and socio-economic conditions of Afghanistan to worsen, inducing the migration of experts and professionals.
4. **Downstream Dominance:** Iran and Turkmenistan, with their economic and military strength, are all set to continue their hydro-hegemonic dominance over the basin.
5. **Excluding one of the riparian countries from agreements often leads to significant tensions and disputes**, ultimately hindering long-term success. Ongoing disputes regarding water management and resource allocation in the region are indicative of the failure of inclusive agreements which take all three countries into consideration (Afghanistan, Iran, and Turkmenistan), further underscoring the need for comprehensive cooperation leading to sustainable outcomes.
6. **The historical context** of these conflicts is also significant. Decades of **Soviet occupation and civil wars in Afghanistan** had resulted in huge losses for its leadership that, as a result, has always felt the need to set development projects as a priority to regain the opportunities lost. This peaked with the Afghan government's unwillingness to debate the terms with Iran and Turkmenistan, as officials thought negotiations would slow down their existing processes.
7. **The upstream state does not have the potential of becoming a strong hydro hegemon given its economic and socio-political status** despite its geographic location

Koshi River Basin (KRB)

Background

The Koshi River originates from high-altitude Tibetan Plateau of China and navigates distinct physiographic regions such as the Himalayas and the Terai plains before converging with the Ganga-River in India (Sharma, 2017) (Figure 20). The entire catchment area is 74030 km² (FMIS, 2012). An estimated 43% of the landmass rests within the border of China, 42% within that of Nepal and 15% in that of India (Sharma, 1997; FMIS, 2012). The southern basin is dominated by the South Asian monsoon, whereas the northern Tibetan Plateau

belongs to a rain shadow zone. Nepal experiences four seasons: pre-monsoon, monsoon, post-monsoon, and winter (Prasad, 2021). It contains a rich biodiversity and is a source of valuable ecosystem services that directly sustain the lives and livelihoods of the 40 million basin inhabitants as well as contributing to the livelihoods of many more people downstream. The basin is significant due to its potential for hydropower generation and irrigation. But it is also extremely disposed to natural disasters such as glacial lake outburst floods, landslides or sedimentation. The risks are even greater because of the young geological structures in the region and the significant impact of monsoons seasons, water etc, (Wahid et al., 2017).

Figure 20: The Koshi River Basin (Lamsal et al., 2024).

Problems and Motivations

The basin faces significant water-related risks, such as **dangerous flooding events and landslides**. The high elevation and diverse terrain, young geological formations, prevalent glaciation and strong influence of monsoon render the region **prone to erosion, sedimentation and natural hazards including glacial lake outburst floods, landslides, debris flows, droughts and floods** (Wahid et al. 2017). There are also **frequent droughts** in the rain-fed tributaries in the dry season. Moreover, **urbanization** and the invasion of floodplains has compounded pressures on the basin's water bodies and ecosystems (Wahid et al., 2017).

Climate change is expected to worsen these challenges, impacting seasonal water accessibility and threatening food and energy security (Wahid et al., 2017). Global warming is predicted to alter important hydrological processes in the Himalayan headwaters, such as rainfall, evaporation, and river flow. These

changes could have significant consequences for water availability in downstream areas (Eriksson et al., 2009). Variations in the amount, timing and intensity of rainfall are likely to change the flow of water that will in turn impact the ecosystems and the ecosystem services they provide for human wellbeing and livelihood (Dixit et al., 2009). According to model predictions, **Nepal's mean annual temperature is likely to rise** by 1.4°C in 2030, 2.8°C in 2060, and 4.7°C in 2090 based on Global Climate Models (**GCMs**) and Regional Climate Models (**RCMs**) (NCVST, 2009).

Studies identified notable variations over time and space in key hydrological parameters, including precipitation patterns, actual evapotranspiration rates, and water yield, with distinct differences observed between the basin's northern and southern regions (Bharati et al., 2012).

The frequent and severe floods in the Koshi River provide strong evidence to support the observations and findings that highlight the extensive damage to property, agriculture, and loss of lives in Nepal's Terai plain and India's Bihar region at various times, such as in 1869, 1870, 1954, 1968, 1971, 1980, 1984, and 1991 (Mishra, 2008). One of the most recent catastrophic floods occurred in August 2008. This flood resulted in the deaths of 4–6 people, impacted 6000 hectares of farmland, destroyed crops valued at USD 3.7 million, displaced 40,378 individuals from 7102 families, and caused damage to 4 km of the east-west highway in Nepal (ICIMOD, 2008). The destruction was even more severe in India, where 42 lives were lost, 35,000 hectares of crops were ruined, over one million people were affected, and more than 70000 were displaced (ICIMOD, 2008).

Cooperation methods

The Koshi River faces frequent floods and caused extensive damage, leading to flood management efforts in India and Nepal including the **Koshi River Agreement of 1954**. However, the Koshi flood of 2008 raised questions in both countries about the efficacy of the current Koshi barrage and existing river embankment. Consequently, the **Koshi High Dam Project**, initially proposed in 1937 as a solution to combat flooding, has been given renewed priority as an integral part of flood mitigation, irrigation, and hydropower generation effort (Devkota & Gyawali, 2015). **The International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD)** established in 1983 is a regional center focusing on knowledge development and learning that aims to develop a complete understanding of basin system dynamics (**ICIMOD, 2024**). ICIMOD's Regional Member Countries (RMCs) are Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, India, Myanmar, Nepal, and Pakistan. Through impact analysis and enabling informed decision making, ICIMOD is strengthening the river basin management framework for more systematic and sustainable responses to these challenges. At ICIMOD, the **Koshi Basin Programme** used the **driver-pressure-state-impact-response (DPSIR)** framework to embrace a holistic, systems-based approach. This strategy hopes to bridge various disciplinary knowledge covering the scientific, economic, social, and ecological domains, which informs decision-making

mechanisms in governing transboundary water resources sustainably, while also indicating trade-offs arising due peacekeeping and development agendas (Sharma, 2017).

The **HKH-HYCOS regional flood monitoring system** established by ICIMOD facilitates sharing of knowledge and provides riverine flood alerts in vulnerable communities as a tool for preparedness against disasters in Nepal and India. Shrestha et al. (2015) has proposed this system to provide real-time hydrological data, including river water levels, to improve the flood forecasting system. For instance, Nepal's Department of Hydrology and Meteorology employed this service, through an official bulletin on its homepage, to issue nationwide flood advisories (Shrestha & Pradhan, 2015). A striking cross-border example was when literally upstream communities in Nepal's Mahottari district relayed real-time flood alerts through ICIMOD's experimental **Community-Based Flood Early Warning System** to downstream populations in neighbouring Bihar, India on 12 August 2007. This project provided 4–8 hours of early warning for residents to be evacuated to safe shelters and livestock to higher ground (Vaidya et al., 2022).

The governance of the KRB involves **three key committees**. In 2000, following diplomatic discussions between India and Nepal, the **Joint Committee on Water Resources (JCWR)** was formed at the secretary level to coordinate transboundary water management. During its inaugural meeting in Kathmandu later that year, the JCWR proposed consolidating existing committees into the **Joint Committee on Koshi and Gandak Projects (JCKGP)**, led by director generals. The JCKGP convened for the first time in December 2001. After the Koshi embankment breach in August 2008, the JCWR expanded the JCKGP's mandate to include operational and financial oversight of annual development plans. In 2008, the JCWR also established the **Joint Standing Technical Committee (JSTC)** at the joint-secretary level to supervise project-specific and hazard-related initiatives, directing the JCKGP to align with its technical guidance (Vaidya et al., 2022).

Lessons learned

- 1) **Holistic Transboundary Collaboration:** Institutionalized cooperation is necessary to mitigate risks in shared river basins. Formal mechanisms for dialogue, resource allocation and technical coordination have been established through the India-Nepal Joint Committee on Water Resources (JCWR), Joint Committee on Koshi and Gandak Projects (JCKGP) and Joint Standing Technical Committee (JSTC). These structures allow for joint decision-making, which is easier after things like the 2008 embankment breach.
- 2) **Early Warning Systems Importance:** Timely, localized flood alerts empower communities to act, and systems like ICIMOD's HKH-HYCOS and the Community-Based Flood Early Warning System (CBFEWS) are proof of concept. The 2007 example of the Ratu River illustrates how upstream-downstream coordination and technology allow disaster impacts to be managed even with little lead time.

3) Integrated, Adaptive Management: The DPSIR adopted by ICIMOD reinforces the changing nature of information for sustainable decision-making from purely scientific, ecological and socio-economically driven insights. Climate projections (e.g., increasing temperatures, non-uniform precipitation) along with models such as SWAT indicate that water management needs to take spatial-temporal variability and future extremes into consideration.

Mekong River Basin (MRB)

Background

The Mekong River, stretching over 4800 kilometers, originate in southeastern China (Tanggula mountain range in China's Qinghai province). The Mekong River flows through Tibet's Autonomous Region and Yunnan province before marking the border between Myanmar and Laos, as well as Laos and Thailand. It then continues its course through Cambodia, re-enters Vietnam, and empties into the South China Sea (Figure 21). Spanning over 1000 km as a border boundary, the Mekong is one of the most international rivers in the world. The river is a vital ecological and hydrological lifeline for Southeast Asia that supports the livelihoods of more than 70 million people, providing essential resources for agriculture, fishing, and transportation (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020; Haefner, 2016). It has one of the most abundant freshwater fisheries globally (Geneva Water Hub, 2017). The river supplies almost the entire water supply for Laos and Cambodia. It also offers essential agricultural support to northeastern Thailand and Vietnam's key rice-producing region (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). Furthermore, Mekong River waters sustain rich biodiversity, including endangered species such as the Irrawaddy dolphin and the giant Mekong catfish, and it is home to some of the highest diversity of fish and snails globally. The river's seasonal flow patterns are particularly crucial for agriculture, especially in Cambodia and Vietnam, where the flood pulse system plays a vital role in rice cultivation and fish spawning (Haefner, 2016). This combination of economic, cultural, and ecological importance underscores the Mekong River's status as one of the world's most critical river systems (MacQuarrie et al., 2008). The Mekong River is known for its unique hydrological features, particularly its seasonal and widespread floods. From July to October, during the wet season, monsoon rains lead to high water levels and extensive flooding, primarily affecting Cambodia and Vietnam. However, these floods play a vital role in supporting freshwater fisheries, enhancing soil fertility through sediment deposits, and storing water for use during dry periods. While the economic damage caused by floods in the Lower Mekong Basin is estimated at \$60–\$70 million, the potential benefits, if properly utilized, are valued at around \$8–\$10 billion (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Figure 21: The Mekong River Basin (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Problems and Motivations

The Mekong River faces a variety of challenges and disputes among its riparian countries, driven by competing interests in water resource management, dam construction, and regional development. Managing the Mekong River has also been complicated by the region's historical context of conflict, most notably during the Vietnam War. **The Nam Ngum project**, which began **in the 1970s**, was an early example of the region's pivot toward hydropower. However, concerns about the river's ecological health and the effects on communities that rely on the resources of the river persist (MacQuarrie et al., 2008). Countries like Laos, Cambodia, Vietnam, and China have prioritized these at the cost of heightened tensions over shared water supplies and ecological sustainability.

The building of dams - especially in Laos and China - is one of the biggest threats to Mekong River management. Laos, which began building **the Xayaburi Dam in 2012**, has alarmed downstream countries, particularly Cambodia and Vietnam, about the dam's potential to alter patterns of water flow, fish migration, and the lives of millions of people who depend on the river for farming and fishing. Likewise, **the Lower Sesan II Dam in Cambodia poses a threat** to the area's environmental equilibrium, while compounding conflict between the sides in the **Mekong River Commission's (MRC)** mechanism (Haefner, 2016). These dams show the incompatibility between national priorities and the region's shared environmental needs. Laos has been a touchstone in the discussion over dam development. China's development of **the Lancang Cascade of dams**, which began in the early 2000s, has also fuelled tensions.

The collapse of Laos' Saddle Dam in 2018, which caused significant fatalities and displaced thousands, highlighted the risks associated with rapid dam construction and inadequate infrastructure oversight (Biba, 2018). These dams have altered the natural flow regime of the river, raising concerns about their detrimental effects on fisheries and local communities downstream, particularly in Vietnam and Cambodia (Mekong River Commission, 2006). **Vietnam's severe drought in 2016**, the worst in nine decades, was partly blamed by experts on China's reservoir dams, which have raised evaporation rates upstream. Eleven power plants are proposed for the Mekong mainstream, with over 80 more planned along its tributaries and related infrastructure. These **hydro-energy projects** could harm salinity levels, disrupt fish migration patterns, and reduce nutrients essential for agricultural productivity (DHI Group, 2015). **Pollution** is becoming an increasing threat, as contamination from heavy metals and the effects of a surge in sand-mining activities raise concerns about the quality and availability of water in the Lower Mekong region (Thilakarathne and Sridhar, 2017).

Despite ongoing negotiations between China and the **Mekong River Commission (MRC)**, **China has been reluctant to fully cooperate**, especially in sharing critical hydrological data beyond the wet season. This **lack of transparency** has hindered regional planning and effective environmental management (Zawahri & Hensengerth, 2012). In addition to the challenges posed by China's actions, its absence from the MRC and its influence through financing dam projects in the Lower Mekong countries have raised concerns about geopolitical leverage and debt dependency. Countries like Laos have increasingly relied on Chinese loans to fund dam projects, deepening their economic dependence on China (Songwanich, 2018). This has **exacerbated tensions**, as downstream nations feel marginalized in decisions that directly impact their water resources (Ho, 2014).

Cooperation Methods

The Mekong River has been a focal point of transboundary water management efforts for decades. Over time, various treaties, agreements, and cooperation mechanisms have emerged to address water resource

management, economic development, and conflict resolution in the region. Regional cooperation began **in the early 1950s** with the establishment of the **UN's Economic Commission for Asia and the Far East (ECAFE)**, which included a bureau focused on flood control. **In 1957**, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, and Thailand **adopted a statute to promote, coordinate, supervise and control** the planning of water projects that led to the creation of the **Mekong Committee (MC)**. The establishment of **the Mekong Committee** made the Mekong one of the earliest basins in the world to come under institutionalised governance (Zawahri, & Hensengerth, 2012; The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). The committee served as a platform for riparian states to manage shared resources that facilitated data exchange and resource management among Cambodia, Laos, Thailand, and Vietnam during a politically volatile period, particularly during the Vietnam War (MacQuarrie et al., 2008). Despite increasing functional authority, such as a **1975 joint declaration** allowing the Mekong Committee (MC) to establish project agencies, the initiative was undermined by political turmoil in Indochina (MacQuarrie et al., 2008).

The legacy of conflict has contributed to distrust, hindering effective collaboration on water management. Cambodia withdrew in 1977 as the Khmer Rouge pursued an isolationist agenda, and rising regional tensions led to Vietnam's invasion of the country in 1979. **The Cold War** further deepened divisions, with anti-Communist Thailand aligning with the US, while pro-Communist Vietnam and Laos sided with the Soviet Union. **Despite these challenges, the Mekong Committee (MC) persisted in its activities**, though on a smaller scale, throughout the conflict (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

The end of the Cold War led to new cooperation, while transforming economic dynamics demanded new ideas, in the 1990s. **The Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS) was established in 1992**, leading an era of regional collaboration focusing on economic cooperation and infrastructure development for the riparian countries. This included an effort to mitigate conflict through strengthened joint development projects and more efficient management of water resources (MacQuarrie et al., 2008). The GMS established a stronger foundation for a more integrated approach to tackle transboundary issues in the Mekong Basin. The resulting three years of negotiations produced the **1995 Mekong Agreement** with **the Mekong River Commission (MRC)** being established as an intergovernmental RBO (River Basin Organization). However, the two upstream countries, China and Myanmar did not become full members and are designated as “dialogue partners” since 1996 (The World Bank, 1999). The agreement introduced principles for equitable and sustainable water resource utilization (Schmeier et al., 2023). The MRC was created to promote discourse and collaboration between the riparian states and provide a formal mechanism for consultation and cooperation. As a “constitution for cooperation”, the MRC addresses technical responsibilities, decision making procedures to implement the Mekong Agreement, and undertaking scientific work, notably river health monitoring. The MRC tracks water levels and quality, as well as flood forecasts. Without supranational legal regulatory competence, its role is rather that of a coordinating organ for the national interests of the four

lower-basin countries. Despite these challenges, the **MRC has emerged as a model for water cooperation** (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). The Mekong River Commission (MRC) has established a **Basket Fund** to support the implementation of its Strategic Plan for 2021-2025. This fund is a multi-donor initiative aimed at promoting integrated water resources management and addressing transboundary issues in the Mekong River Basin¹. The fund supports various projects and activities that contribute to the sustainable development of the region, including water diplomacy, environmental protection, and socio-economic development (SDC, 2024).

In 2006, the MRC established the **Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement** (PNPCA). These procedures require the member states to notify and consult one another about projects that may affect the river, such as dam construction. The MRC advocates for Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM), by attempting to reconcile profit-generating ventures with preserving nature and being equitable toward people. The MRC additionally assists sharing information between countries, plan and implement joint projects, including large dam and watering systems. This explicit collective action framework helps to provide for discussions and potential mitigation of any potential transboundary impacts (Schmeier et al., 2023). **In 2010**, the MRC adopted its **Strategic Plan 2010–2015**, which is building basin wide cooperation. Also, **the 2018 MRC Council** studying presented unique insight on the long-term sustainability of the Mekong River according to future developments (Schmeier et al., 2023).

Despite regional cooperation, the unilateral development of dams by China on the Lancang River (the upper Mekong) has strained relationships with downstream countries. In response, China initiated **the Lancang-Mekong Cooperation (LMC)** mechanism in **2016** to enhance collaboration in water resources, economic development, and environmental sustainability. This initiative **marked a shift in China's approach, as it encouraged joint working groups and information sharing** among the Mekong countries (Biba, 2018). The framework is a development and investment initiative developed by China and involving Laos, Cambodia, Thailand, Myanmar and Vietnam. It is a far broader framework than the MRC, focusing on everything from infrastructure and finance, to land, agriculture, forestry and poverty alleviation (Xinhua News Agency, 2016). **The 2018 Joint Statement of the 2nd LMC Leaders' Meeting** reaffirmed the commitment to regional cooperation on water management and disaster response (China Report ASEAN, 2019). Despite these issues, the **Mekong River Commission** continues to play a pivotal role in promoting stability, reducing tensions, and facilitating collaborative management among its member countries (MRC, 2021). One key divergence between the two MRC and LMC is that the Framework is an Asian led initiative, whereas the MRC has, since its inception, relied significantly on foreign donor support (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

Despite disputes among the Mekong riparians, there have been instances of regional cooperation tied to water resource management. For example, **Thailand has purchased hydroelectricity from Laos**, fostering mutual dependency and increasing regional stability (Sadoff & Grey, 2002). This **economic interdependence** extends

beyond the river basin, encompassing broader systems such as labour flows, markets, and infrastructure. By fostering cooperation in these areas, the riparian countries have developed ties that help mitigate tensions arising from river system conflicts. This broader economic integration has the potential to strengthen individual economies, making them more competitive in the global market.

Lessons learned

1. **Inclusive Dialogue:** The establishment of the **Mekong River Commission (MRC)** in 1995 highlights the importance of collaborative decision-making among all riparian countries.
2. **Adaptive Management Strategies: The Lancang-Mekong Cooperation (LMC) framework,** initiated in 2016, emphasizes the need for flexible approaches to address dynamic environmental and socio-economic conditions affecting the river basin.
3. **Integration of Scientific Research and Data Sharing:** Joint studies conducted by the MRC and LMC to assess hydrological impacts demonstrate the necessity of informed policymaking through scientific collaboration.
4. **Trust and Mutual Understanding:** The efforts of lower Mekong countries to balance China's influence by engaging with other regional powers illustrate the importance of fostering trust and cooperation in water management diplomacy.
5. **Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM):** The MRC applies IWRM principles to balance economic growth with environmental protection. This approach plays a key role in a river basin with many different needs.
6. The Mekong performs relatively well on **basin-level financing**, as the MRC's "**Basket Fund**" represents one of the few examples of alternative funding instruments that have been successfully implemented.
7. The **absence of an RBO** that includes all riparian states is a major challenge for the Mekong Basin. The lack of a single platform for coordination holds back cooperation.
8. The **Mekong Agreement** covers only the mainstream and does not cover the entire basin with its tributaries. Additionally, the MRC agreements currently contain no clear dispute-resolution mechanism, limiting opportunities for the organisation to oversee and manage any disagreements that arise between the riparian states.

Saralbhanga River Basin (SRB)

Background

The Saralbhanga River (Figure 22) is a small river originating from Bhutan before entering India particularly passing through the Bodoland Territorial Area Districts (BTAD) in Assam (India) (Figure 23). Traditionally the source of the river is at the Servarayan in Tamil Nadu. The Sarbhanga River is formed by the meeting of the Keezhaaru and Melaaru tributaries at Omalur (India). It may not be the longest of rivers near this area, but it plays a huge role in the health of the ecosystem and the community that thrives on its banks. The river is a vital source of livelihood for the local population in the surrounding areas as it used for agricultural purposes (Bisht, 2019).

Figure 22: The Saralbhanga River Basin (Bandyopadhyay & Ghosh, 2016).

Figure 23: Bodoland Territorial Area Districts (SPMIAS, 2024).

Problems & Motivation

In geographical terms, the river flows through a **politically sensitive region** that has witnessed conflict and political autonomy, specifically for the Bodo ethnic group (Sharma, 2016). This context has **created a climate of distrust and friction** between neighboring border communities, making it difficult to cooperate on joint development of shared water resources. The Saralbhanga River thus became the **epicenter of complex disputes and problems between Bhutan and India** with local settlements of Assam bearing the brunt of the consequences (Bisht 2019). Downstream, **prolonged droughts, low flows** in the rivers and recurrent **flash flood** events in the Assam region are a result of upstream activities and increasingly erratic monsoon rain and climate variability in Bhutan (Bisht, 2019; Dutta & Yashwant, 2021). In addition, it may create problems of **siltation and agricultural land destruction** downstream, which are some of the common environmental and socio-economic problems faced by the local communities (Yashwant, 2018). There have seen frequent flash floods, especially **in the year 2004 and 2016**, which have led to considerable damage to infrastructure as well as agricultural land in the state of Assam. In 2004, local narratives linked the flash floods to **the breach of the Kurichu dam in Bhutan** and alleged that the sudden release of water without notice worsened the flood situation in Assam.

In 2016, two flash floods caused economic losses to the Sarpang district of Bhutan and Assam and this clearly indicates the interlinkage of water-induced disasters across the Indo-Bhutan border (Bisht, 2019). As a result, local communities often attributed these disasters to upstream activities in Bhutan, exacerbating agent provocateurs and complicating discussions around water management and cooperation.

The situation **worsened in 2017** when Bhutanese authorities **blocked the construction of a traditional nine-foot-high indigenous check dam by farmers in Kokrajhar district**. The dam, locally known as **Jamfwi/Dongo**, is essential for irrigation, enabling farmers to divert water from the river to irrigate their fields. Local farmers opposed the decision to stop constructing this dam because agriculture is their main activity and the dam was necessary to keep their rates of harvest (Yashwant, 2018). **In 2018, Bhutan's government diverted the Saralbhanga River**, which triggered concerns among local farmers in Assam, who anticipated that these upstream activities would exacerbate river siltation and cause further degradation of agricultural terrain downstream. The diversion would interrupt their irrigation practices, as it is crucial to their crops and livelihood (Bisht, 2019).

Cooperation Methods

One of the key initiatives is the cooperation surrounding the Saralbhanga River in Bhutan's southern plains which aims to foster collaboration between Bhutan and India for effective management of transboundary water bodies. **A key agreement was born in 2017**, when farmers in Assam sought cooperation in the face of the impacts of **Bhutan's decision to divert the river**. In response to these issues, Oxfam organized a meeting with the **Bhutan-India Friendship Association (BIFA)** to discuss fulfilment of the farmers' irrigation demands (Yashwant, 2018), with the support of the **Northeast Research and Social Work Networking (NRSWN)**, the **All Bodo Students Union (ABSU)** and the **Bodo Women's Forum for Peace and Development (BWFPD)**. The collaboration bore fruit in a major way when the Bhutanese authorities allowed Assam farmers to construct traditional check dams and irrigation systems called **Jamfwi/Dongo**. This traditional practice has significant importance to divert the water for farming, and consequently, improve the local means of livelihood (Yashwant, 2018).

Additionally, **the Saralpara initiative for sharing transboundary rivers supported by Oxfam** which is an example of a successful local cooperation model and one that demonstrates the need for **involving the local community** in resource management. Respected for its ability to provide stronger bonds among community members and generate livelihoods for people in the frontier areas. In fact, identified as the **Shramdan** its activity engaged more than 500 participants from 36 villages in June 2019, so local communities were involved in managing their water resources (Preetam, 2019).

Lessons learned

1. **Community Engagement is Crucial:** Local communities should be involved in water management decisions. Local farmers and community groups including **the All Bodo Students Union and Bodo Women's Forum for Peace and Development** have been instrumental in advocating for their rights and needs, as exemplified by the case of the Saralbhanga river.

2. **Importance of Informal Networks:** Informal networks and local NGOs have an important role to play in facilitating dialogue and cooperation across borders between communities. **The Bhutan India Friendship Association (BIFA)** mediated by sympathizing with the local concerns of farmers and cooperating between the Indian and Bhutanese farmers.
3. **Addressing Immediate Livelihood Concerns:** Water diplomacy must focus on addressing the immediate concerns of local livelihoods to gain traction and build support from local people. Collaboration for the Saralbhanga river was mostly **focused on the immediate needs of irrigation** and the long-term need for agricultural sustainability, demonstrating the importance of pursuing cooperation around local needs
4. **Adaptability to Local Contexts:** Border regions require water management approaches that are sensitive to the unique geographical and socio-political contexts. The Saralbhanga River illustrates how local contexts, such as the nature of historical conflict in the Bodoland Territorial Area Districts, shape cooperative initiatives and the factors influencing their success
5. **Sustaining Initiatives through Institutional Support:** While local initiatives can be effective, **there is a need for long-term institutional support to sustain these efforts.** The informal cooperation observed in the Saralbhanga case should be institutionalized to ensure ongoing collaboration and resource management.

5.2.3 Europe

Examples from Europe are represented by three river basins and the Baltic Sea:

The Baltic Sea
The Danube River Basin
The Iberian Region
The Rhine River Basin

The Baltic Sea

Background

The Baltic Sea (Figure 24) is bordered by nine states. Its southern border is Russia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Germany, and Denmark, while its northern border is with the Scandinavian Peninsula (Finland and Sweden) (Szymczycha et. al., 2019). The Baltic Sea covers an area of approximately 370,000 km² and has a volume of around 21,000 km³ (Fitzmaurice-Lacks, 2002), with a 1,729,000 km² overall drainage area, and a mean yearly river discharge about 440 km³ (Leppäranta & Myrberg, 2009). Its width exceeds 1500 km, and its latitudinal extension is around 650 km (Szymczycha et. al., 2019).

Figure 24: The Baltic Sea (Szymczycha et. al., 2019).

Recognized as the largest brackish water body in the world, the Baltic Sea receives fresh water from numerous rivers, with an annual input estimated at 450 km³. The Baltic Sea exhibits unique geographical and hydrographical features, particularly characterized by restricted water exchange due to the narrow contact with the North Sea and the presence of sills between its basins. Additionally, there are varying conditions across different sections of the sea, significant temperature fluctuations between winter and summer, and considerable differences in salinity levels (Fitzmaurice-Lacks, 2002).

Problems and Motivations

After World War II, there was a significant expansion of urban areas in the Baltic Sea states. During the eighties, the populations of coastal cities such as Helsinki, St. Petersburg, Tallinn, Riga, Stockholm, and Gdansk, along with their suburbs, grew manifold. As a result, the **pollution levels and environmental issues**, including the contamination of groundwater, surface water, and coastal waters, became increasingly apparent (Lääne, 2001). In **the mid-1960s, the rising pollution levels** in the Baltic Sea and its coastal waters, stemming from various sources like river discharges, estuaries, outfalls, and pipelines, emerged as a significant issue for all the Baltic Sea states (Lääne, 2001). **Eutrophication** emerged as a significant issue in the 1970s due to excessive nutrient inputs from agriculture and wastewater, leading to harmful algal blooms and oxygen depletion (HELCOM, 2024).

The problem of **hazardous substances**, including heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants, became evident in the 1980s as they accumulated in sediments and the marine food web, causing long-term **damage to biodiversity**. Moreover, the intense **overfishing destabilized the marine ecosystems** and depleted fish stocks. In the 1990s, **the introduction of non-indigenous species** disrupted the ecological balance, particularly as global trade and shipping increased (HELCOM, 2024). **Climate change impacts**, such as warming waters and rising sea levels, have exacerbated these issues since the early 2000s, affecting species distribution and habitats. Additionally, **increased human activities**, such as resource extraction and maritime transport, have led to higher pollution and physical disturbances, further threatening the fragile marine environment (HELCOM, 2024). While significant public concern is overshadowed by land-based pollution, which accounts for approximately 80% of marine pollutants, shipping contributes notably to the pollution in the Baltic Sea (Jenisch, 2002). **The Baltic Sea Region ranks among the world's most active transport hubs**, accounting for 7.5% of global maritime trade, equivalent to 340 million tons per year (Jenisch, 2002). The **Helsinki Convention** aims to protect the Baltic Sea by prohibiting the discharge of oil, harmful substances, sewage, and garbage from ships (Jenisch, 2002). Despite the implementation of waste reception facilities in ports, illegal oil discharges from ships remain a serious issue, with 500-700 cases reported annually (Jenisch, 2002).

Cooperation Methods

Following extensive preparatory efforts, the **Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea**—also known as **the Helsinki Convention**—was signed in **1974**, by the seven Baltic Sea states (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, and Poland), and **came into effect in 1980**, and over time, the membership expanded to include Russia and Sweden (Lääne, 2001). The Helsinki Convention's principal goals are to safeguard the Baltic Sea from all forms of air, sea, and land pollution, maintain biological variety, and encourage the sustainable use of marine resources (Goba et al., 2023).

A regional platform for environmental policymaking, **the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM)**, also known as **the Baltic Marine Ecosystem Protection Commission**, was founded in **1974** with the goal of shielding the Baltic Sea's marine ecosystem from all pollution sources. (HELCOM, 2024).

HELCOM has played a critical role in the development and implementation of novel water-protection technology (Lääne, 2001). The commission members have been working actively to provide recommendations as required by the aims of the convention. These actors have the responsibility for collecting, processing, summarizing and disseminating the available relevant scientific, technological, and statistical information, as well as supporting scientific and technological research (Lääne, 2001). Since 1979, HELCOM has been comprehensively collecting information from the marine environment using the **Baltic Monitoring Programme (BMP)** which has enabled regular updated evaluations about the condition of the Baltic Sea environment. This undertaking is done with the participation of the specialists from all Baltic States and with the specialists from the **International Council for the Exploration of the Seas (ICES)** (Fitzmaurice-Lacks, 2002). **In 1983, HELCOM prepared a guidebook** to enhance collaboration on marine pollution response to foster collaboration between the Baltic Sea states (HELCOM, 2024). The first periodic assessment of the marine environment covering the years 1980–1985 was completed in 1987, establishing a benchmark for future assessments. **In 1988, the Helsinki Ministerial Meeting** adopted a declaration that called for a 50% reduction in nutrients and hazardous substances by 1995 (HELCOM, 2024). **The Convention's text was revised and signed in 1992** by the commission members to place a stronger focus on implementing technological solutions and adopting **Best Available Technology (BAT)** and **Best Environmental Practice (BEP)** (Lääne, 2001).

Sweden and Poland took the lead by organizing the **Ronneby Conference** (Ronneby, Sweden) in **1990**. At this conference, the Prime Ministers of the Baltic Sea States endorsed the "**Baltic Sea Declaration**," marking a significant milestone in enhancing environmental cooperation in the region (HELCOM, 2024). The declaration highlighted the necessity for the ecological restoration of the Baltic Sea and called for the immediate development of the **Baltic Sea Joint Comprehensive Environmental Action Programme (JCP)** to tackle emissions reduction (Kremser, 2002). In 1992, during a Diplomatic Conference in Helsinki, Finland, the Environment Ministers from the participating countries endorsed the objectives and principles of the Joint

Comprehensive Programme (JCP). To support its implementation, **the Programme Implementation Task Force (PITF) was established** (Kremser, 2002). This task force was responsible for initiating, facilitating, and monitoring the coordination of activities related to the JCP, as well as periodically updating the program to ensure its effectiveness (Kremser, 2002). **In 1993**, HELCOM organized a **ministerial meeting in Gdańsk (Poland)**, to mobilize resources for environmental action and initiated workshops to implement the **Helsinki Convention** in post-Soviet states (HELCOM, 2024). In 1994, the Helsinki Ministerial Meeting recommended the establishment of **marine protected areas (BSPAs or HELCOM MPAs)**, further strengthening conservation measures (HELCOM, 2024). **The revised Helsinki Convention entered into force in 2000**, alongside a 10-year review of the Joint Comprehensive Programme. In 2001, the **Copenhagen Declaration** was adopted, focusing on safety and emergency response in the Baltic region and the **2003 Bremen Declaration** emphasized the ecosystem approach to managing the Baltic Sea environment. In 2006, the Baltic Sea was recognized as a **Particularly Sensitive Sea Area (PSSA) and a Sulphur Oxide Emission Control Area (SECA)** under the IMO. The HELCOM nutrient input reduction scheme, introduced **in 2007**, addressed eutrophication, a major issue in the Baltic Sea. In 2010, HELCOM initiated marine spatial planning cooperation with VASAB and became the first region globally to achieve 10% marine spatial protection (HELCOM, 2024).

To highlight its global vulnerability, the Baltic Sea was awarded a **Special Area Label by the International Maritime Organization in 2013**. In 2017, the second detailed assessment of the **Baltic Sea ecosystem health, or (HOLAS II)**, was issued and was followed by the **Brussels Declaration in 2018**. In 2019, the Baltic Sea was **classified as a Nitrogen Oxide Emission Control Area** in an attempt to discharge air pollution. Recent milestones include the adoption of the **Regional Action Plan on Underwater Noise in 2021** and the commissioning of HOLAS III in 2023. The year 2024 marked the 50th anniversary of HELCOM, which commenced with the adoption of the **Riga Declaration** as part of its commitment to protecting the Baltic Sea for future generations.

Lessons Learned

1. **Significance of Regional Cooperation:** The collaborative management of shared water bodies calls for the interaction of bordering states. **The Helsinki Commission (HELCOM)** can be cited as an example of regional cooperation towards a common environmental goal.
2. **Scientific Research Integration:** To inform decision-making processes, scientific evidence, and research data are the key. The policies regarding the sea have been formulated and implemented with constant monitoring and assessment of the ecological state of the Baltic Sea.

3. **Holding onto the Best Practices:** The implementation of **Best Available Technology (BAT) and Best Environmental Practice (BEP)** has proven to be instrumental in pollution control and water quality improvement. The adoption of effective practices in the different states enhances overall performance.
4. **Adoption to Change:** Adjusting to new environmental developments and challenges is very important. The states of the Baltic Sea have **revised treaties and policies** based on newly available scientific information and changes in socio-economic conditions.
5. **Long-term Commitment:** In order to achieve the set goals, everybody who is relevant to the situation must display devotion and continuous action. Additional **political will and funding** to protect the environment are necessary to create real changes in the Baltic Sea's health.
6. **Holistic Approach:** Addressing water management issues requires a holistic perspective that considers land-based activities, marine ecosystems, and socio-economic factors. Integrated management strategies that encompass all aspects of the marine environment are more effective.

The Danube River Basin (DRB)

Background

The Danube River (DR) is the second-largest river in Europe, connecting 19 nations and serving as a migration and trade corridor. The Danube River (Figure 25) spans 2,857 km from its source in the **Black Forest Mountain** range in Germany to its mouth in the Black Sea in Romania and Ukraine, with an average discharge of 6,486 m³/s (Sommerwerk et al., 2022). It drains a basin area of 817,000 km² (10% of continental Europe) and flows through several major cities, including four national capitals: Venna, Bratislava, Budapest, and Belgrade. The river's natural flow changes with the seasons and differs across the basin, influenced by variations in rainfall.

Precipitation ranges from less than 500 mm per year in the central and eastern parts of the basin to over 3,000 mm annually in the western areas. Mountains cover one-third of the basin, and the average elevation of the basin is around 450 meters above sea level (Habersack et al., 2016). The Danube River Basin (DRB) is split into three sub-regions: the Upper, Middle, and Lower Basins, along with the Danube Delta. The Upper Basin stretches from the Danube's origin in Germany to Bratislava in Slovakia. The Middle Basin, which is the largest, runs from Bratislava to the dams at the Iron Gate Gorge. The Lower Basin encompasses the lowlands, plateaus, and mountains of Romania and Bulgaria (Paunovic et al., 2007).

Figure 25: The Danube River Basin (Michaud et al., 2015).

The basin is inhabited by 83 million people, who come from diverse cultural, linguistic, and historical backgrounds. The area is also rich in significant natural habitats, such as wetlands and floodplain forests (Meehan, 2019). Although being a significant source for hydropower generation, navigation, agriculture, recreation, and water supply, only 24.7% of the water bodies are classified as having high ecological quality (ICPDR, 2018). Nevertheless, around 20 million individuals rely on the river as a source of drinking water (Koev & Popova, 2022).

Problems and Motivations

The Danube River has long been a stressed and vulnerable system, yet it continues to hold significant biological potential despite extensive socioeconomic exploitation over time (Hein et al., 2019). After World War II, the political and economic stabilization of the region brought to light issues such as **increased flooding and the deterioration of navigation**, which were exacerbated by earlier regulation works on the river (Jansky et al., 2004). After the Danube River had changed drastically from 1950 to 1980, the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) in 1994 reported that 69 large dams, with a total water volume exceeding 7,300 million m³, had been constructed along the river. The volume of goods carried and handled on the river increased more than tenfold during this post-war period. The opening of the Rhine–Main–Danube

waterway in 1992 transformed the Danube into a crucial continental route, linking numerous inland ports stretching from the North Sea to the Black Sea. This development greatly enhanced the river's role in navigation and increased its importance as a major transportation route (Jansky et al., 2004). Reclamation of the Danube's water resources brought about drastic modifications in the hydro-morphology and water quality of this river. Due to the operation of the reservoirs, the Danube River as reported by the International Water Assessment Center in 2002, experienced an unprecedented drop in the riverbed. This was because of increased erosion resulting from diminished transport of suspended sediment. Sediment build-up decreased, causing the river to move faster. The changes also altered flood patterns, shortening the length of flooding but making it more frequent and extreme. In the past, major floods event would happen much less frequently, once or twice a century, reflected in years such as 1445, 1501, 1721, 1787, 1876 and 1884. Yet the 20th century was marked by a steep increase in their frequency, along with the more widespread regulation of rivers along the Danube. Historic records show that there have been notable flood events in 1929, 1947, 1954, 1963 and 1965 (Jansky et al., 2004) which points to this trend.

The 1954 and 1965 events were catastrophic. In 1954, floodwaters broke dikes at four points in Hungary's Szigetkoz region, inundating nearly 33,000 hectares of land, in part or entirely. Some 65,000 people were evacuated from flooded areas after the disaster in 1965. The socio-economic and political context of the time in the region deeply affected the response towards these environmental issues (Jansky et al., 2004). Following the collapse of the Soviet Union, conditions started to worsen as the Black Sea ecosystem steadily declined due to rising levels of nutrient and organic pollution. This deterioration reached its worst point in 1990, when around 40,000 km² of the Black Sea was classified as "dead" (ICPDR, 2018). Furthermore, human activities have significantly harmed the Danube River and its tributary systems. While industries, agriculture, and tourism play a vital economic role, they rely heavily on the Danube as a valuable resource. However, these activities also endanger the river and its position as one of the world's most important biodiversity hotspots (Finlayson et al., 2018). In recent years, the Danube River Basin has been overwhelmed by a series of crises and disasters that have captured global interest including the Baia Mare cyanide spill in 2000. More recently, in 2010, the Ajka red sludge disaster occurred after a dam at a Hungarian aluminum facility collapsed, releasing approximately 700,000 cubic meters of hazardous red sludge. The incident resulted in the deaths of ten individuals and caused severe damage across an area of around 1,100 hectares (Haefner, 2016). Additionally, an increasing frequency of large flood events in the Danube River Basin has created considerable concern about the role of climate change in driving higher flood risk. For example, the economic damages caused by the floods in June 2013 reached amounts of €2.4 billion (ICPDR, 2018). This was necessary to protect the Danube and its ecosystems from similar disasters on the river; clear policies were needed to be finalized and enforced.

Methods of Cooperation

As far back as 1616, the Danube played a crucial role in peace negotiations, as an Austro-Turkish agreement signed in Belgrade allowed Austrians the freedom to navigate the middle and lower sections of the river (Shepherd, 2014). The **1856 Treaty of Paris** established the **European Commission of the Danube**, an international body tasked with managing the navigation and trade on the Danube River. This commission was a significant development in international cooperation and marked the first time an international body had been given such extensive powers over a major waterway. **The European Commission of the Danube**, which included Danube nations as well as significant shipping countries like Great Britain and France, ensured that all European states had the right to free trade and navigation on the Danube River (Shepherd, 2014). The experiment in cooperative management of the Danube River post-World War II has been a notable success story in international water governance. Following World War II, emerging East-West political blocs necessitated a revised strategy for managing the Danube. The 1948 Danube River Conference in Belgrade transferred authority over navigation from external powers to the sole jurisdiction of individual nations (Shepherd, 2014). Recognizing the increasing degradation of water quality, eight countries (Austria, Germany, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, Serbia, Romania, and Bulgaria) along the Danube River signed the Bucharest Declaration in 1985. Between 1985 and 1987, a joint monitoring initiative was created and adopted through the Bucharest Declaration. Thirteen monitoring stations were set up along shared border areas to gather samples based on specific, mutually accepted criteria and to document monthly flow rates (Murphy, 2013). This information has been shared once a year since 1988. However, the political divide between East and West during the Cold War split the Danube Basin into two parts, greatly limiting the sharing of information and cross-border data exchange. In 1998, the collapse of the Iron Curtain dramatically altered global geopolitical dynamics, leading to the reshaping of nations and borders throughout Europe (Shepherd, 2014).

In 1991, the countries created the **Environmental Program for the Danube River Basin (EPDRB)** to support national actions to protect the river basin (Shepherd, 2014). Under the program, countries agreed to adopt a shared environmental monitoring system, address liability for cross-border pollution, protect wetland habitats and conserve areas of ecological importance. **The Research and Engineering Institute for Environment**, which has overseen the Bucharest Declaration monitoring program from the beginning, recognizes the pressing need to expand monitoring initiatives across the basin. It is collaborating with the EPDRB to work toward these objectives (Murphy, 2013).

In 1994, the countries along the Danube River joined forces to sign the Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC). To achieve the goals outlined in the Convention, they established the International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River (ICPDR) in 1998 (ICPDR, 2019). The ICPDR consists of 15 contracting parties dedicated to implementing the DRPC and serves as a platform for coordinating and collaborating on key water management issues. The organization primarily includes national delegations that convene twice

annually. Headquartered in Vienna, the ICPDR is led by a president who holds the position for one year, with the presidency rotating among member countries in alphabetical order. A significant portion of the ICPDR's work is carried out by Expert Groups, which are composed of specialists from member countries and 21 official observers.

For assessing trends in water quality, the ICPDR supervises the TransNational Monitoring Network (TNMN), which was set up in 1995. The network closely examines physical, chemical and biological conditions in the Danube and its tributaries and gives an overview of the pollution levels as well as long term trends in water quality in the basin. The data is derived from national monitoring programs and 109 monitoring stations in the Danube and its tributaries as of 2017. This was followed by the establishment of the Accident Emergency Warning System (AEWS) in 1997 which led to the establishment of a rapid communication mechanism in case of pollution incident as well as rapid responses to environmental threats (ICPDR, 2019). A step forward was reached when **Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC)** came into force in 1998 and the ICPDR Secretariat was established in 1999, which allows countries to coordinate their policies and actions (ICPDR, 2019). This was followed by the Joint Danube Survey, which was launched in 2001, paving the way for further data collection and an improved data assessment process, allowing countries to implement measures to manage hazardous substances better. Another key milestone was the adoption of the Danube River Basin Management Plan (DRBMP) for the Danube River Basin in 2009 and its updates, which serve as a strategic framework for integrated management of the waters and specify concrete measures for improving water quality, protecting ecosystems and managing floods (ICPDR, 2019). The flood action plans for the 17 sub-basins in the Danube catchment area were adopted at the 2nd Ministerial Meeting in 2010. At its 2016 3rd ICPDR Ministerial Meeting, the ICPDR adopted its three pillars of “cleaner, healthier and safer waters for everyone to enjoy.” The introduction of the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) in 2000 and the EU Floods Directive in 2007 also laid a strong regulatory foundation upon which joint is built (ICPDR, 2019). WFD has been established to find new legal basis for water management. It provides the legal basis to safeguard and rejuvenate water bodies the length and breadth of Europe. It promotes water management in drainage basins, gives Member States specific deadlines to protect the aquatic ecosystem and guarantees the good ecological and chemical status of water bodies (Habersack et al. 2016).

Public participation programs include Danube Day, Danube Art Master, Danube Box, Danube Watch, Information events, public consultation, and social media, which were launched to engage local communities in conservation efforts, fostering a sense of shared responsibility (ICPDR, 2019). These measures have ensured that all involved countries work together to balance human needs with ecological preservation, making the Danube experiment a model of successful international cooperation in river management. With time, the ICPDR has reached many milestones on its path to achieving the targets for cleaner, healthier and safer waters.:

- Organic emissions have been cut to half the levels of 2005.
- Nutrient pollution from phosphorus has been cut by 30%.
- Nitrogen emissions have been cut by 10%.
- The Joint Danube Survey has closed most information gaps on hazardous substances.
- Over 120 fish migration aids have been built to restore continuity, and 50,000 ha of wetlands have been reconnected.
- New sewer systems have been built to ensure good chemical status of groundwater bodies.

Lessons Learned

1) **Findings from collaborative Danube studies** are incorporated into every phase of the Danube River Basin Management Plan cycle, assisting the nations along the Danube in determining appropriate actions to address basin-wide challenges.

2) **Coordinated River Basin Management:**

a) Managing shared transboundary water resources effectively requires Coordinated River Basin Management (CRBM), which relies on accurate data and collectively agreed-upon actions to tackle common issues.

b) Dialogue across sectors is essential for creating and carrying out river basin management strategies.

3) **Blending scientific expertise with inclusive stakeholder consultations** has allowed climate adaptation strategies to be embedded in the preparation of the upcoming Danube River Basin Management (DRBM) Plan and Danube Flood Risk Management (DFRM) Plan.

4) **Risk Mitigation:**

a) Executing the Danube Flood Risk Management Plan lowers flood hazards basin-wide and supplies strategies for efficient flood control, preparedness, and risk reduction.

b) Creating inventories of potential accident risks is a fundamental requirement for formulating and executing a robust accident prevention strategy in the Danube River Basin.

c) The Danube's emergency alert system for accidents ensures prompt initiation of protocols to minimize significant harm to communities and ecosystems from pollution events.

5) **Stakeholder Engagement:**

a) Greater engagement of stakeholders fosters a stronger sense of commitment among countries in the International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River (ICPDR).

b) Building and maintaining a structured process for communication and public involvement across the Danube Basin has boosted the ICPDR's ability to achieve its goals.

The Iberian Rivers

Background

The Iberian Peninsula, located in southwestern Europe, is characterized by its diverse river systems, which include five major global river basins (Figure 26): Minho, Lima, Douro, Tejo, and Guadiana (INAG, 2004). Approximately, 45% of Iberian water (surface and aquifers) is associated with these five basins, with Portugal contributing 32 % of the water and Spain 68 % (INAG, 2004). The Minho River originates in the Serra da Peneda in Portugal and flows into the Atlantic Ocean, forming part of the border between Spain and Portugal (Vlachos & Correia, 2000). The Douro River begins in the Sierra de Urbión in Spain and flows westward through Portugal before emptying into the Atlantic at Porto (Almeida et al., 2009). The estimated population of Spain is approximately 48 million, while Portugal has a population of around 10 million (World Bank, 2023). These populations heavily depend on transboundary rivers such as the Tagus and Douro for essential resources, including drinking water, agriculture, and hydropower generation. The communities living along these rivers face significant challenges related to water management, as increasing demands due to population growth and climate change lead to tensions over water rights and usage (Martínez-Alier, 2023).

Figure 26: The Rivers of the Iberian Peninsula (Benito & Machado, 2012).

Problems and motivation

Spanish Portuguese water relations were characterized by a **hydro-hegemonic framework**, where Spain, as the upstream country, exerted significant control over shared water resources, often leading to tensions and inequitable distribution of water (Lopes, 2012). **The treaties** established between Spain and Portugal in **1864**

and 1927 primarily focused on delineating political borders and hydroelectric potential, neglecting the critical issue of water quantity and equitable distribution, leading to Spain exerting considerable control over water flows (Cunha, 1996). This oversight has resulted in **tensions with Portugal**, particularly during periods of drought. For example, **the prolonged drought in the early 1990s** heightened conflicts over water allocation (Lopes, 2012). **In 1985, the Spanish Water Law** aimed to modernize water management frameworks but continued to **support the traditional hydraulic paradigm** that prioritized large hydraulic infrastructures, such as dams and reservoirs, often **at the expense of ecological sustainability and local community needs** (Agudo, 2009). The release of **Spain's National Hydrological Plan (NHP) in 1993** and the opposition to Portugal's Foz Côa dam **heightened tensions in Iberian water politics**, challenging Spain's dominant position in regional water management. **The Portuguese Alqueva Dam** impounds the Guadiana River and was completed in 2002 **raised concerns in Spain** about potential impacts on downstream water availability, leading to disputes over water rights and usage (Lopes, 2012). **The lack of clarity in the treaties** regarding the regularity and volume of transboundary flows led to ad-hoc responses to water shortages and surpluses, creating a reactive rather than proactive management approach (Cunha, 1996). Additionally, **Spain's unilateral decisions** regarding water releases from reservoirs often left **Portugal vulnerable**, particularly during critical agricultural periods, leading to accusations of inequitable water management (Swyngedouw, 1999). **In 2017**, these tensions culminated in **a formal complaint by Portugal to the European Commission** over Spain's plans to use the increasingly scarce water flow of the Tagus River for nuclear waste treatment, highlighting the transboundary implications of such decisions (Martínez-Alier, 2023). **Tension** between the two countries over the right to water usage is on the rise because of the **drought** motivated by climate change. For example, in 2022, Spain announced that it was unable to fully honor the quotas agreed upon for the Douro and Tagus rivers when Spanish reservoirs reached a new minimum that year. **A joint complaint** to the European Commission, submitted to the European Commission by the **ProTejo collective**, and signed by over 27 Portuguese and Spanish organizations, denouncing the **non-compliance with the Water Framework Directive (WFD)** by Portugal and Spain to the European Commission for the non-implementation of ecological flows in the Cedillo dam (Lambuça, 2024). Overall, water scarcity and allocation problems are aggravated by the traditional focus of both countries on dam construction and large-scale water transfers from wetter to drier regions (in Spain). In other words, **the main policies negatively affecting river water management** in the Iberian Peninsula stemmed from this traditional hydraulic paradigm, which prioritized infrastructure over sustainability and equity (Sauri & Del Moral, 2001; Pato, 2013).

Cooperation Methods

Historically, relations between Spain and Portugal regarding water governance have been characterized by a **series of treaties dating back to 1864 (Treaty of Limits)**, with four other signed treaties, reflecting a framework of cooperation despite underlying tensions. The two countries have further **signed protocols and exchanged official notes** to explain or add specific themes to those treaties, in 1866, 1912, 1951, 1976, 1980 and 2008 (Lopes, 2012).

The dynamics of water interactions between Spain and Portugal were relatively stable until the 1990s with Spain maintaining a hegemonic role over Portugal (Lopes, 2012). Through that decade, however, Spain's supremacy was eroded by internal changes deployed by both nations, as well as their entry into the European Union (Lopes, 2012). **The 1990s also**, marked a turning point, as public contestation in both countries, particularly against projects like the **Foz Côa dam** at Guarda, Portugal, highlighted the need for a more integrated and participatory approach to water governance, ultimately leading to the development of **the Albufeira Convention in 1998** (Lopes, 2012). **COAGRET** (Coordinator of Those Affected by Large Dams and Water Transfers) was **created in 1995** as a non-governmental organization initiated by **Greenpeace Spain** and the environmental coalition **CODA (Coordinator of Environmental Defence Organizations)**. COAGRET served as a platform for uniting stakeholders, water specialists, and activists who opposed large hydraulic infrastructure projects, particularly those involving water transfers (Bukowski, 2016).

Signed in 1998, the **Albufeira Convention: the "Convention on Cooperation for the Protection and Sustainable Use of the Waters of the Spanish Portuguese Hydrographic Basins"**, **came into force on 17 January 2000**. It was a major step forward in the management of shared water resources between Spain and Portugal. The convention was intended to improve information sharing, joint planning, and impact assessments of projects affecting these shared water systems, indicating a gradual move to a more participatory process of water governance (Lopes, 2012). The governance of these shared water resources continued to evolve with the implementation of the European Union Water Framework Directive (WFD) from the year 2000 onwards, which encouraged bilateral cooperation between Spain and Portugal through the Albufeira Convention (Barreira, 2007; Bukowski, 2016). **The Albufeira Convention established two inter-related bodies** to provide the political and technical support needed to reach its objectives: **The Conference of the Parties** (political and diplomatic in nature); and the **Commission for the Implementation and Development of the Convention (CADC)**, which has a more technical and operational nature. In 2007, the CADC initialized the **public participation process** by creating a website for the involvement of people in sustainable river basin management (Council of the European Union, 2008). The platform has an extensive collection of information about shared basin management and facilitate information campaign and public debates on these issues (Council of the European Union, 2008). Nevertheless, according to Lambuça (2024), the Albufeira Convention is inadequate to address the current water scarcity and does not meet the Water

Framework Directive. **The Spanish organization FNCA (Fundación Nueva Cultura del Agua), established in 2002**, is a vital player in promoting collaboration among scientists, regulators and civil society to make science and research accessible to decision makers (and vice versa). The founders of FNCA were many academics who were very active in creating COAGRET (Bukowski, 2016). Through **conferences and workshops**, the foundation helps strengthen the scientific legitimacy of water management strategies, which then filters into national and regional policy. It is this collaboration that eventually leads to the sustainable management of shared water resources in the region (Bukowski, 2016). The intense media coverage on the severe drought that affected the center of Spain and the north-west of Portugal in 2004–2006 led to the preparation of the **Additional Protocol to the Albufeira Convention**, which was then signed in 2008 (Lambuça, 2024).

Lessons learned

- 1) Effective bilateral cooperation:** The **Albufeira Convention** is widely recognized as a significant example of effective bilateral cooperation.
- 2) The gradual shift from a hydro-hegemonic framework to a more equitable and participatory governance model** has allowed for improved management of shared river basins, reflecting a commitment to addressing both ecological sustainability and social justice.
- 3) The collaboration of the scientific community**, exemplified by the efforts of the **FNCA** has been instrumental in promoting a new water culture and influencing policy through credible research and advocacy.
- 4) The alignment of national policies with the European Union's Water Framework Directive (WFD)** has further strengthened these efforts by mandating transboundary cooperation and public participation in water management. The WFD has been pivotal in promoting sustainable water management practices and enhancing the quality of transboundary waters.

The Rhine River Basin (RRB)

Background

The Rhine River (Figure 27) rises in Switzerland's Alps and continues its meandering path over 1280 km eventually emptying its waters into the North Sea. The Rhine River basin (RRB) spans an impressive 185,000 km² and flows through nine countries: Germany, Switzerland, the Netherlands, France, Belgium, Luxembourg, Austria, Liechtenstein, and Italy (Schiff, 2017). Switzerland and France are the main upstream partners, Germany is in a middle position and the Netherlands is the downstream partner. About seventy million people live within the catchment area (Moellenkamp, 2007). The Rhine River represents a critical

lifeline within Europe, serving as a multifaceted resource that sustains hydropower generation, potable water supply, agricultural irrigation, and recreational activities for an estimated 50 million individuals across the region (ICPR, 2001).

Figure 27: The Rhine River and its key tributaries (Frings et al., 2019).

Problems and Motivations

In the post-World War II period, the industrial, municipal and agricultural sectors grew, and the demand for fresh water grew making the Rhine one of the most contentious river basins in the world with potential **conflict over water quality and quantity** between the riparian countries. Historically, the Rhine has served as a critical waterway for trade and cultural exchanges but has also confronted serious environmental threats due to pollution and habitat destruction from industrial operations and urbanization (Schiff, 2017). In the period leading up to the **Sandoz Spill**, on November 1, 1986, accidentally dumping over 20 tons of toxic chemicals into the Rhine River when a Sandoz warehouse in Basel was compromised, the river suffered through one of the deadliest environmental disasters in history (Schwabach, 1989). The damage done to the

ecological health of the Rhine included the near extinction of the Eel population, and thousands of homes in the downstream area needed to have their drinking water source replaced. By the mid-20th century, as Europe began to economically rebound after the devastation of World War II, the Rhine River had acquired the grim nickname of “**Europe’s most romantic sewer.**” That was because of the extreme pollution from industrial effluents and domestic releases into the river. The Netherlands, which lies downstream at the Rhine’s estuary into the North Sea, suffered most from this transboundary water pollution (Nollkaemper, 1996). In addition, the Rhine was an important trade and transport artery, and its **pollution was threatening vital economic activities** like shipping, fishing and tourism. This was another ground that propelled the states towards collaboration. **Public pressure**, advocacy from environmental organizations, and the emergence of a global political identity all contributed to a move away from national self-interest towards a focus on sustainability (Reichert, 2016). In reaction, the affected countries started to work together to restore and protect the Rhine and established **joint projects** to jointly manage and protect this vital river. These initiatives seek to ensure the sustainable utilization of the river resources in the context of environmental issues (Schulte-Wülwer-Leidig et al., 2018).

Methods of Cooperation

With respect to the Rhine, the development of **international water law** was mainly reactive, seeking to address specific disputes over the discharge of harmful substances through ad-hoc measures. This often resulted in higher pressure between the upstream countries and the downstream countries (Reichert, 2019). Due to the postwar Dutch suffering from cross-border water pollution, **the International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR)** was established in 1950. The successful collaboration among the Rhine riparian states within the ICPR offered valuable lessons that **helped shape the creation of new international water agreements** and the formation of river commissions in other European river basins (ICPR, 2024). The ICPR has evolved progressively and operates with no formal treaty or legal framework. Nevertheless, this constraint was removed **in 1963** by the signing of a treaty, hereafter called the **Bern Convention**, which functioned as the formal establishment of, and institutionalization of the ICPR (ICPR, 1963). Until the mid-1970s, ICPR's efforts produced limited success at addressing pollution problems caused by saline and chemical waste being discharged into the river (Lammers, 1984; Birnie et al., 2009). In a step further to improve cooperation, the countries forming the ICPR France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Switzerland and the European Economic Community (EEC) signed two agreements in 1976: **the Convention for the Protection of the Rhine Against Chloride Pollution (1976 Chlorides Convention)** and **the Convention for the Protection of the Rhine Against Chemical Pollution (1976 Chemical Convention)** (Reichert, 2019). A gradual improvement in the quality of the Rhine waters was the main goal of the Chloride Convention (Kiss, 1985). The ratification process was, however, much more complicated and

dragged on in large part because of environmental worries in France (De Villeneuve, 1996). Due to intensive diplomatic bargaining between the parties, the Convention was not put into effect until 1985, as ongoing disagreements persisted between the French and the Netherlands. The disagreement went to arbitration, which was finalized in 2004. It soon became evident that the 1976 Rhine Chemical Convention was “a regulatory failure” (Nollkaemper, 1996). The negotiation and ratification processes, governed by international law, proved excessively slow and complex, failing to adequately address ecological needs and advancements in technology (Reichert, 2005).

The **vagueness and absence of enforcement systems in the treaties** provoked frustration among many stakeholders, and both citizens and states raised demands for actions to be taken to combat Rhine pollution (Schiff, 2017). **The Sandoz Spill experience** created significant public outcry and widespread political backing across all riparian nations for the programs. This strong support helped offset the limited legal authority these programs initially had, such as the 1976 Rhine Chemical Convention (Wieriks, 1997) and the need for coordination. This prompted a massive public concern and political will for an integrative management approach that led to the **1987 Rhine Action Program**. This initiative is a breakthrough to prevent conflict rather than responding to it and subsequently focusing on returning the whole Rhine environment to a healthy state by year 2000 (ICPR, 2003). This program was an **integrative approach** to restore the river’s ecosystem, rather than solving isolated problems arising by the need for better management of common environmental problems. Furthermore, the program proved effective for measurable outcomes and inspired initiatives to recover other water bodies, such as **Salmon 2000** (Wieriks, 1997). By the turn of the century, the quality of the Rhine’s water had already markedly improved, accidental pollution incidents had dropped in frequency, and salmon populations had once again been reintroduced to the river. Nitrate contamination, primarily driven by agriculture runoff, remained an obstacle, but industrial and municipal discharges from harmful toxins into the river were dramatically reduced (Reichert, 2019).

The remarkable recovery of the Rhine’s biological health poses an interesting paradox. Unlike the Rhine Chemical and Chlorides Conventions which were established with legally binding obligations, **the Rhine Action Program, the Master Plan “Salmon 2000” and the Action Plan on Floods** that have followed were, to the contrary, set out as non-binding cooperation frameworks involving declarative commitments by riparian states. But these programs defined the overall objectives and principles, then left it up to the national authorities of the states that would participate to decide what to do with them in practice. Despite their non-binding status and generality, these **initiatives were more effective** in promoting ecosystem recovery **than their legally binding predecessors** (Reichert, 2019). This raises the critical question: **what factors contributed to their enhanced efficacy despite their lack of formal legal enforceability?**

First, The Sandoz spill served as a pivotal event, galvanizing public demand and fostering political commitment among the Rhine’s riparian states, thereby compensating for the programs’ non-binding legal

status (Wieriks, 1997). The new approach represented a significant shift, moving away from ad-hoc attempts to address narrowly defined conflicts between upstream and downstream riparian states over the discharge of specific pollutants. Instead, it prioritized a **holistic strategy** focused on the shared objective of restoring and protecting the Rhine's ecosystem as a whole (Reichert, 2019). **Second**, the shift in procedural strategy under the new objectives contrasted sharply with earlier frameworks. Where the 1976 Rhine Chemical Convention relied on rigid, legally binding emission limits tied to slow-moving international ratification processes, the Rhine Action Programme introduced **adaptable, time-specific goals** that could be refined through ongoing collaboration within the ICPR and tailored by individual riparian states. **Regular monitoring and reporting to the ICPR** allowed for transparent assessments of progress, identification of gaps, and rapid adjustments to meet targets. This dynamic, learning-oriented approach was driven by a network of over **150 experts who pooled technical knowledge and fostered innovation**. Over time, expertise deepened within governmental and economic sectors, **trust among state representatives solidified**, and **public backing** for coordinated ecological measures **strengthened** (Reichert, 2019).

A significant factor in pushing for sustainable and comprehensive management of water resources in cross-border settings has been the **1992 UNECE Water Convention**, formally titled the (Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes) (Reichert, 2016). Bernauer (2002) notes that the biggest strength behind **The UNECE Water Convention** is flexibility. It acts as a driving force for the advancement of international water law in Europe and globally. While it does not directly regulate individual water bodies, it offers a conceptual framework to guide the creation and enhancement of international collaboration on the management and protection of shared freshwater resources. In addition to the core objectives set as pillars for the cooperative governance of the Rhine Action Program, the principle of information sharing for **joint bodies** set forth in the UNECE Water Convention enabled an Action Program to enhance water quality and increase sustainable practices by citizens and countries (Bergesen et al., 2018). These collaborations have proven to have transformational effects for all countries that participate. **It is hoped that such collaborations can be adopted widely** to ensure the protection and improvement of the water resources worldwide.

The latest set of regimes governing the Rhine came into effect in 2000 when the European Union introduced another layer of obligation and compliance to the governing and monitoring of the river. The EU accomplished this evolutionary change in regime type through the adoption of the **Water Framework Directive (WFD)**; a comprehensive policy framework designed to offer legislative coherence with respect to the region's water management (European Parliament and Council, 2000). As a legislative framework, therefore, the WFD linked together the multitude of previously disparate mechanisms of European water governance into a single policy for implementation across all transboundary EU water bodies, i.e., including the Rhine (Schiff, 2017).

Lessons Learned

- 1) **Importance of Shared Historical Governance:** The Rhine River provides an important example of how shared historical legacies of water governance, compassions in long-term transformed political relationships, can greatly facilitate transboundary water cooperation. Shared histories enable states to identify common interests and avoidances and, therefore, facilitate the establishment of formal agreements that address water-related issues.
- 2) **Clear legal agreements:** The Rhine case suggests that while non-binding instruments, like the Rhine Action Program, can be successful, lasting **success in water management is often tied to formalized agreements** with binding commitments and accountability systems. This formalization ensures compliance and further promotes sustained cooperation among the riparian states.
- 3) **The Role of Institutional Support:** The European Union's Water Framework Directive and the Rhine 2020 plan illustrate how transboundary water governance can acquire legitimacy and support through institutional frameworks. Such institutions can hold states accountable and incentivize them to comply with environmental agreements, making the governance regimes more viable.
- 4) **Environmental disasters** can provide opportunities for proactive cooperation, as represented in the **Sandoz Spill**, to catalyse development of management strategies focused on common goals. This entails an integrated water resource management approach that takes into account the entire ecosystem, including the interlinkages across different environmental dimensions and the needs of stakeholders.
- 5) **Adaptation to Changing Circumstances:** Over time, the Rhine has faced challenges such as pollution and economic interests, leading to changes in its governance. The trends in such adaptive capacity challenge governance frameworks to be attuned to the dynamic environmental and social landscape.
- 6) In terms of constructing popular support of new agreements and policies, it is crucial to **involve local communities, industries and NGOs in the collaborative discussion** to reflect diverse perspectives.
- 7) Ongoing evaluation through complete **monitoring program** provides the input for decision-making with regards to the attainment of environmental goals and targets.
- 8) **Public awareness campaigns** are critical for the promotion of sustainable water management: educating the public about water conservation and ecosystem health reinforces public support for collaborative solutions.

5.2.4 Middle East

Examples from the Middle East are represented by the following 4 river basins and the Disi aquifer:

River Basin	Aquifer
Euphrates-Tigris Basin	Disi Aquifer
Jordan River Basin	
Orontes River Basin	
Yarmouk River Basin	

The Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB)

Background

The Euphrates-Tigris system consists of two rivers, each 80 km apart, that run almost parallel to 1900 km (Tigris) and 2,800 km (Euphrates). The system (Figure 28) emerges from the valleys and gorges of eastern Anatolia in Türkiye, and travels through northern Syria and Iraq, before converging in south-east Iraq to create a distinct section of the river, known as Shatt Al-Arab, which separates it from Iran, which ultimately merges into the Arabian Gulf (Lahn & Shamout, 2015).

Figure 28: The Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020).

The Tigris River is originating from southeast Türkiye, in the southern slopes of the Taurus branch of the Mountain, and draining an area of Türkiye, Syria and Iraq (Zarei, 2020). The Tigris River travels along the Turkish Syrian border for 32 km before reaching Iraq. The river and its tributaries **provide water for around 30 million people** (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2020). The Karah Su and Murad Su rivers merge near Kuban to **form the Euphrates River** (Al-Ansari, 2013). It drains an area of 444000 Km² which covers parts of four nations (Iraq, Türkiye, Syria and Saudi Arabia) (Zarei, 2020). Supporting an estimated 60 million people, the Euphrates is a direct water **provider to 27 million** of these (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). The Euphrates and Tigris rivers are the main provider to the potable and agricultural water in the region (Kucukmehmetoglu & Geymen, 2014). However, about 90% of Iraq's surface water is provided by neighboring countries, with roughly 80% coming from Türkiye (Al-Muqdadi et al., 2016).

The Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB) comprises around 789000 km² and includes parts of Türkiye, Syria, Iraq, Iran, and Saudi Arabia (Wolf et al., 1999). Within the lower basin there is an immense floodplain created where the rivers Karun (Iran), Euphrates, and Tigris meet to produce perennial lakes, marshes, and riparian zones, particularly the Shatt Al-Arab River and the Mesopotamian Marshes (Olson & Speidel, 2024).

Problems and Motivations

Climate change, insufficient riparian cooperation, aggressive hydro development, inefficient farming practices, and political instability are all contributing to deteriorating conditions in the Euphrates-Tigris Basin (ETB) (Lahn & Shamout, 2015). Since the 1970s, the downstream flow of the Euphrates River has decreased by approximately 40-45%, primarily because over 30 dams and barrages have been built (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). Previously, the usual yearly **discharge** of the Euphrates at the Syrian Turkish border was approximately 30 billion cubic meters (BCM), which **decreased to about 25 BCM** in 2013 (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013).

The basin water conditions are expected to be more stressed with forecast river flow in Türkiye keep dropping because of increased temperatures and evaporation related to climate change (Kibaroglu, 2014, (Zarei, 2020). The Tigris' Mesopotamian **Marshes are around 14% of their initial extent** because of upstream damming efforts. The river is also **susceptible to a variety of contaminants**, including untreated household and industrial waste, agricultural runoff, and irrigation return flows (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013).

Decreased access to water has serious implications for Syria and Iraq, who rely largely on transboundary waters from Türkiye and are currently amongst the world's highest water-stressed countries (Euronews, 2019). Struggles between upstream user management decisions (Türkiye) and downstream needs from Syria and Iraq dominate **regional hydropolitics** (Wolf & Newton, 2007; Voss et al., 2013). Türkiye's early efficient use of water resources, such as **hydropower development** (1936) and major **dam construction in the 1970s**, created an **enormous obstacle to collaboration** across the region, as the country is the biggest contributor of water

to the Euphrates, generating about 89% of the flow and 51% to 65% of the Tigris' annual discharge (Lahn & Shamout, 2015). Türkiye's extensive dam-building activities have granted it significant control over water flow to downstream regions. This development poses ongoing challenges for nations such as Iraq. Specifically, the construction of the Ilisu Dam on the Tigris River has reduced water availability, limiting rice cultivation and displacing farmers, which has led to public protests (Euronews, 2019).

The Southeast Anatolia Project (GAP), initiated by Türkiye includes the creation of 22 dams and 19 hydropower units along the Euphrates and Tigris River basins, worsened relations between the riparian countries (Voss et al., 2013; Zarei, 2020). A key instance is the **Ataturk Dam's completion in the 1990s**, which caused the displacement of many communities with insufficient relocation provisions. This heightened tensions from the already delicate situation between Türkiye and its neighbors, Iraq and Syria, over the management of shared water resources (Akyürek, 2005). A key outcome of the project has been a serious decline in water flowing to downstream countries, with Iraq suffering an 80% drop in its share of Euphrates water (Zarei, 2020).

Compounding this situation are the regional challenges stemming from the **lack of enforceable international agreements** regarding the management of surface and groundwater shared by Türkiye, Iraq, and Iran. Iraqi and Syrian governments often attempted unilaterally to regulate their respective water demands with Turkey in order to undermine the other's position (Aldalooi, 2024). This was the main reason that the 13 meetings of the Joint Technical Committee (JTC) between the co-riparian states held in 1980–1993 failed to lead to the creation of a basin-wide regime (Kirschner and Tiroch 2012, 121).

The transboundary water relations between **Türkiye and Syria were significantly affected by the political crisis that emerged in October 1998**, when Türkiye demanded Syria to stop supporting non-state armed groups. Türkiye's forcible diplomacy and its political and military implications led to the signing of a security agreement known as the **Adana Accord in 1998**. Following this agreement, **Syria's complaints** regarding the flow of the Euphrates River **diminished**, and water resources played a crucial role in post-conflict recovery and peacebuilding (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). However, **the Syrian civil war (2011-2024)** and broader regional instability have further complicated cooperation efforts. While the conflict's origins are multifaceted, water issues have undoubtedly played a role, highlighting the intersection of environmental, political, and social factors in the region's governance challenges (Kibaroglu, 2020). **The source of the conflicts and arguments originates from the lack of a formal, basin-wide agreement that allocates the water** of each river between the three countries (ESCWA, 2002; Gruen, 2000). Moreover, in current years, **various state and extremist groups** have increasingly turned to **manipulating water resources as a strategic weapon** in Iraq and Syria. They have taken **control of or damaged key dams**, including those in Tabqa, Tishrin, Mosul, and Fallujah, to exert influence over water flow (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019).

Iraq is currently facing a serious threat of water scarcity due to poor water resource management, internal political tensions, and volatile relationships with surrounding countries (Al-Muqdadı et al., 2016). A water scarcity could significantly harm the Iraqi economy in a variety of national areas, including agriculture and public health (Al-Muqdadı et al., 2016). Furthermore, it may cause unforeseen environmental difficulties (Al-Muqdadı et al., 2016). The lack of a comprehensive framework for water cooperation has left loopholes in existing agreements, undermining efforts to establish effective governance structures in the Euphrates-Tigris basin (Kibaroglu, 2020; Kibaroglu, 2017).

In conclusion, although numerous agreements and protocols have been signed among or between the transboundary countries, none of them have gone into force, on account of the powerful positions of both Turkey and Iran compared to Iraq and Syria. Turkey dominates the Tigris and Euphrates against Iraq and Syria, while Iran has control of most of the tributaries of the Tigris (Yousuf et al., 2018).

Cooperation Methods

Figure 29 shows a summary of cooperation evolution in the Tigris-Euphrates Basin during the period 1975-2018 (The Economist Intelligence Unit., 2020).

Figure 29: Timeline of cooperation evolution in the Tigris-Euphrates Basin.

The only recorded **example of interstate fighting over water** in the Euphrates-Tigris Basin and may be in the whole world date back to 2500 BC. Iraq, Türkiye, and Syria have been involved in a long-standing water issue that has yet to be resolved through mutual agreement (Al-Muqdadı et al., 2016). In the early 20th century, France and Britain initiated efforts to form committees and institutions aimed at managing the Euphrates River. However, these attempts did not result in formal agreements, leading to a persistent lack of regional

coordination (Lahn & Shamout, 2015). Since then, the recurring trend has been occasional bilateral involvement with no regional binding structures, as well as repeated discontinued development due to larger political instability (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). Furthermore, these bilateral agreements were not primarily about water and did not build on earlier treaties (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019).

In 1923, Iraq signed its first treaty with Turkey called the Lausanne agreement, which included an article indicates that both countries must preserve their rights when a water management system is built in the territory of another state or when water is used in the territory of one of the countries (Yousuf et al., 2018). Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye signed their first agreement (The **Treaty of Ankara**) in 1926, although Türkiye violated its responsibilities at the time (Al-Muqdadı et al., 2016). The "**Treaty of Friendship and Neighbourly Relations**", signed in **1946** between Iraq and Türkiye, represents a significant attempt to manage the shared water resources of the Euphrates and Tigris rivers. This treaty aimed to promote cooperation by establishing a framework for the equitable use of these vital watercourses, which play a crucial role in both countries' water security and agricultural productivity (Zarei, 2020). However, the two countries neglected its implementation. Technical coordination efforts **in the 1960s and 1970s** were interfered by political regimes in Syria and Iraq. The "**Algiers Accord**" of **1975** also called the **1975 "Agreement between Iran and Iraq concerning the use of frontier watercourses"** emphasized the need for collaborative management of transboundary water resources (Zarei, 2020). The 1975 Algiers Agreement aimed to resolve a border dispute between Iran and Iraq, addressing issues of navigation and resource allocation. However, the subsequent Iran-Iraq War (1980–1988) disrupted this cooperation. Despite recent efforts to revive dialogue, the agenda has remained largely unchanged since 1975, with little diplomatic progress (The National, 2019).

A Joint Technical Committee (JTC) was formed in 1983 with the contribution of Türkiye, Syria, and Iraq, its goal was to provide methods and procedures for determining appropriate and acceptable amounts of water that each country may draw from the Euphrates and Tigris rivers. However, the JTC was unable to reach significant agreements, prompting the suspension of negotiations in 1993 (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). **In 1987 and 1990**, two **bilateral protocols** emerged as provisional agreements following high-level discussions among leaders of the basin countries. The **1987 Turkish Syrian Protocol on Economic Cooperation**, the first formal bilateral agreement along the Euphrates, included Türkiye's commitment to maintain a water flow (approximately 16 billion m³ annually) along the Turkish Syrian border, in exchange for a security arrangement with Syria (Kibaroglu, 2020). This marked the first instance where a measurable and consistent volume of shared water flow was established. However, the agreement was driven by immediate security concerns at the time rather than serving as a foundation for a long-term arrangement (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). The **1990 Syrian Iraqi water protocol** allocated 42% of Euphrates water to Syria and 58% to Iraq as a fixed yearly proportion (Kibaroglu, 2020; Altınbilek, 2004). The **Euphrates–Tigris Initiative for Cooperation (ETIC)** was founded in 2005 (Kibaroglu, 2020). It is a collaboration of water

experts, former diplomats, technocrats, and scholars from Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye, set up as a form of track-two diplomacy to advance dialogue and scientific collaboration on international waters. ETIC intends to promote dialogue and cooperation over water issues management even with the general political tension and conflicts in the region by concentrating on less contentious issues like dam safety, river hydrology, or geographic information systems. On the other hand, this participatory approach addressing the needs of the target countries enhances trust and cooperation needed for regional stabilization and sustainable utilization of transboundary water resources (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). The established ETIC, together with other informal policy initiatives **CPET (Collaborative Programme Euphrates and Tigris)** which covered the period from 2013 to 2018, was aimed at providing aid to Euphrates and Tigris countries: Türkiye, Iran, and Iraq in improving their water management through dialogue, trust building, information sharing, analysis, and setting priorities for investment in the region (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). **In 2009, Türkiye and Iraq established a water protocol** that focused on the two countries exchanging hydrological and meteorological data as well as the effective use of regional water resources. The protocol also included monitoring and assessing water raw materials in light of climate change, harmonizing existing hydrological measurement systems, upgrading irrigation methods, technical assistance from Türkiye regarding Iraqi water treatment and supply, and even the construction of flood and drought control measures. With assistance from **the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC)**, the **Strategic Foresight Group**, a think tank based in Mumbai, held a series of **Blue Peace meetings in 2013 and 2014**. Participants agreed to concentrate on the Tigris River, given that the circumstances in Syria hindered any cooperative efforts across the entire basin that would involve the Euphrates (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). The delegations, which included senior advisors to prime ministers, former cabinet ministers, parliament members, officials from water ministries and authorities, as well as experts from Iraq and Türkiye, reached an agreement on **a plan of action** aimed at enhancing the exchange and standardization of data related to the flows of the Tigris River (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). While this informal plan has not been completely put into action, later technical meetings between the water agencies of Iraq and Türkiye have incorporated the topic of **data exchange and harmonization** into their official discussions regarding the potential construction of joint dams along the border (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). Syria's civil war has made real regional collaboration impossible, given the country shares more than one river basin (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). In 2014, Türkiye and Iraq began ministerial-level communication on their transboundary water resources, which concluded in the signing of the minutes of the bilateral cooperation meeting (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021). This step reflects the importance of water as a vital issue in international relations and the role of diplomacy in addressing environmental concerns (Kibaroglu & Sayan, 2021).

In 2017, the Iraqi government sought an advisory mission to look into collaboration between Iran and Iraq on the preservation of shared wetland areas and marshes fed by the Tigris, which have been drying out as an

outcome of upstream dam developments, increased water extraction for agriculture, and decreased rainfall (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019). Finally, in **2019** Türkiye and Iraq reached an **agreement and developed an action plan to set up a Water Resources Center in Baghdad** to tackle water-related challenges in the region (AA Energy, 2019).

In conclusion, there are no official water allocation rights for both surface and groundwater, which is mostly owing to disagreements in interpretation of international water law (Voss et al. 2013). These disparities substantially limit the possibility of reaching an agreement on basin-wide legal allocations or management practices. Furthermore, the scarcity of hydrologic data, as well as a lack of transparency and accessibility, lead to an incomplete understanding of water accessibility and use in the basin (Voss et al., 2013). As a result, ETB countries must move beyond bilateralism and adopt a regional collective approach, as well as delegate greater negotiating power to key water agencies and stakeholders (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2019).

Lessons learned

1. The Role of Technical Cooperation as a Stabilizing Mechanism

With the aid of technology and science, information enables discourse and trust between the riparian states that sets the stage for formal agreements, which require a higher degree of trust and confidence even if one is lacking in the given moment. To the backdrop of geopolitical instability and a limited base of formal agreements, **the Joint Technical Committee (JTC)**, later turned into collaborative efforts like the **Euphrates–Tigris Initiative for Cooperation (ETIC)**, illustrates that although political relations are strained, there are still avenues for technical cooperation.

2. Institutional Flexibility Enhances Resilience during Conflict

Creating flexible and informal institutions ensures cooperation can persist even in politically volatile settings, helping to manage tensions and build frameworks for future collaboration. The **informal and track-two diplomacy** efforts, such as ETIC and the Collaborative Programme on Euphrates and Tigris (CPET), demonstrate the value of flexible governance mechanisms. These initiatives allow water professionals, academics, and former diplomats to engage in discussions on non-contentious topics like dam safety and hydrological monitoring, maintaining communication during periods of conflict.

3. Bilateral Protocols Provide Short-Term Solutions but Require Long-Term Strategies

Bilateral protocols regarding the sharing of waters may provide short-term relief, but the entire process calls for diplomatic contacts and collaboration towards customizing solutions to future issues and environmental changes. The various treaties made between the parties offered one-off aid by detailing how water would be shared, but there were no long-term mechanisms for resolution of conflicts, dispute after dispute emerged. At the same time, the treaties set the foundation for collaboration, but maintenance in the form of constant follow-ups was very necessary.

4. Cooperation is Linked to Broader Regional Politics and Security

Water allocation diplomacy should not be dissociated from regional security concern. The vulnerability of water infrastructure to attacks makes it imperative to adopt measures that protect them in a cooperative security framework. That is also in the 1987 protocol where the Türkiye consented to a certain minimum flow of water to be released on the understanding that Syria will be concerned about the security situation.

5. Data Exchange Builds Trust and Supports Effective Water Management

Sharing data and ensuring transparency in water management foster mutual trust and strengthen cooperation in transboundary water governance. Initiatives such as **ETIC and the Blue Peace meetings** highlight the importance of **data harmonization and transparency** in water diplomacy.

6. The absence of a regional cooperation mechanism remains a considerable challenge, and there are very limited regional cooperation channels in other areas (economic or political) that could form a basis of closer engagement on water management. The foremost water diplomacy measure for the nation is to establish regional water cooperation mechanisms, such as river basin organization with Türkiye. These steps could in turn mitigate the general hostile situation in the region.

Jordan River Basin (JRB)

Background

The Jordan River Basin is shared among Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Palestine (West Bank) and Israel (Figure 30). The headwaters of the Jordan River originate from the Anti-Lebanon mountain range, primarily fed by three main sources: the Hasbani River in Lebanon, the Baniyas River from the Golan Heights (Syria), and the Dan River in Israel. These tributaries merge to form the upper Jordan River, which flows southward through the Tiberias Lake (Katz, 2022; Swain, 2004), the largest freshwater lake in the region. After exiting the lake, the river continues 5 km downstream, and merges with the Yarmouk River, which is a major tributary whose catchment area lies in the Huran Plain (Syrian and Jordan) and the Golan Heights as well as in some parts of Jordan. The Jordan river continues to flow approximately 100 km to the Dead Sea, acting as a natural boundary between Israel and Jordan as shown in Figure 1 (Katz, 2022). The river stretch between the Tiberias Lake and the Dead Sea is called 'lower Jordan'. The Upper Jordan River's natural inflow to Tiberias Lake is estimated to be between 500 and 550 million cubic meters (MCM) per year (Naff, 2000), while the Jordan River's average annual natural flow into the Dead Sea is estimated to be 1200-1400 MCM (Naff, 2000; Swain, 2004; Safier, 2011). The river's water quality is generally considered good (Al-Addous et al., 2023).

Figure 30: The Jordan River Basin (Klise et al., 2009).

Problems and Motivations

The Jordan river faces several challenges, including reduced flow due to upstream diversions and climate change, which threaten both water availability and ecological health (Fathallah, 1996). Factors such as increased water consumption and the impact of the Syrian crisis, started in 2011, have exacerbated the decline in the river's flow (Al-Addous et al., 2023). In fact, since **Israel's establishment (1948)**, the Jordan River has been a crucial bargaining point due to the need for water and the ongoing antagonism between Israel and the neighboring Arab States (Swain, 2004). As most sections of the river and its tributaries are managed by a different riparian state (Katz, 2022), the numerous challenges that face Jordan River Basin are largely due to the fragmented political system involving multiple countries with complex, often conflicting relationships. The overlapping jurisdictions, particularly between Jordan and Israel, complicate water management, as both

countries are positioned upstream and downstream of each other along various parts of the Jordan river system. Additionally, Lebanon, Syria, and Israel control the Upper Jordan's headwaters, while Jordan and Syria jointly oversee the Yarmouk River, which merges with the Lower Jordan, forming the border between Israel and Jordan (Katz, 2022).

The amount of water transported by the river has been considerably reduced primarily to the exploitation of the fresh water of the Sea of Galilee and the Yarmouk River in Syria (Swain, 2004). Historically, the river had an annual discharge of 1,200–1,350 MCM, but today, it has fallen to less than 100 MCM due to extensive water diversions by Israel for agriculture and urban consumption (Katz, 2022). This depletion not only **affects the river's ecosystem** but has also **diminished the Dead Sea's water levels**, a major economic resource for Jordan and Israel (Mehyar et al., 2009). Furthermore, **biodiversity in the river basin has been significantly impacted by the diminished flow**, creating additional pressures on local farmers who depend on the river for irrigation (Mehyar et al., 2009).

Challenges in water governance and hence sustainable water management was initiated by the **1916 Sykes-Picot Agreement**. The new borders created by the agreement resulted in the Upper Jordan River headwaters and most of the Tiberias Lake falling under British control, largely influenced by Zionist lobbying for future access to water resources (Gil-Har, 2000). **The rapid population growth and economic development** of the region from the 1930s to the 1950s put additional pressure on the Jordan River's limited resources (Wolf, 1995). During this period, water usage studies led by the U.S. emphasized the importance of fair resource distribution to prevent further conflict. However, water disputes persisted, contributing to what is now termed **the "water wars" from 1964 to 1967**, when both the Arab States and Israel took aggressive measures to secure control over water (Lowi, 1995). In 1964, **Israel began diverting 320 MCM of water** each year through its **National Water Carrier**, dramatically reducing the Jordan River's flow and causing tensions with Jordan. As a result, **Syria and Lebanon** resolved in 1965 to build **canals** to divert the Jordan's headwaters upstream of the National Water Carrier, which were **destroyed by Israeli forces** (Swain, 2004).

Israel had greater control of the Jordan and Litani Rivers, taking advantage of its new hydro-strategic position after the 1967 war and the 1982 invasion of Lebanon. Therefore, it **was withdrawing more water from the Jordan basin**. Despite the political tensions because Israeli utilization of the basin's total discharge by the 1990s had reached more than 60%, regional cooperation on practical water management issues increased. However, even as nations acknowledged each other's water rights, **disagreements over specific allocations remained unresolved**, leading to what was described as a "silent war" over water (Lowi, 1993).

Cooperation methods

One of the earliest frameworks to promote collaboration among the riparian states was the **Johnston Plan (1953)** proposed a comprehensive strategy for water allocation among Israel, Jordan, Syria, and Lebanon.

Despite the plan **not being officially ratified** for political reasons (Haddadin, 2000), it provided a foundation for subsequent negotiations and influenced informal water-sharing practices until the 1990s (Wolf, 1995). The most notable formal agreement is the **1994 peace treaty** between Israel and Jordan, which included Annex II: "Water-Related Matters." Innovative technological and scientific approaches played a key role in the water-related section of the treaty. According to the treaty, Israel is permitted to extract 12 million MCM from the Yarmouk River in the summer and 13 MCM in the winter. In response, Jordan can store 20 MCM of water in Lake Tiberias in the winter, which Israel must release back to Jordan during the summer (Susskind & Islam, 2012). Additionally, Israel committed to assisting Jordan in locating extra water through desalination technology, which aligns well with Israel's ongoing desalination initiatives (Susskind & Islam, 2012). However, **the provisions of the water agreement no longer appear to be equal** considering the social, economic, and environmental developments that have happened in the region as a whole and within the two countries individually (Talozi et al., 2019).

The **'Pact for better basins management of national and transboundary basins'** was signed by representatives of river basin organizations from Jordan, Lebanon, Israel and the West Bank **in the 2011** general assembly of the Mediterranean Network of Basin Organizations held in Porto, Portugal (Comair et al., 2012a). The pact was also **signed at the World Water Forum in 2012**. The meeting in Porto led to a consensus that countries will eventually have to deal with water quantity and quality issues after the political issues are overcome. Using decision support tools that consider water allocation rules, water demands, and regulations implemented in all nations, the co-riparians will need to assess their water management plans when a fair and reasonable agreement has been established (Comair et al., 2012b).

In **2022**, Israel and Jordan signed a **Memorandum of Understanding** aimed at the rehabilitation and protection of the Jordan River, which has suffered significant degradation due to drought and sewage discharge (The Water Diplomat, 2022). **The agreement marks a significant step** in environmental cooperation between the two countries. It follows a decision by Israel to restore a section of the southern Jordan basin, enhancing sewage treatment and increasing water releases from Lake Tiberias from 30 MCM to a maximum of 70 MCM (The Water Diplomat, 2022). This initiative **builds on the 1994 peace treaty**, which included clauses for the river's protection, addressing the severe decline in water quality and flow caused by damming and diversion projects by Israel, Syria, and Jordan, resulting in a 98% reduction in flow and increased pollution levels in the river's lower section (The Water Diplomat, 2022). Jordan and Israel, together with the United Arab Emirates, signed **water-for-energy memorandum of understanding**. The plan, first announced in 2022, is for Jordan to create 600 megawatts of solar electricity capacity to be sold to Israel. In exchange, Israel would offer Jordan with 200 million cubic meters of desalinated water, which is in short supply (Mansour & Reiffenstuel, 2022). However, the deal has **been effectively cancelled by Jordan** due to the war in Gaza.

In conclusion, like other situations in the world, the dynamics of cooperation in the Jordan River Basin are influenced by the concept of hydro-hegemony, where power asymmetries shape the interactions between states. Israel, as the regional hydro-hegemon, leverages its military and economic advantages to assert influence over water-sharing arrangements with its neighbors (Stark, 2011).

Lessons Learned

1. **Equitable and Reasonable Use: Agreements** governing the Jordan River **should adhere to the principle of "equitable and reasonable use"** of shared water resources. This principle is crucial for ensuring that all riparian states benefit fairly from the water, rather than allowing hydro-hegemony to dominate.
2. **Effective Allocative Mechanisms: Allocative mechanisms** for the Jordan River **should be based on a combination of** water quality, use, need, and availability, **rather than** relying solely **on availability** as has been the practice in the past. This multifaceted approach is essential for creating fair agreements that reflect the actual needs and conditions of all parties involved.
3. **Flexibility in Agreements: Water treaties** related to the Jordan River **need to be flexible** rather than rigid. A renegotiation of water agreement terms is a must due in large part to changes in population and the availability of alternative water resources (desalination and treated wastewater)
4. **Clear Definitions to Avoid Ambiguity: Allocative mechanisms** should **avoid ambiguity** in defining flows and uses. Clear definitions help prevent misinterpretations that can arise during implementation, ensuring that all parties understand their rights and obligations. Ambiguity can lead to disputes and undermine the effectiveness of agreements.
5. **Addressing Power Asymmetries: The existing agreements** often reflect power imbalances, where more powerful states, particularly Israel, can dictate terms that may not be equitable for Jordan and Syria. **Recognizing and addressing these power dynamics is crucial for creating fair and effective water management agreements** that serve all parties involved.
6. **Inclusion of Local Stakeholders: Engaging local communities and stakeholders** in the negotiation and implementation processes is vital for the Jordan River basin. Their involvement ensures that agreements are grounded in the realities of water use and management on the ground, leading to more effective and accepted solutions.

Orantes River Basin (ORB)

Background

The Orontes River (Figure 31), referred to as the Asi River in both Arabic and Turkish, translates to "Rebel," as it is unique in Western Asia for flowing from south to north, which is a direction that is unusual for rivers in this region (Ballabio et al., 2015; FAO, 2009). The Orontes River serves as a critical shared watercourse for Lebanon, Syria, and Türkiye. Originating at Lebanon's Labweh springs near Baalbek, it travels through Syria and Türkiye, eventually draining into the Mediterranean Sea (FAO, 2013). Two key tributaries sustain its flow—the Afrin and Karasu rivers—while its basin spans 26325 km², reflecting its regional significance (Ballabio et al., 2015).

Figure 31: The Orontes River Basin (Oregon State University, & University of Dundee, 2009).

Geographically, the river stretches approximately 448 km in total: 83 km lie within Lebanon, 280 km traverse Syria, 27 km mark the Syrian Turkish border, and the final 59 km cross into Türkiye itself. The area of the basin is distributed by 7.6% in Lebanon, 67.4% in Syria, and 25% in Türkiye (Ballabio et al., 2015). Syria utilizes the largest share of the river's water resources and has developed extensive dam infrastructure along its course (Dolatyar & Gray, 2000). The Orontes River has a mean annual discharge of approximately 2400 million m³; however, reports indicate that the current surface water availability is only about 1110 million m³. The river serves as a critical source of water for irrigation and agricultural activities in the riparian countries (FAO, 2009).

Problems and Motivations

Historically, the Orontes River has been a **source of territorial conflict** among its three riparian states—Türkiye, Syria, and Lebanon. Subsequently, **conflicts** over basin management **escalated**, reaching critical intensity in the **post-1940s** period. A significant ecological disruption occurred when **Lake Amik in Türkiye**, historically sustained by the Orontes as its primary tributary, entirely **dried up by 1970**. While **river diversion** expanded agricultural land, it simultaneously exacerbated disputes over water distribution among the riparian states (Kibaroglu et al., 2011). Syria, prioritizing water for irrigation and industrial purposes, currently appropriates roughly 90% of the river's flow. Meanwhile, Lebanon—traditionally reliant on its independent water source, the Litani River—faces persistent challenges in securing equitable access to the Orontes. The **2002 Lebanon-Syria agreement** faced widespread criticism for its pro-Syrian bias, allocating Lebanese users a marginal 3.8 m³/s, a disproportionately low share reflecting Syria's hegemonic control (Ballabio et al., 2015).

Syria-Türkiye relations have fluctuated due to **overlapping claims over water and territory**. Syria's dismissal of an international treaty recognizing Turkish sovereignty over Hatay province has further politicized Orontes negotiations, entangling hydrological disputes with broader geopolitical tensions (Kibaroglu et al., 2011). **The Syrian civil war (2011-2024) compounded instability**, as Türkiye's infrastructure projects in Syria faced destruction, fostering mutual distrust. Presently, the **Orontes Basin is governed through unilateral management frameworks, and the absence of trilateral collaboration** amplifies conflict risks, particularly water scarcity. **The Basins at Risk project** designates the Orontes as “at risk,” citing potential drastic water supply reductions due to expansive territorial development initiatives. Scholars emphasize that only collaborative resource-sharing among riparian communities can mitigate tensions, promote sustainability, and avert insecurity threatening regional development (Ballabio et al., 2015).

Cooperation methods

One of the significant advancements noted from the 1940s was the formation of the **Syrian Lebanese Joint Committee** which provided for Lebanon's annual allocation of 100 million cubic meters (MCM) and established a framework for shared governance (Shamout, 2015). The committee added the allocation of infrastructure development and security of Lebanon's water supply through dams and regulators to the modified allocation protocols introduced in 1968. Ultimately, **bilateral negotiations led to a 1972 agreement** which signified an end to Syria's unilateral claim over the Orontes River and committed to the cooperative management of its water resources (Shamout, 2015). While the agreement symbolized significant cooperation between the countries, it was diluted by political conflict and tensions associated with the violent skirmishes that erupted between the two countries. However, the agreement was important in the indication of cooperated management of the river instead of Lebanon wars as a contest of sovereignty. Rather, the use of the river as a stabilizing factor was encouraged and on the **20th of September 1994, the bilateral agreement** stating the river as "shared water" was signed. This agreement laid down the river's childbirth place, average annual discharge, and the allowances of water – for Lebanon, 80 MCM/year and for Syria, 340 MCM/year. The 1994 agreement also included provisions for a **Joint Technical Committee** to manage the river flow within Lebanese territory, financed by Syria, and established a joint arbitrary committee to evaluate compliance with the agreement (Shamout, 2015; Ballabio et al., 2015). Syria and Lebanon are both signatories to the **UN Convention on Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses**. This commitment prompted the two nations to incorporate the convention's principles into the **2002 Orontes water sharing agreement**. Many experts view this agreement as a successful outcome that benefits both riparian countries, creating a **win-win situation** for both states. It developed over ten years of discussions and revisions, focusing on the equitable and reasonable utilization of the river while promoting collaboration between the states involved. An agreement between Syria and Türkiye was finalized in 2001 that calls for cooperation on technical issues and identifies the potential for cooperation on future projects (TFDD, 2003); however, it does not address sharing of a specific quantity (Klise et al., 2009). Additionally, **the 2004 Free Trade Agreement between Syria and Türkiye** included discussions on water cooperation, although these efforts were complicated by the outbreak of the Syrian civil war in 2011, which severely disrupted infrastructure and management initiatives. **The 2010 Framework Agreement on Water Cooperation between Türkiye and Syria** also aimed to address shared water resources, but its implementation has been hindered by political tensions (Kibaroglu et al., 2011). Attempts at trilateral negotiations over the Orontes are frustrated by a land conflict over the Hatay Province, which Türkiye controls, but Syria believes is a part of its own territory (Çarkođlu et al., 1998; Wirkus, 2004).

Lessons learned

1. **The Necessity of Legal Frameworks:** This case brings forth the need for other international agreements, both bilateral and trilateral, between Lebanon, Syria, and Türkiye, regulating the usage of water resources. Legal agreements are critical because they articulate the obligations of the respective countries, making it possible for all the riparian countries to share the benefits of the river on an equitable basis.
2. **Political stability is a cornerstone of cooperation:** Although the region is politically charged, constant dialogue in countries sharing the resources is necessary for building trust for transboundary water management.
3. **Conflicts over land** hinder cooperations among riparian states such as the case of the conflict over the Hatay Province, which Türkiye controls, but Syria believes is a part of its own territory.

Yarmouk River Basin (YRB)

Background

The Yarmouk River, the largest tributary of the Jordan River, is shared by Jordan, Syria, and Israel. It flows along the northwestern border of Jordan with Syria and between Jordan and the occupied Golan Heights running for over 140 km, eventually joining the Jordan River about 7–9 km south of Tiberias Lake as shown in figure 32 (Hussein & Grandi, 2017). It flows from Jabal al Arab (Jabal al Druze), at an elevation of about 1700 meters above sea level, to Baqura at 200 meters below sea level, where it joins the lower main Jordan River (Al-Rubeai, 2004; UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). Approximately 80% of the basin area (7,242 km²) lies within the Syrian territory, and the remaining lies inside Jordan (Obeidat et al., 2019).

Traditionally, the river's flow has been estimated to range from 450 to 500 million cubic meters (MCM) annually (Swain, 2004), roughly 40 to 50% of this flow is estimated to have originated as groundwater (Zeitoun et al., 2019). However, this flow has drastically decreased over the years, from 229 MCM per year in the 1980s (JVA, 2016) to 40 MCM in 2015. This low rate probably being mainly due to changes in water availability, surface water offtakes and groundwater abstraction in Syria, and, to a lesser degree, in Jordan (Muller et al., 2016).

Figure 32: The Yarmouk River Basin (Hussein & Grandi, 2017).

Problems and Motivations

The transboundary Yarmouk River basin has been a central point of tension among Jordan, Syria, and Israel, driven primarily by competing water demands and unilateral actions that have complicated collaborative management efforts. Although there was a warning of potential "**water wars**" due to increasing demands for water (Homer-Dixon, 1994), others argue that water scarcity can foster dialogue, **regional cooperation, and peace** (Allan, 2002; Wolf et al., 2003). Syria's upstream dominance of the river characterized it as the hydro hegemon, while Jordan, as a downstream state, possesses less political and bargaining power (Zeitoun & Mirumachi, 2008; Hussein & Grandi, 2017).

The change in regional dynamics post 1967 war made Jordan more reliant on external water sources like the Yarmouk River. At the same time, the extensive of dam construction upstream by the Syrians further limited Jordan's water access (Haddadin, 2001). In addition, while Jordan revealed its intentions in the late 1950s to redirect the Yarmouk River for irrigation by building the **King Abdullah Canal (East Ghor Canal)**, Israel initiated the development of a **National Water Carrier to channel water from the Tiberias Lake to its dry southern regions** (Frenken, 2009). Although Jordan and Syria signed an agreement on water resources management of Yarmouk River basin in 1987, Syria's unilateral construction of dams on the Yarmouk River tributaries without Jordanian approval escalated tensions, as these actions significantly reduced the river's flow into Jordan. Syria's decision to prioritize its water needs upstream undermined the spirit of cooperation and exacerbated the existing water scarcity in Jordan (Hussein & Grandi, 2017). Syria refused to provide

Jordan with the water share agreed to in the 1987 treaty, blaming the reduction of the flow on a decrease in precipitation. Despite the formal agreement, the Al-Wehda Dam faced significant delays, and Syria continued to exploit the river by constructing additional dams and drilling wells, further reducing the flow of water into Jordan (Kubursi, 2011). **By 2012**, Syria had constructed **48 dams** and drilled approximately **3,500 wells** to extract groundwater, **violating the terms of the 1987 agreement** (Namrouqa, 2012). The Al-Wehda Dam, finally completed in 2009, has never reached its full operational capacity, where it held only 20 MCM of water in 2009–2010 (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). Additionally, the water quality in the dam has also deteriorated over time, making it suitable only for agricultural use (Al-Taani, 2013). Due to the decline in agricultural activity and water extraction and power cuts in Syria **because of the outbreak of the Syrian civil war in 2011**, the flow of the Yarmouk River into Jordan increased to approximately 60 MCM (Jamani, 2012). The political instability in Syria has shifted the balance of waterpower in favor of Jordan, as Syria's ability to enforce its upstream dominance has diminished, realizing it is a temporal situation (Jamani, 2012). Moreover, Jordan strengthened its trade relations with other countries over Syria (Hussein & Grandi, 2017). This shift in power dynamics could lead to renegotiations of water-sharing agreements in the future.

Cooperation Methods

Cooperation methods surrounding the Yarmouk River have evolved through a series of bilateral rather than multilateral agreements and treaties among Jordan, Syria, and Israel (Frenken, 2009). However, these efforts have often faced significant obstacles due to power imbalances and implementation issues. As of today, there is no comprehensive agreement in place for Yarmouk River water management, but bilateral agreements. One of the earliest initiatives to address water allocation in the region was **the Johnston Plan in 1953**. This plan aimed to distribute water from the Jordan Basin, which includes the Yarmouk Basin, among Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, and Syria (Climate diplomacy, 2024). The Johnston Plan proposed water allocations of 616 MCM to Israel, 720 MCM to Jordan (including the West Bank), 35 MCM to Lebanon, and 132 MCM to Syria, with 506 MCM from the Yarmouk River itself (Manna, 2006; Phillips et al., 2007; Haddadin, 2009; UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). While the plan reached a technical agreement among the riparian states, it was never ratified due to the political implications of recognizing Israel (Hof, 1998). The Johnston Plan laid the groundwork for subsequent bilateral agreements, particularly between Jordan and Syria. The **1953 bilateral agreement between Jordan and Syria**, aimed to establish joint management of water resources based on an earlier **1952 American draft** (Climate diplomacy, 2024; Zeitoun et al., 2019; Zawahri, 2010). The Al-Wehda Dam (the Unity Dam) was supposed to be constructed near Maqarin, with a capacity of 300 MCM. The agreement outlined that Jordan would utilize the dam's water for irrigation, while Syria would generate electricity (Haddadin, 2009; UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). This agreement created a **bilateral commission** to oversee water management and resolve disputes through arbitration (Rosenberg, 2006). However, the lack of detailed

provisions on water allocation weakened its ability to effectively meet the needs of both countries. Over time, unilateral Syrian actions, including the construction of unauthorized dams, diminished the intended impact of the agreement.

By 1987, relations between Jordan and Syria had improved enough to renegotiate a **new agreement**, formalizing the **construction of the Al-Wehda Dam with a reduced capacity of 225 MCM**. Under this agreement, Jordan took on the full financial responsibility for building and maintaining the dam (Hussein & Grandi, 2017). This new agreement favored Syria by eliminating third-party arbitration and establishing an intergovernmental framework for dispute resolution (Hof, 1998; UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). The agreement acknowledged Syria's 26 existing dams and stipulated that Jordan could only utilize the Yarmouk's resources after all Syrian dams were filled. The agreement further obligated Syria to discharge 208 million cubic meters (MCM) annually to Jordan and permitted the former to construct 25 dams along the Yarmouk system (Yorke, 2013; Turkish Review, 2014). However, despite these initiatives, the agreement proved inadequate in regulating groundwater utilization, which emerged as a significant source of friction because Syria augmented its infrastructure. This eventually culminated in the construction of an additional 48 dams and the drilling of approximately 3,500 wells to extract groundwater. Consequently, this diminished the water flow to Jordan, prompting disputes, as Jordan accused Syria of contravening the treaty (Zeitoun et al., 2019). The situation was further complicated by the **1994 Water Annex** of the Israel-Jordan peace treaty, which included provisions for the Yarmouk River. This agreement granted Israel access to a significant share of the Yarmouk's waters, despite its substantial freshwater resources, reducing Jordan's share and contributing to tensions with Syria (Hof, 1998). Under the terms of this treaty, Israel agreed to transfer 50 MCM annually from Tiberias Lake to Jordan, but the broader impact of the annex highlighted the ongoing inequities in regional water sharing (Zeitoun et al., 2019). **In 2001**, Jordan and Syria engaged in **bilateral talks** to address the diminished water flow from the Yarmouk. These discussions led to an agreement to reduce the size and capacity of the Al-Wehda Dam to better match the lower-than-expected water levels (Zeitoun et al., 2019). It was only in 2003 that Jordan and Syria reached a final agreement on a plan for **the Wahdah dam**, and its construction started in 2004 (Oregon State University, 2008), and completed in 2005 (Haddadin, 2014). Even with the formation of the **Joint Water Committee in 2009** to monitor water quality and flow, these unilateral actions continued to undermine collaborative management efforts (Hussein & Grandi, 2017).

Lessons Learned

- 1. Political Tensions:** multilateral cooperation is not possible in case of political tensions among the riparian states. A peaceful agreement may pave the way to such agreements.
- 2. Asymmetry of Power between the co-riparians:** The agreements governing the Yarmouk River have been criticized for their inequitable nature, often favoring more powerful states and failing to ensure fair

distribution of water resources. This highlights the importance of designing treaties that prioritize equity and inclusivity.

- 3. Effective Agreements:** An agreement should include important clauses that govern groundwater abstraction, environmental concerns, water quality, and the ability to adapt to changing water quality, availability and need. It should also avoid ambiguous and rigid clauses that do not adapt to changing circumstances which result in inequitable allocation of water.
- 4. Need for Comprehensive Frameworks:** There is a need for comprehensive frameworks that address not only water allocation but also environmental protection and crisis management to ensure the long-term viability of water resources.
- 5. Need for Inclusive Cooperation:** Bilateral cooperation alone may be limited in addressing the complexities of transboundary water management. A more inclusive approach that involves multiple stakeholders, including regional actors and international organizations, is essential for fostering comprehensive solutions and ensuring that all voices are heard in the decision-making process.
- 6. Internal solutions to cope with water scarcity:** Instead of a dispute with uncooperative riparian states, water scarcity could be partially resolved internally and through “peaceful means such as the construction of the Water Conveyance from the fossil-water aquifer of Disi – in the South of Jordan – to its capital, which opened in 2013.

Disi Aquifer (DA)

Background

The Disi aquifer, referred to as Al-Sag in Saudi Arabia, stretches from the Tabuk Plain in northern Saudi Arabia to Wadi Rum in southern Jordan (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). In the case of Jordan, the aquifer system (Figure 33) mostly exhibits in the southern desert and present in subsurface across most of the country (Shaban, 2022). The Disi aquifer is estimated to hold 10 km³ of water in Jordan and 65 km³ in Saudi Arabia (Eckstein, 2015). It consists of fossil groundwater accumulated over 30,000 years with very low natural recharge rates (UN-ESCWA and BGR, 2013; Eckstein, 2015; Muller et al., 2017). Recharge rates for the aquifer are extremely low, estimated at approximately 2.5 mm/year in Saudi Arabia and as low as 0.03 mm/year in Jordan in areas with minimal rainfall, increasing to 3–11 mm/year in higher elevation areas (Mahasneh, 2017). Groundwater in the aquifer is fresh and suitable for all purposes (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013), which is used for public supplies and agriculture in Jordan (Muller et al., 2017).

The aquifer is designated as an important groundwater resource for southern Amman (Ferragina & Greco 2008), that supplies about 100 million m³ yearly to the capital city and other regions of the country (Abu-Jaber & El-Naser, 2016). Furthermore, close to 80 million m³ annually has been allocated for agricultural irrigation

and supply drinking water to southern coastal Aqaba city sourced from the Disi aquifer. In the Tabuk region, abstraction was estimated to be between 1050 and 1700 million m³ for the year 2004 (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013), which posed great challenges towards its sustainable use because it is non-renewable in nature.

Figure 33: The Saq–Ram Aquifer System and Disi Basin, South Jordan (Seraphin et al., 2022).

Problems and Motivations

The Disi aquifer has been **the center of intense disputes due to over-exploitation**, primarily driven by Saudi Arabia’s agricultural expansion. Since the 1980s, **Saudi Arabia has heavily escalated its pumping from the aquifer** in the region, particularly in the Tabuk area, which enabled the country to become a net exporter of cereals but put the aquifer's long-term viability in jeopardy (El-Hadj, 2004; Muller et al., 2017). Whilst groundwater extraction in Jordan has received significant media coverage, the impacts of the extraction of the Disi aquifer by Saudi Arabia on the aquifer are far less transparent, with research indicating that an increasing Saudi Arabian agricultural footprint is an important risk to the long-term sustainability of the Disi aquifer on the Jordanian side (Puri et al., 1999). The **intensive extraction of groundwater from the Saudi side**

(approximately 1000 million m³/ year) has led to a significant decline in water levels, forming a cone of depression that extends toward the Jordanian border, endangering Jordan's access to this vital resource (Abunayyan Trading Corporation and BRGM, 2008; Müller et al., 2017). Jordan's major step was **the 1986 ease of the Disi Aquifer territories to farming companies**. Four companies—Ram, Wafa, Arabco, and Grameno—leased 100 km² of state land for 25 years to extract 70 to 80 MCM of the Disi water source free of charge (Ferragina & Greco, 2008; Barham, 2012). This action was part of a wider policy of binding customary water uses as a possible future option with Saudi Arabia for negotiating shared water resources. Although major attempts were made to increase the extraction rates, Jordan's area was nought comparable to that of Saudi Arabia (Haddadin, 2006). Such **discrepancies, in accordance with its equitable share, have brought about quite some criticism** (Salameh et al., 2014). It has been proven that competition for groundwater resources usually results in a "**pumping race**" (De Gooijer et al., 2008). Thus, the perception of scarce water resources drove into the final desperate search for all the sources of water for domestic and municipal needs before any other uses (Haddadin, 2006). The strategic shift culminated in efforts to pump water from Disi to Amman to address critical water shortages in northern Jordan's urban centers (Salameh et al., 2014). Jordan, **already facing extreme water scarcity**, responded by **constructing the Disi-Amman pipeline in 2013**, which transports around 100 million m³ (MCM) of groundwater annually from the Disi aquifer to Amman for domestic consumption (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013). The pipeline (325 km) provides drinking water to Amman, where water demand is concentrated, and allows for the partial recovery of over-exploited renewable aquifers in northern Jordan (MWI and BGR, 2019). Despite its importance, **the project was developed without formal cooperation or agreement with the Saudi government**, which raised concerns over the future management of this shared resource. The **absence of bilateral coordination**, coupled with environmental worries, also **resulted in the World Bank and other international donors withholding financial support** for the project (Ferragina & Greco, 2008).

Cooperation Methods

Historically, the only formal arrangement between Jordan and Saudi Arabia concerning the Disi aquifer was a **land exchange treaty established in 1965**, which granted Jordan access to coastal areas near Aqaba (Haddadin, 2006). Despite the absence of comprehensive agreements, **both nations participated in a data exchange forum related to the aquifer**, although Saudi Arabia was often hesitant to share information (Allen, 2010). **In 2006**, discussions between the two governments began to develop, culminating in **an agreement in 2011/2012**, that outlined extraction limits from the Disi aquifer, which aligned with Jordan's unilateral efforts to construct the Disi pipeline project. Although the project was completed in July 2013 without formal consent or collaboration from Saudi Arabia, **the Saudi government did not publicly oppose it, suggesting implied acceptance** of Jordan's initiatives (MWI and BGR, 2019). The methods of cooperation regarding the Disi

aquifer have undergone significant changes, especially following the **bilateral agreement signed in 2015**, which solidified Saudi Arabia's support for Jordan's use of the aquifer (Haddadin, 2006; Ferragina & Greco, 2008). The 2015 agreement **delineated two critical zones along the transboundary aquifer's frontier**. The **first zone**, designated as a "Protected Area," prohibits all groundwater extraction activities and mandates cooperation for any drilling of monitoring wells through the "**Technical Joint Committee**." The **second zone**, referred to as the "Management Area," permits groundwater abstraction exclusively for municipal purposes, with strict regulation of well drilling in accordance with technical guidelines. Furthermore, horizontal and inclined wells are restricted to prevent contamination of the aquifer's groundwater (Maass-Morales et al., 2024). However, the existing agreement does not put restrictions on annual abstraction quantities, and forecasts show that the practically usable groundwater resource is expected to be drained by the end of the century (UN-ESCWA & BGR, 2013; Muller et al., 2017).

The agreement between the two countries has several significant outcomes (Government of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and Government of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2015). Firstly, it establishes a **framework for the joint management of the Disi aquifer**, promoting cooperation between the two nations to prevent over-extraction and pollution of groundwater resources. The agreement **mandates the elimination of activities that rely on groundwater extraction in designated protected areas**, thereby safeguarding the aquifer's integrity (Figure 34). Additionally, **it creates a Joint Technical Committee** responsible for monitoring groundwater levels and quality, facilitating data exchange, and ensuring compliance with the agreement's terms.

Figure 34: The Transboundary Disi Aquifer Protected Area and Management Area which is part of Saq-Ram TBA (Maass-Morales et al., 2024).

Lessons Learned

1. **Importance of Historical Rights:** Meanwhile, the successful negotiation of the bilateral agreement in May 2015 brought all parties to realize the historical rights of water usage are extremely significant. The Jordanian government, through presenting the fact that it had nearly 49% of rights of the Disi Aquifer, proved historical Jordanian rights; they facilitated the Saudi approval for the project and maintained the status quo.
2. **Unilateral Actions and Diplomatic Engagement:** While Jordan unilaterally decided to develop the Disi project and, as well, engaged in discussing technical matters with Saudi Arabia, these actions show the effectiveness of using national initiatives and diplomatic efforts in combination. The strategy made it possible for Jordan to fulfill its intentions to obtain water security and at the same time achieve clearance from Saudi Arabia.
3. **Geopolitical Considerations:** The general political scope, in general, affected the way of trade and defense regarding the water management issues. For instance, Saudi Arabia aimed to have a unified Jordanian state as a measure of its position in the region's guiding principles, hence its support for Jordan's action concerning the Disi Aquifer.
4. **Data Sharing and Transparency:** The lack of detailed agreements among the parties and the fact that the Saudi Arabian government was not willing to provide the data for the aquifer indicated the creation of more data sharing and data institutions for better management of transboundary waters. By creating confidence through data sharing, relations can be improved, and conflict can be reduced.
5. **Regional Cooperation:** The scenario of an aquifer is an expression of what collaboration at the regional level in relation to the shared water resources management can look like in real-time. This finally highlights the fact that collaborative frameworks can be put into place even in situations where there are no prior overall arrangements, as evidenced by the meeting of the mind between Jordan and the Saudis.

5.2.5 North America

Examples from North America are represented by 2 river basins (Columbia and Delaware) and the Great Lakes.

Columbia River Basin (CRB)

Background

The Columbia River (Figure 35), originates in the Rocky Mountains of British Columbia, Canada, stretches approximately 2000 km before emptying into the Pacific Ocean (Cosens, 2016). It stands as the largest river along the Pacific Coast of North America and is the third largest in the United States by volume of runoff (Naik & Jay, 2005). The Columbia River is a major waterway in the American Pacific Northwest, draining an area of 724,025 km² across Washington, Oregon, Nevada, Utah, Idaho, Wyoming, and Montana, as well as British Columbia in Canada (Benke & Cushing, 2005). Although just 15% of the basin lies within Canada, it contributes 38% of the average annual flow and 50% of the peak flow (Shurts, 2012).

Figure 35: The Columbia River Basin (EPA, 2022).

The Columbia River has long played a vital role in driving economic growth and supporting agriculture in the Pacific Northwest. However, it is now among the most extensively altered rivers in the United States. However, the semi-arid conditions of much of the interior sub-basin necessitate extensive irrigation during the growing season to support agricultural activities (Naik & Jay, 2005). The river is controlled by multiple dams including Mica, Revelstoke, and Arrow in Canada, as well as John Day, Grand Coulee, and Bonneville in the United States. It plays a crucial role in hydroelectric power production and supports industrial activities (Kite, 1997).

Problems and Motivations

The problems of the Columbia River have a complex history, marked by **significant human intervention and environmental changes**. The rise of **commercial fishing** and the establishment of canneries in 1866 marked the beginning of extensive economic activity in the region. **By 1896**, the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers had developed several **dams and** started building **locks** at the Cascades as part of their efforts to improve river navigation (White, 1995). These early modifications set the stage for further **alterations to the river's hydrology and ecosystem**. **In 1948**, a rapid runoff caused a **catastrophic flood** in May, which destroyed the town of Vanport in Oregon (Barton & Ketchum, 2012). This event underscored the need for more comprehensive flood control measures, which later became a central focus of the **Columbia River Treaty (CRT) established in 1961** (Riley et al., 2020). While the CRT provided a robust framework for managing high water flows, it largely **neglected low water flows** and other critical considerations such as **indigenous rights, fish populations, and ecological health** (Hamlet, 2003). The **construction of dams** under the CRT had profound impacts on the Columbia River Basin's ecosystem. Dams obstructed access to 37% of historical spawning grounds for anadromous fish (e.g., salmon and steelhead), including the entire river system in Canada, **leading to significant declines in fish populations** (Cosens & Williams, 2012). Furthermore, the inundation of river and lake systems caused by dam construction in Canada resulted in the **flooding** of large areas, drastically **altering the basin's ecosystem**. These alterations had severe consequences for local economies, **destroying productive agricultural and forest lands, submerging cultural sites, and displacing** approximately 2300 people from over a dozen communities (Government of British Columbia, 2012).

In addition to human activities, **climate change** has increasingly influenced the hydrology of the Columbia River. The basin relies heavily on snow accumulation as a natural reservoir (Cosens & Williams, 2012), however, climate change forecasts indicate a potential **decline in water** coming from snow melt by up to 35% in the U.S. part and 12% in the Canadian part of the basin by 2060, which **could adversely affect summer energy production** due to insufficient artificial storage (Hamlet, 2003; Nolin et al., 2012). The combined effects of climate change and human activities have led to **numerous physical, chemical, hydrological, and**

biological changes in the Columbia River's fluvial and estuarine ecosystems. These interventions have significantly impacted the long-term trend of observed annual average flow, particularly affecting the seasonality of the flow.

Methods of Cooperation

The International Joint Commission, established by the **1909 Boundary Waters Treaty** between the United States and Canada, was initially tasked with studying the feasibility of creating storage facilities within Canada to provide flood control and power benefits for both nations (Mouat, 2012; Shurts, 2012). This effort led to the formation of the **Columbia River Treaty (CRT)**, which, although established **in 1961**, was not **adopted until 1964** due to significant challenges. These challenges stemmed primarily from the planned construction of three dams in British Columbia that would deliver most of the flood control and hydropower benefits to the United States (Cosens & Williams, 2012). **Negotiations from 1961 to 1964** between the Canadian federal government and British Columbia ultimately led to an agreement that British Columbia would manage the operation and benefits of the Treaty, with these benefits shared between the U.S. and British Columbia (Mouat, 2012; Shurts, 2012). The treaty **facilitated cooperative conservation and management** of the river between the United States and Canada, primarily focusing on **power generation and flood control** (Riley et al., 2020). **The Columbia Basin Fish and Wildlife Program (CBFWP)**, established **in 1980** by the Northwest Power Planning Council, was created to protect, compensate, and enhance fish and wildlife resources that were adversely impacted by the construction and operation of the hydropower system in the Columbia River Basin. The program was an attempt at **adaptive management occurred in the U.S. portion** of the Columbia River Basin during the late 1980s to early 1990s as part of a fish and wildlife restoration effort, but it ultimately was not successful (Cosens & Williams, 2012). **In 1997, the Columbia River Environmental Coordination Group (CRECG)** was formed as a collaborative initiative involving **government agencies, tribal nations, and environmental organizations**. Saving water quality, restoring habitats and managing fish populations within the Columbia River Basin are among the group's main goals (McKinney, 2026). It also furthers the **collaboration of stakeholders**, offers suggestions for integrating environmental aspects into planning, and involves the public to raise awareness and garner support for conservation initiatives, that in turn helps promote sustainable management practices in the region (Denoon et al., 2020). **In March 2014**, British Columbia **published the decision document** that articulated 14 guiding principles for potential changes or improvements to the Columbia River Treaty. These principles stress the need to address climate change and work with Indigenous folks and local communities going forward (Denoon et al., 2020). Both the U.S. Entity and British Columbia acknowledge a shared recognition of the necessity of future-dated flexibility in agreements and their implementation (Bankes & Cosens, 2014). Additional groups, such as the **Columbia Basin Trust**, the **Local Governments' Committee**, and the **Columbia Basin Regional Advisory Committee**

(CBRAC), on the Canadian side of the international Columbia River Basin continue to engage local communities and stakeholders (Denoon et al.,2020).

Lessons learned

1. Legal and Institutional Frameworks: Robust legal and institutional frameworks that facilitate stakeholder engagement and adaptive management must be established. Providing a framework for cooperation and conflict resolution, these frameworks ensure that the interests of all parties to the Columbia River Treaty are represented.

2. Community Engagement and Local Government Involvement: Local governments allow the representatives of regional leaders to also have a place in the decision-making process. Further outreach to basin residents is important for ensuring transparency and representing the interests of the community.

3. Embracing Adaptive Governance for Ecosystem Resilience in the Columbia River Basin: Adaptive management of the environmental changes occurring within the Columbia River introduces flexible inputs that have the potential to address new conditions in unforeseen ways. Hydropower production has historically come at the expense of ecological integrity, contributing to declines in populations of salmon and steelhead. This focus on ecosystem resilience means the river is able to accommodate variability and sustain biodiversity and underlines the need to balance the health of ecosystems with hydropower generation.

4. Collaborative Decision-Making: Stakeholders can come together and adopt collaborative decision-making processes to ensure fairness and judicious policy implementation. This promotes trust and leads to agreement on issues that might have otherwise been heated disputes, and it is critical to ensure smooth management of the Columbia River body's common resources.

5. Integration of Traditional Knowledge: Indigenous knowledge and perspectives can help guide sustainable water management practices that are sensitive to the needs and dynamics of local ecosystems. Many of these systems of knowledge have been built and honed for thousands of years and have the potential to complement scientific knowledge and practice in ways that are culturally relevant and effective, particularly given Indigenous relationships to the Columbia and surrounding ecosystems.

Delaware River Basin (DRB)

Background

The Delaware River, a crucial waterway in the United States, traverses the states of New York, Pennsylvania, New Jersey, and Delaware, with New York City (Figure 36) being the most significant upstream user (Mandarano, Featherstone, & Paulsen, 2008). The river receives water from 216 tributaries, with the Schuylkill and Lehigh Rivers in Pennsylvania being the largest among them (Kauffman et al., 2008).

Figure 36: Delaware River Basin (Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative, 2024).

The Delaware River rises in the Catskill Mountains (New York) and courses 531 km and through 35000 km² of rural and urban landscapes before emptying out onto the Atlantic Coastal Plain and into Delaware Bay

(Moore, 2021). The Delaware River Basin (DRB) drains areas in Pennsylvania (51%), New Jersey (23%), New York (18%), and Delaware (8%) (Kauffman et al., 2008). Despite occupying just 0.4% of the United States' land area, the basin provides water to 5% of the country's population, according to Williamson et al. (2016). (Williamson et al., 2016).

While more than 8.63 million people live in the Delaware Basin (Sayed, 2023); it serves approximately 14.2 million people for drinking, agricultural and industrial use (Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative, 2024; Suykens, 2018; Kauffman et al., 2011). The basin contributes over \$21 billion in economic value to the region (Sayed, 2023). The land cover within the basin comprises 55% forest, 26% agriculture, 4% wetlands, and 15% urban areas (Kauffman et al., 2011). It supports a wide range of water uses beyond domestic supply, including recreation, fisheries, wildlife, energy production, industry, and navigation. The watershed features a mix of land uses, such as forests, agricultural areas, and urban developments, as highlighted by the Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative (2024).

Problems and Motivations

The Delaware River Basin has encountered complex governance challenges that have evolved over time, requiring coordination among numerous entities, including 19 federal agencies, 14 interstate agencies, 43 state agencies, 38 counties, and 838 municipalities (Suykens, 2017). The close presence of large urban centers such as Philadelphia and New York City significantly harmed the Delaware River, negatively impacting both **aquatic habitats and water quality** starting as early as the 1800s (Moore, 2021).

In the 1930s, a significant **dispute between New York and New Jersey** arose when New York decided to significantly increase its use of the Delaware River as a water supply source for New York City. This dispute resulted in the 1931 Supreme Court case, *New York v. New Jersey*, which is considered "the most significant original legal case involving water issues in the eastern United States," (Suykens, 2017). The Court granted New York an allocation of 440 million gallons of water daily, implementing the doctrine of equitable apportionment, which remains legally binding on the involved states (Suykens, 2017). However, the states sharing the Delaware River found the **judgment insufficient**, as it did not establish a comprehensive management approach for the entire basin (Suykens, 2018).

By the 1940s, the tidal section at Philadelphia was labelled "among the greatest severely polluted regions in the United States" by the **Interstate Commission on the Delaware River Basin** (INCODEL, 1940). Philadelphia alone was discharging up to 350 million gallons per day of untreated **sewage into the river**, exacerbated by **pollution from wartime industries**. This **severe pollution** led to unprecedented anoxia levels (the absence of dissolved oxygen in a body of water) documented by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service in 1946 (Kauffman et al., 2011). **During World War II**, the river's pollution was so extreme that it corroded the gold braids on uniforms aboard the HMS Nelson battleship, docked at the Philadelphia Navy Yard (Kauffman,

2010). **By the 1950s**, the Delaware River had gained a reputation as one of the world's most polluted waterways, with oxygen levels during summer months often falling to zero (Kauffman et al., 2008). In 1952, ichthyologist Edward Raney identified the river as a prime example of how industrial and household pollution had devastated striped bass habitats (Kauffman et al., 2010). Despite various efforts to address the pollution, a **1973 study by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA)** concluded that the Delaware Estuary would **never achieve the designated use of being fishable** (Chittenden, 1974).

Methods of Cooperation

The unique blend of political and physical geography makes the Delaware River a notable example in river basin management (RBM). Its shared jurisdiction among numerous political entities, including some of the largest and most significant cities and states in the U.S., has turned it into a testing ground for institutional innovation over a much longer period compared to most other river basins. Additionally, its physical characteristics, such as morphology, estuarine dynamics, and the presence of mineral deposits, have significantly influenced the management challenges faced in the basin (Moore, 2021).

The **court's decision in 1931 regarding water allocation** in the DRB is considered static, meaning that any modification to this allocation would require reintroducing the case to the court—a complex and time-consuming process. Following this ruling, the states sharing the DRB recognized the need for improved collaboration and **began negotiations, which led to the development of several models** for interstate cooperation. These models **ranged from voluntary, non-binding approaches to more formal agreements that were legally binding** (Suykens, 2018).

The **Interstate Commission on the Delaware River Basin (INCODEL)** was **established in 1939** through legislative action to work alongside similar organizations in nearby states. Initially, the commission focused on addressing river pollution, but its scope expanded over time to include conservation issues, water supply demands, and other potential uses and benefits derived from the basin.

The **Water Resources Association of the Delaware River Basin (WRA)** was **formed in 1959** through collaboration among industry leaders, public and private utility providers, and water-focused organizations. These stakeholders shared a common goal: to guarantee public involvement in governing the Delaware River and its tributaries. By 1961, **the WRA had contributed significantly to negotiating the federal interstate compact that established the Delaware River Basin Commission**. In the decades since, the organization has continued to observe the actions of the DRBC and related agencies within the four-state basin region. For more than sixty years, the WRA has served as a steadfast advocate, bringing together diverse water users to safeguard the basin's resources and balance competing interests (Wizard World, 2011).

Continuous efforts culminated in the finalization of the **Delaware River Basin Compact in 1961**, which is a federal law and law in each basin state. The compact created the **Delaware River Basin Commission**

(DRBC), which is composed of members from state and federal governments, employs its own dedicated personnel, and operates under separate legal jurisdiction (Moore, 2021). The commission holds legal authority to ensure coordinated management of a river system, transcending political jurisdictions to maintain unified oversight (Godfrey et al., 2012). The establishment of the DRBC through the Compact introduced a groundbreaking strategy for managing river basins. **By 1963, INCODEL's** responsibilities and residual financial resources had been shifted to the newly formed commission.

Before the DRBC emerged, river basin management relied on two flawed approaches: either rigid top-down bureaucracies or underpowered committees composed entirely of state officials, like INCODEL. The DRBC broke this pattern by employing stronger authority, supported by dedicated personnel and operational independence. Central to the Compact was the mandate for the commission to design a detailed roadmap for water allocation and development across the basin which is a process requiring input from communities and industries alongside technical assessments of supply, demand, and pollution levels (Delaware River Basin Commission, 2009). This **innovative structure** merged authority once fragmented between state and federal agencies, creating **a hybrid governance model**. Over time, the Compact and DRBC's evolving frameworks have made ecological protection and cooperative decision-making prioritized goals, reflecting evolving environmental governance principles (Moore, 2021). The Compact allowed direct federal involvement by including a federal representative as a member of the Commission (Suykens, 2018), although federal involvement in the initiative has steadily declined over time. **Funding** from the federal government was **discontinued in 1997**, shifting oversight responsibilities to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as the designated federal authority. This transition was formalized under the **1997 Emergency Supplementary Appropriations Act** (Suykens, 2018).

Other significant cooperation includes the **Partnership for the Delaware Estuary**, which works to restore and protect the estuary through habitat restoration and **community engagement** (Partnership for the Delaware Estuary, 1996), and **the Delaware Estuary Program**, which provides a comprehensive management plan aimed at improving water quality and promoting sustainable resource use (Delaware Estuary Program, 1996). The State of the **Delaware River Basin Report** further assesses water quality and management strategies, offering data and recommendations for stakeholders (DRBC, 2008a). Various **Watershed Management Plans** address specific environmental issues, such as pollution control and sustainable land use practices, while collaborative **Water Quality Monitoring Programs** collect and analyze data to assess ecosystem health (Helsel & Hirsch, 2002). **The Clean Water Act of 1972** establishes the regulatory framework for water quality standards and pollution control measures, guiding cooperative actions among federal and state agencies (Cech, 2003). Furthermore, the **Delaware River and Bay Integrated List Water Quality Assessment** identifies water quality conditions and waters needing Total Maximum Daily Loads (TMDLs) for pollutants, reflecting a comprehensive approach to managing and protecting the Delaware River and its ecosystems (DRBC, 2008b).

The Water Supply Storage Facilities Fund (WSSF) was created to secure dependable water resources for the DRB. Revenue from fees on surface water withdrawals supports the fund, which finances multiple priorities such as covering the DRBC's portion of annual maintenance and operational costs for these facilities, and funding infrastructure upgrades. Additionally, the WSSF enables long-term planning to sustainably manage the basin's water supply amid growing demands and environmental pressures. **In 1988**, the members of the Delaware River Basin Commission reached a **tacit agreement** to allocate contributions from the signatory parties in the following manner: Delaware would contribute 12.5%, New York 17.5%, New Jersey 25%, Pennsylvania 25%, and the United States 20% (Delaware River Basin Commission, 2024). These measures have contributed to improved water quality and sustainable resource management in the basin.

Recognizing the need for long-term, nationwide assessments of water resources, the U.S. Congress has appropriated funds since 1991 for the USGS to conduct the **National Water-Quality Assessment (NAWQA) Program** (Fischer, 2004). Scientists in the NAWQA Program work with partners in government, research, and public interest groups to assess the spatial extent of water-quality conditions, how water quality changes with time, and how human activities and natural factors affect water quality. This information is useful for guiding water-management and protection strategies, research, and monitoring in different hydrologic and land-use settings across the Nation. The **Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative** was **created in 2011** to address challenges threatening the long-term sustainability of water resources. Its primary focus is protecting drinking water supplies for communities relying on the basin's surface water and groundwater. By identifying and analyzing critical issues, the Collaborative works to ensure these vital resources remain secure for future generations. This partnership brings together federal and state agencies responsible for environmental regulation and public health, alongside the Delaware River Basin Commission. The initiative also involves collaboration with municipal and private water providers, **nonprofit groups** specializing in watershed conservation, environmental activists, and universities conducting research on water sustainability (Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative, 2024).

In **conclusion**, the Delaware basin, which was once considered one of the most polluted regions in the United States, is **now recognized as a model for best practices in integrated river basin management** across the country (Suykens, 2018).

Lessons Learned

- 1) **Legal disputes necessitate the need for enhanced collaboration**, which led to negotiations and the development of various models for interstate cooperation, ranging from voluntary to legally binding agreements.
- 2) **The establishment of formal institutions** such as the DRBC marks significant milestones in river basin management.

- 3) **Cooperation extends beyond the formal institutions**, with various organizations and initiatives contributing to sustainable resource management in the basin. **Examples include** the Partnership for the Delaware Estuary, the Delaware Estuary Program, and the Water Supply Storage Facilities Fund. Collaborative efforts have led to the creation of groups (e.g., the Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative) that work to address the need for public involvement in river management, and water resource sustainability.
- 4) **The successful cooperation in the Delaware River Basin made it a model for integrated river basin management:** Integrated river basin management has resulted in significant improvements in water quality, which highlights the effectiveness of collaborative approaches in addressing complex environmental challenges.
- 5) **Continuity of financial resources:** The DRB exemplifies the importance of maintaining continuity in financial resources that are independent of the contributions from signatory parties. This financial independence has allowed the DRBC to operate effectively despite fluctuations in state and federal contributions.

The Great Lakes

Background

Spanning the border between Canada and the United States, the North American Great Lakes (Figure 37) hold one-fifth of the planet's freshwater surface reserves. This vast system, covering 24346 km² within a total basin area exceeding 76000 km², encompasses five major bodies of water: Superior, Michigan, Huron, Erie, and Ontario, along with their interconnecting waterways (Kittikhoun & Schmeier, 2020). Governance of these critical resources is divided between the Canadian province of Ontario and eight U.S. states including Illinois, Indiana, Michigan, Minnesota, New York, Ohio, Pennsylvania, and Wisconsin (Hayder, 2019).

The Great Lakes are central to the region's ecology, economy, and culture (Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement, 2012). They are interconnected by straits, canals, locks, and rivers, enabling the transportation of billions of dollars' worth of goods daily, including fuel, construction materials, and agricultural products, through these waters and into the Atlantic Ocean via the Saint Lawrence Seaway (King, 2020).

The Great Lakes serve as a crucial resource for industrial activities, agricultural production, and energy generation, while also supporting commercial shipping routes and recreational industries such as boating and tourism (Pebbles, 2020; Ducey et al., 2018). Beyond these economic roles, the lakes function as an essential source of drinking water, supplying over 40 million residents across the region with their daily needs (Great Lakes Commission, 2015).

Figure 37: The Great Lakes Region (Maps of the World, 2024).

Problems and Motivations

The Great Lakes face significant environmental challenges including **severe water quality degradation** due to pollution from urban, agricultural and industrial sources, inadequate water infrastructure, invasive species and habitat destruction, all of which are exacerbated by climate change (Mahdian et al., 2020; Pebbles, 2020). The **International Joint Commission (IJC)** identified that the lakes were under **severe ecological stress**, necessitating coordinated management efforts to restore and protect this crucial freshwater resource (International Joint Commission, 2013). Conflicts arose between the U.S. and Canada, as well as between individual states and provinces, over management approaches to **worsening fishery crises** during the early 20th century (Pebbles, 2020). Industrial expansion and urban growth across the region during the **1950s devastated aquatic ecosystems**, driving multiple fish species to extinction or near-collapse. **Expansive forests and wetlands in both nations were increasingly replaced by agricultural fields and urban developments. Pollution from mining operations**-stained stretches of Lake Superior's shoreline red for miles, while deteriorating water quality forced widespread beach closures (Hoppe, 2001). The opening of the St. Lawrence Seaway to Atlantic shipping routes and the catastrophic collapse of Great Lakes fisheries became central points of **tension between stakeholders. Water quality reached alarming lows in the 1960s**, exemplified by dramatic incidents like the 1969 Cuyahoga River fire, which drew widespread media attention. Simultaneously, excessive nutrient pollution caused eutrophication, depleting oxygen levels and creating ecological dead zones across the lakes. These crises underscored the urgent need for coordinated environmental action (Kittikhoun & Schmeier, 2020). **Disagreements** have arisen regarding the interpretation of the **Great Lakes Compact's** provisions, particularly concerning water withdrawals for agricultural, industrial, and municipal uses, as the states involved have differing priorities and economic interests, leading to **conflicts over the allowable amounts of water extraction and its purposes** (Great Lakes-St. Lawrence

River Basin Water Resources Council, 2008). One notable **interstate dispute** occurred in the early 2000s when **Michigan opposed Ohio's** proposed plan to divert water from Lake Erie to support its growing population and agricultural needs. Michigan argued that plan could violate the Compact. This conflict highlighted the differing priorities between the two states, where Ohio focused on meeting its water needs, while Michigan was concerned about protecting the integrity of the Great Lakes ecosystem (Great Lakes-St. Lawrence River Basin Water Resources Council, 2008). Again, **in the 1990s** Michigan's concerns about potential impacts on water levels and quality led to a **dispute over a Wisconsin paper mill** seeking to increase its water intake from Lake Michigan. This dispute resulted in **legal challenges and negotiations**, ultimately leading to a compromise that limited the mill's water intake while considering both states' interests (Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement, 2012).

Methods of cooperation

The governance of the Great Lakes involves multiple jurisdictions, including U.S. and Canadian federal governments, states, provinces, and local authorities, which can hinder coordinated management efforts (International Joint Commission, 2013). To address these challenges, various cooperative methods have been implemented over the years.

The shared waterways between the United States and Canada have long required cooperative governance, as actions in one nation inevitably impact the other. To address this interdependence, both countries signed the **Boundary Waters Treaty in 1909, establishing the International Joint Commission (IJC)**. This binational body was tasked with resolving disputes over transboundary waters and approving infrastructure projects influencing water flow or levels. Over time, the IJC's authority grew significantly with the binational **Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement (GLWQA)**. Legal frameworks like the **U.S. Clean Water Act** and **Canada Water Act** operationalize the GLWQA, first signed in 1972 after extensive negotiations. Revised in 2012, the GLWQA prioritizes collaborative restoration efforts and public involvement in water quality protection (Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement, 2012).

Under the GLWQA, the IJC gained expanded responsibilities, including monitoring compliance with water quality standards and advising governments on meeting ecological targets. These frameworks transformed the IJC into a pivotal institution for balancing environmental stewardship and diplomatic collaboration in the region (Pebbles, 2020).

In 1954, Canada and the United States finalized negotiations to construct the binational St. Lawrence Seaway, marking a milestone in shared infrastructure. The following year, the **Convention on Great Lakes Fisheries** formalized cross-border cooperation through the creation of the **Great Lakes Fisheries Commission (GLFC)**. This body coordinates sustainable fisheries management and joint research initiatives between the two nations (Great Lakes Fisheries Commission, 2019; Pebbles, 2020). Efforts to establish such cooperation

faced decades of deliberation, with over 27 proposals for transboundary governance frameworks reviewed before the GLFC's inception (Botts & Krushelnicki, 1987).

Complementing this, the **2008 Great Lakes Compact** established binding rules among eight U.S. states to prohibit water diversions outside the basin and strengthen regional governance. This agreement expanded the **Great Lakes Commission's (GLC)** advisory role in addressing water-related challenges (Great Lakes-St. Lawrence River Basin Water Resources Council, 2008).

Further initiatives include the **Great Lakes Restoration Initiative (GLRI)**, launched in 2010 to fund pollution control and habitat rehabilitation projects (Strobel, 2014). Region-specific strategies like the **Lakewide Action and Management Plans (LAMPs)** guide tailored solutions for ecological threats while fostering stakeholder coordination (International Joint Commission, 2014). The 2012 GLWQA update introduced the binational **Great Lakes Executive Committee**, comprising government officials, Indigenous representatives, and watershed agencies. This body oversees agreement implementation through specialized subcommittees targeting priority environmental issues (Pebbles, 2020).

Public engagement has played a central role in shaping governance strategies for the Great Lakes. It gained momentum in 1983 with the formation of **Great Lakes United**, a binational coalition advocating pollution solutions (Botts et al., 2018). One key initiative, the triennial **Great Lakes Public Forum**, serves as a platform for collaboration among local governments, environmental groups, industry leaders, and community members to address water quality concerns and exchange management approaches (International Joint Commission, 2006). Complementing this effort, **the Lake Ontario–St. Lawrence River Public Interest Advisory Group** focuses on integrating diverse perspectives into water management decisions through structured outreach and consultation (International Joint Commission, 2014). These practices align with the GLWQA, which explicitly prioritizes public participation and the inclusion of Indigenous communities in governance, underscoring a commitment to equitable decision-making (Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement, 2012). **The IJC** has further reinforced transparency through initiatives such as large-scale public consultations, including those during the GLWQA renegotiation, which engaged over 4,000 participants to enhance trust in governance outcomes (Denoon et al., 2020). The institutional frameworks governing the Great Lakes initially emerged from urgent responses to potential crises but have gradually shifted toward proactive collaboration and conflict prevention. Over the decades, these adaptive structures have allowed institutions to refine specialized expertise in water diplomacy, emphasizing cooperative management over reactive solutions (Pebbles, 2020).

Lessons learned

- 1) **Early recognition of shared interests and the need for cooperation is crucial:** Understanding the interconnectedness of the Great Lakes ecosystem and how actions can affect the other side of the border, the U.S. and Canada signed the **Boundary Waters Treaty of 1909** that established the **International Joint Commission (IJC)**. This early initiative paved the way for joint management efforts.

- 2) **Formal agreements and institutions facilitate effective transboundary governance:** Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement (GLWQA) and institutions like the **Great Lakes Fisheries Commission** highlight the value of these strong formal frameworks in coordinating policies, research, and management practices. These accords create a template for action plans and public outreach.
- 3) **Addressing diverse environmental challenges requires a multifaceted approach:** Different Acts along with initiatives emphasize the comprehensive approach required for water management. These initiatives highlight the joint responsibility of the federal, state, and local sectors.
- 4) **Stakeholder engagement and inclusivity are vital for sustainable governance:** The Great Lakes governance structure recognizes that multi-sectoral participation, such as indigenous, local, environmental and industrial perspectives, will produce more sustainable water management practices
- 5) **Adaptive governance and the development of specialized expertise contribute to long-term success:** The institutional arrangements in the Great Lakes have evolved and adapted to circumstances as they have changed and established a common technical experience of diplomacy related to water. Having this flexibility and specialized knowledge has enabled effective collaboration and conflict prevention in the management of this complex ecosystem.
- 6) **Collaboration and conflict prevention are key principles of successful water diplomacy:** Mature institutional arrangements in the Great Lakes region are focused on cooperative management and conflict prevention rather than conflict management or resolution.

6. Recommendations

This study aimed at investigating the role of water diplomacy in the management of transboundary water resources (surface and ground water). The key goal was to realize the lessons learned from successful stories of transboundary water resources management worldwide. Published literature across the globe was studied to realize the best practices of water diplomacy that contributed to the successful management of transboundary water resources. Although there are cases that are successful (e.g., the Rhine and the Senegal rivers), many of the transboundary river basins are partially successful (e.g., the Yarmouk River), while others are examples of no cooperation such as the Indus and Nile rivers. Such unsuccessful cases are not included in this study. This section highlights the major recommendations based on the investigations throughout this project. These insights illustrate not only the drivers of successful water diplomacy but also how they manifest specific examples to enhance the understanding of effective water resource management.

1. **Collaborative Frameworks:** Establishing cooperative frameworks is essential for effective management of shared water resources. These frameworks facilitate cooperation, information exchange, and joint decision-making among riparian states.
 - **Niger River Basin:** The establishment of the Niger Basin Authority (NBA) in 1980 provided a framework for cooperation among nine riparian countries, demonstrating the importance of collaborative governance in managing shared water resources effectively.
 - **Orange-Senqu River Basin:** The Orange-Senqu River Commission (ORASECOM) promotes integrated water resource management, exemplifying how cooperative frameworks can balance the needs of upstream and downstream countries.
2. **Comprehensive Flexible Agreements:** Formulating comprehensive and legally binding agreements that address both environmental and socio-economic aspects is crucial. Such agreements should regulate water distribution, usage, and incorporate adaptive management principles to respond to changing conditions. Water treaties need to be flexible rather than rigid. A renegotiation of the water agreement terms is a must due in large part to changes in population and the availability of alternative water resources (e.g., desalination and treated wastewater).
 - **Syr Darya River:** The "Agreement on the Joint Use of Water Resources of the Syr Darya River Basin" is a legally binding framework that ensures equitable water distribution and highlights the need for comprehensive agreements among riparian countries.
 - **Ganges River Basin:** The establishment of formal treaties, such as the 1977 and 1996 treaties, showcases the importance of comprehensive agreements for regulating water sharing and fostering cooperation between India and Bangladesh.

3. **Importance of Data Sharing:** Transparent and open data sharing on water quality, quantity, and usage patterns is vital for building trust among countries. Enhanced data sharing can lead to more informed decision-making and reduced conflicts related to water resources.
 - **Irtys River Basin:** The lack of shared data on water usage in China raised concerns among Kazakhstan and Russia regarding over-extraction. Open and transparent data sharing is crucial to mitigate such concerns and build trust.
 - **Lake Chad Basin:** Regular dialogue and systematic data sharing among the riparian countries can improve strategic decision-making and resource management, addressing geographical and political challenges.
4. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving local communities and diverse stakeholders in the decision-making process enhances legitimacy and effectiveness in water management strategies. It fosters a sense of commitment and ownership among those affected by water management policies. Non-governmental organizations play a significant role in shaping water governance, especially when perceptions of hegemonic behavior, as seen with India's negotiations, erode trust among neighboring states.
 - **Columbia River Basin:** Greater engagement of local communities, including involving regional government representatives in decision-making, helps ensure that diverse interests are represented, and transparency is achieved. Indigenous knowledge and perspectives can help guide sustainable water management practices that are sensitive to the needs and dynamics of local ecosystems.
 - **Delaware River Basin:** Collaborative efforts in this basin have led to the formation of groups like the Delaware River Basin Source Water Collaborative, emphasizing public involvement in sustainable resource management.
 - The case of the **Saralbhanga river** illustrates how local farmers and community groups, such as the All Bodo Students Union and Bodo Women's Forum for Peace and Development, played a significant role in advocating for their rights and needs regarding water use.
5. **High-Level Political Will:** Successful water management diplomacy and cooperation require strong political commitment from national leaders. High-level engagement is necessary to facilitate the implementation of agreements and overcome bureaucratic hurdles.
 - **Mekong River Basin:** The cooperation between Laos, Thailand, and Vietnam shows that strong political will at high levels is necessary to effectively navigate and manage shared resources, particularly when addressing geopolitical challenges related to water management.

- **Lake Tanganyika:** The establishment of the Lake Tanganyika Authority, which promotes dialogue among the countries involved, highlights the role of political will in fostering effective water governance.
6. **Risk Mitigation and Preparedness:** Developing robust plans for risk management, including flood control and emergency preparedness, is important for minimizing hazards and protecting communities and ecosystems from adverse events.
- **Danube River Basin:** Execution of the Danube Flood Risk Management Plan significantly lowers flood hazards and supplies strategies for efficient flood control and risk reduction, demonstrating proactive risk management.
 - **Niger River Basin:** Experiences in the Niger River demonstrate how adaptive management practices can effectively respond to seasonal floods and droughts, underscoring the importance of preparedness.
7. **Adaptive Management Practices:** Incorporating adaptive governance that allows for flexibility in management strategies is crucial to addressing the dynamic nature of water resources and environmental changes effectively.
- **Columbia River Basin:** The focus on ecosystem resilience through adaptive governance has allowed the Columbia River to manage its hydropower production while still maintaining biodiversity, showing how flexibility is key.
 - **Mekong River Basin:** The Lancang-Mekong Cooperation emphasizes flexibility in management strategies to adapt to dynamic environmental changes, highlighting the necessity for ongoing research and adaptability.
8. **Trust and Transparency:** Building trust through transparent communication and proactive engagement is necessary to foster effective collaboration and resolve conflicts related to water resources.
- **Brahmaputra River Basin:** Cooperation between China and India demonstrates the critical need for trust. Transparent communication and data sharing can mitigate tensions arising from resource competition.
 - **Lake Chad Basin:** Transparency in project publications has promoted trust among NGOs, government officials, and funding organizations, facilitating better cooperation.
9. **Shared Historical Governance:** Historical legacies of water governance can significantly enhance cooperation among countries. For instance,
- The 2015 bilateral agreement regarding the **Disi Aquifer** illustrates the importance of recognizing historical rights to water usage. Jordan's assertion of its nearly 49% rights played

a critical role in gaining Saudi approval, showcasing how historical claims can shape negotiations and maintain the status quo.

- **The Boundary Waters Treaty of 1909 between the U.S. and Canada** exemplifies how early recognition of interconnected ecosystems can lead to cooperative management efforts, preventing conflicts and fostering long-term collaboration.
- Experiences along **the Rhine** demonstrate how shared histories facilitate identifying common interests and establishing formal agreements to manage water resources effectively.

10. Role of Technical Cooperation: Despite geopolitical tensions, technical cooperation serves as a stabilizing mechanism.

- The Euphrates–Tigris Initiative for Cooperation (ETIC) and **The Joint Technical Committee (JTC)** illustrates that even under strained political relations, technical collaborations can foster trust and set the stage for formal agreements.

11. Addressing Power Asymmetries: The inequitable nature of agreements governing the **Yarmouk River** highlights the need to address power imbalances between states. Agreements often favor more dominant states, revealing the importance of designing treaties that prioritize equity and inclusivity.

12. Political Stability and Continuous Dialogue:

- Political stability is vital for effective transboundary water management. Constant dialogue, even in politically charged regions, nurtures trust and facilitates ongoing cooperation among water-sharing countries.

13. Collaboration over Conflict Management:

- Mature institutional arrangements in regions like the Great Lakes focus on cooperation and conflict prevention rather than merely conflict resolution, indicating that fostering a collaborative environment is key for sustainable water diplomacy.

14. Role of Scientific Collaboration:

- The integration of scientific research and advocacy, as evidenced by the efforts of organizations like **FNCA**, has been instrumental in promoting sustainable water management practices and informing policy decisions across various regions.

15. Cross-Sectoral Approaches:

- Addressing issues like gender disparities within water management initiatives demonstrates the need for integrated approaches that empower communities, as seen in **training programs for women farmers in Senegal and Mauritania**.

16. Third party engagement is instrumental in driving cooperation and joint management of water resources.

- Key initiatives for the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System (NSAS) such as the "Programme for the Development of a Regional Strategy for the Utilization of the NSAS" and the "Regional Action Programme for Integrated NSAS Management," both funded by GEF and implemented by UNDP, IAEA, and UNESCO-IHP,
- The **World Bank's engagement** in the Lake Chad Basin through grants from the **Global Environment Facility (GEF)**.

17. The Role of Institutional Support: The European Union's Water Framework Directive (WFD), for example, illustrate how transboundary water governance can acquire legitimacy and support through institutional frameworks. Such institutions can hold states accountable and incentivize them to comply with environmental agreements, making the governance regimes more viable. The governance of the Iberian shared water resources continued to evolve with the implementation of the WFD, which encouraged bilateral cooperation between Spain and Portugal through the Albufeira Convention.

18. Early Engagement and Conflict Prevention: The early engagement among riparian states and proactive dialogue is essential in preventing and resolving conflicts over water resources. They can also contribute to standoffs and undermine the development of solutions for sustainable water management.

7. Water Diplomacy Index (WDI)

The regional and international experts participated in developing the Water Diplomacy Index are listed in table 6. The experts came from different academic institutions, research centers, governmental agencies, and private sector. Twenty water diplomacy criteria belong to 4 key aspects of water diplomacy were derived from the literature and experts involved in the study (Table 7). The mean weight of criteria is in the range 6.5-8.5, where the importance of shared historical governance and gender mainstreaming scored the minimum, whereas four criteria scored the highest mean: institutional support such as joint water committees or river basin organizations transparency in data-sharing and intentions regarding future infrastructure, equity in water allocation: consideration for equitable distribution of water resources among all riparian stakeholders, addressing underlying political tensions).

In this study, five shared river basins were assessed for their WDI: the Rhine River Basin (RRB), the Columbia River Basin (CRB), the Senegal River Basin (SRB), Yarmouk River Basin (YRB), and the Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB). Table 8.3 shows the values of the Water Diplomacy Index (WDI) for each river basin. The RRB scored the highest WDI (80.40), followed by the Senegal River Basin (69.56), and the CRB (67.11), the ETRB (62.29), whereas the YRB scored the lowest WDI (31.77). When compared with the average score of the WDI for the five basins, YRB is the only basin below the average, while ETRB is

about average only. This to remember that ETRB is a common basin with the BPI study which scored below the average value.

Table 6: International and regional experts in water diplomacy.

No.	Name	Institution
1	Dr. Alexander Meland	IHE Delft- Netherlands
2	Dr. Ana Cascao	Consultant/Lecturer- Portugal
3	Armin Bigham Ghazani	Associate Environmental Affairs Officer at the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)
4	Prof. Aysegul Kibaroglu	MEF University in Istanbul
5	Dr. Jara Diego	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
6	Dr. Khalil Alabsi	Ministry of Water and Irrigation, Jordan
7	Dr. Hakam Al-Alami	Environmental Consultant, The Inter-Islamic Network on Water Resources Development and Management (INWRDAM)
8	Dr. Maha Al-Zu'bi	Regional Researcher, International Water Management Institute (IWMI)
9	Prof. Mark Zeitoun	Director of Geneva Water Hub, Switzerland
10	Eng. Maysoon Zoubi	International Water and Water Diplomacy Expert, Member in the Managing Committee of the Blue Peace Middle East Regional Mechanism
11	Prof. Mohammed Azzam	Project Director, Water Diplomacy Center Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan
13	Mohdhassan Faizee	Researcher/advisor at the Water Governance Department, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education, Netherlands
14	Prof. Mutawakil Obeidat	Director, Water Diplomacy Center Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan
15	Dr. Shaddad Attili	Lead Palestinian negotiator for water at Negotiation Department of the PLO, Palestine
16	Dr. Tuğba Evrim Maden	Policy Development Coordinator at SUEN Turkish Water Institute, Türkiye

The scores of each basin in all water diplomacy aspects are shown in table 9. The RRB received a full score in the technical and political water diplomacy aspects which reflect rich availability of information for the diplomacy about water, related resources and the environment and that the political process goes far beyond water itself. The Convention for the Protection of the Rhine Against Chloride Pollution (1976 Chlorides Convention) and the Convention for the Protection of the Rhine Against Chemical Pollution (1976 Chemical Convention) are examples of technical cooperation in the RRB. The Water Framework Directive (WFD), a

comprehensive policy framework designed to offer legislative coherence with respect to the region's water management and 1992 OMVS Convention are pronounced examples of the political diplomacy aspect.

Table 7: Key aspects of water diplomacy and the water diplomacy index criteria with their weights.

Water Diplomacy Aspect	Aspect weight	No	Criteria	Mean Weight
Technical (Total score=124)	4	1	Adaptation of Cooperation Terms to Changing Circumstances	7.5
		2	Continuous Assessment through comprehensive monitoring programs and robust data and information sharing mechanism	8
		3	Integration of Scientific Research	7.5
		4	Joint Infrastructure/Investment in Basin Management	8
Cooperative (Total score=288)	6	1	Importance of Shared Historical Governance	6.5
		2	Existing of Legal Agreements	8
		3	Institutional support such as joint water committees or river basin organizations	8.5
		4	Transparency in data-sharing and intentions regarding future infrastructure	8.5
		5	Equity in Water Allocation: Consideration for equitable distribution of water resources among all riparian stakeholders	8.5
		6	Conflict Resolution Mechanisms: Defined protocols and institutional frameworks for resolving disputes over water allocation or governance	8
Integrative (Total score=66)	3	1	Stakeholder engagement: Engaging local communities, industries, and NGOs	8
		2	Public awareness campaigns	7.5
		3	Gender Mainstreaming: Inclusion of gender considerations and empowering women in water diplomacy and management roles.	6.5
Preventive	3	1	Importance of Third-Party Mediation and Support (financial, technical, education, or trainings)	7

(Total score=64.5)		2	Collaboration Without Crisis (cooperation among riparian states even though there are no disputes e.g., political, environmental, etc.)	7.5
		3	Crises can be used as opportunities for proactive cooperation	7
Political (Total score=128)	4	1	Mutual Dependency Beyond Water (trade, transit, energy, agriculture, etc.)	8.5
		2	Addressing Underlying Political Tensions	8.5
		3	Existing asymmetries between riparian in use of shared waters, power (soft and hard), capacity, knowledge and technology advancement, etc.	8
		4	Affective Aspects/Shared Values (religion, ethnicity, language, culture, history etc.)	7

Full scores were also earned by the SRB in two aspects: cooperative and integrative. The cooperative aspect is an indication of the existence of cooperation and good governance to promote reasonable and equitable water use, while the integrative means that there are connected multiple forms and levels of institutions and stakeholders and the different types of knowledge. The Senegal River Basin Development Organization among other activities strengthened cooperation among the riparian countries. CRB and ETRB also scored high in the technical aspect which reflects the sharing of information about water, related resources and the environment. On the other hand, CRB and SRB scored good score in the political aspect which indicate that water is part of wider diplomatic setting and geopolitics. It is worth noting these basins have no regional treaty among the riparian countries. Remarkably, the Yarmouk River Basin represents the extreme end of water diplomacy, with a very low WDI, that is influenced greatly by the earning no scores for the political and integrative aspects. These are negative indications of water diplomacy among the disputed states over the YRB. Additionally, the cooperative and preventive aspects are low, while only the technical aspect showed acceptable positive indicators of cooperation.

The WDI highlights the significance of water diplomacy in enabling cooperation among countries sharing water resources, vital for conflict mitigation and enhancing sustainability. The analysis notes that certain river basins enjoy good degree of effective water diplomacy - such as the Rhine River Basin - while others like the Yarmouk River Basin have their own collaboration challenges in different aspects except the technical aspect.

Table 8: Values of the Water Diplomacy Index of the river basins.

River Basin	Water Diplomacy Index (WDI)
Rhine River Basin (RRB)	80.40
Senegal River Basin (SRB)	69.56
Columbia River Basin (CRB)	67.11
Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB)	62.29
Yarmouk River Basin (YRB)	31.77

Table 9: Summary of the normalized river basin scores (%) for each water diplomacy aspect and

River Basin	Water Diplomacy Aspect				
	Technical	Cooperative	Integrative	Preventive	Political
Rhine River Basin (RRB)	100.00	65.12	70.45	69.79	100.00
Senegal River Basin (SRB)	73.44	100.00	100.00	52.08	75.81
Columbia River Basin (CRB)	78.13	34.88	70.45	65.63	75.81
Euphrates-Tigris River Basin (ETRB)	78.13	65.12	70.45	69.79	24.19
Yarmouk River Basin (YRB)	73.44	32.56	0.00	34.38	0.00

Through a structured framework of assessment, political will, stakeholder participation, legal frameworks, and technical capabilities, among other criteria, is considered important for understanding good water management practices in the WDI. Findings show the necessity of including local communities, governments, NGOs, and international bodies in governance approaches to build an inclusive framework. Also, given the index's score is based on expert assessment, the emphasis on informed perspectives when evaluating strategies considering the challenges unique to each of the basins is important. The WDI points to areas needing improvement, particularly in politically sensitive regions lacking diplomatic efforts in cooperation, offering enhanced intervention targeting to leverage cooperation. Certainly, the WDI can equip policymakers with tools to make decisions involving resource allocation, conflict resolution, and partnership development with the intent to foster sustainable peace through sustainable water management. In general, the research emphasizes the importance of effective water diplomacy within the ever-connected world experiencing rising pressure on water resources, calling to attention the WDI as an important tool in promoting cooperation and sustainable management.

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